

SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH OF THE SCO COUNTRIES: SYNERGY AND INTEGRATION

上合组织国家的科学研究：协同和一体化

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这些会议文结合了会议的材料 – 研究论文和科学工作者的论文报告。它考察了职业化人格的技术和社会学问题。一些文章涉及人格职业化研究问题的理论和方法论方法和原则。

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复杂物体中的辐射效应及复杂性：起源、结构、成就与展望
**RADIATION EFFECTS IN COMPLEX OBJECTS AND
COMPLEXITY: GENESIS, STRUCTURE, ACHIEVEMENTS,
AND PROSPECTS**

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摘要：本文探讨了将复杂性方法论扩展到辐射对生物和非生物物体的影响领域时所面临的一系列问题。文章讨论了复杂性方法论的起源、发展历程、基本要素以及该方法的未来前景。

关键词：复杂性、协同论、协同作用、范式、涌现。

Abstract. *The article discusses a number of problems related to the expansion of the Complexity methodology to the field of radiation effects on objects in living and non-living nature. The genesis, history, basic elements of Complexity, and the prospects of this approach are discussed.*

Keywords: *Complexity, synergetics, synergism, paradigms, and emergence.*

1. Nature Philosophy Introduction

A very large experience of research in the field of condensed matter sciences (especially in periods of scientific revolutions) shows that the most serious judgment about their effectiveness can be based on the so-called P. L. Kapitsa triangle, the uniform filling of the corners of which indicates a correct strategy, both in the fundamental and applied aspects (Fig. 1); on the other hand, the uneven filling of the corners indicates a clear imbalance, and the ways of rational additional management of situations are clearly indicated.

Fig. 1 P. L. Kapitsa Triangle E – experiment, T – theory, P – practice

Regarding nanoscience and nanotechnology, from the time of their emergence to the present, success has occurred at various times and from different angles. To understand and use this understanding for successful assessment, it is helpful to consider the effect of learning about “new” from its inception to its application.

From a general perspective on the nano problem, it can be seen that:

1. Understanding the object of research;
2. Understanding the subject of research;
3. Understanding the methods of research.

Obviously, we are talking (about each of these three elements) about clarifying the initial plans as a result of information search; in particular, based on the methodological principles of a theoretical physicist, Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, professor, member-correspondent of Academy of Sciences of the USSR J. I. Frenkel: “Searching for the **new in the old** and revealing the **old in the new.**”

According to this synergetic methodology of scientific research, it is useful to study the history of science from alpha to omega.

2. Genesis [1–4]

Radiation physics of complex media is a classical multi-disciplinary science that combines at least three areas of knowledge:

1. Modern understanding of complex media in general, where the importance of structural properties is no less than that of electronic properties;
2. Knowledge about the characteristics of modern radiation sources that provide high intensity with a wide energy spectrum;
3. Modern understanding of the physics of open systems, which allows for an adequate analysis of the nonlinearity and strong non-equilibrium of combined effects.

2.1 Object of study

The history of the emergence and evolution of the science of “Nano” and the practical aspect of “Nanotechnology” based on it are studied. The beginning of these related aspects has been revealed: in 1959, at a conference (in the USA), theoretical physicist Richard Feynman (who became a Nobel Laureate less than 10 years later) presented his new view on the science of the Future in the field of condensed matter. He formulated a new idea that in the range between the size of atoms and the size of a hundred or a thousand times larger, there is an area where there is a transition from mesoscience to quantum science, i.e., from continuous to discrete (the first idea), and that ideally, larger entities (automata) will be able to produce smaller automata with new properties (the second idea).

In fact (and this was realized later), Feynman suggested that splitting an object “from top to bottom” and vice versa, synthesizing “from bottom to top” would not be equivalent (!). In essence, he predicted the idea of the birth paths of the “new from the old”; this (to a certain extent) affects the Principle of Correspondence of N. Bohr. The first implementation (with great progress) of these ideas was carried out almost 10 years later (the invention of scanning tunneling and force microscopes). At the same time, it is necessary to note the discovery of new carbon compounds (fullerenes, etc.). These talented works of scientists marked the birth of Nanoscience and nanotechnology (by the end of the 60s of the XX century). This completed the first stage of the birth of Nanotechnology. Drexler, 1986).

2.2. Research methodology [1,4]

In the second stage of the history of “Nano” there was a rapid development of these ideas separately to the fields of physics, chemistry and biology. The main result of this stage is the identification of common patterns, when the so-called transdisciplinarity appeared. In this phase of the birth and development of transdisciplinarity, gradually such new results accumulated so much that it was required to summarize in a fundamentally new methodology. And it was, indeed, born and formed at a conference in Santa Fe (USA) in 1977. There was legalized the concept of “complex object” and formulated the principles of science – “Complexity”, i.e. theoretical and methodological basis. This science was built as follows: each of the sciences (physics, chemistry, biology, mathematics) allocated several of their provisions in the general system of axioms (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Genesis of the concept of Complexity.

This concludes the theoretical and methodological basis of “Nano”.

2.3. Research subjects [1,4]

It is from these above-mentioned positions of “Complexity” that old (forerunners) and new phenomena and their applications began to be studied. Thus, it was understood that nanophysics, nanochemistry, nanobiology and nanomedicine are strongly overlapping (and at the basis!), so that *transdisciplinarity* has a concrete basis: “Complexity”.

At the same time, in the last quarter of the 20th century, scientists’ interest shifted from the physical and chemical properties of objects to their structure (i.e., composition). Over the course of approximately 20 years, specific elements of structure (composition) were identified and became the primary focus of study: fractality, low dimensionality, chiral symmetry, and hierarchical structure of objects. When these properties were studied in relation to nano-objects, it was then that the paradoxical properties of condensed systems began to be discovered on a large scale, and this is where the power of Complexity was fully revealed. This is the foundation of modern nanoscience and nanotechnology.

As a result of these preliminary composite data on nanoscience and nanotechnology, it has become clear how to teach modern nanotechnology: namely, the genesis and evolution of this new field, its subjects and methods, so that Complexity has become the connecting link. This means that it is necessary to master its specific methods in order to deeply understand and anticipate new effects and their implementation.

Our current understanding of Nano/Complexity is as follows (Fig. 3); it is clear that these ideas about Nano are very different from the original ideas.

Fig. 3 The current understanding of the totality of nanosciences.

3. What is the concept of “Complexity”? [1,4]

It is not difficult to notice that the obtaining of significant scientific results stimulates the emergence of generalizations that go far beyond the field where these results were obtained. Therefore, the progress of fundamental sciences has always been accompanied by the development of meaningful natural philosophical concepts. Moreover, philosophy, in its most successful manifestations, reflected not only the increase in the volume of objective knowledge about the World, but also the improvement of methods for handling this knowledge.

The progress of natural science is measured by the development of fields that have made significant contributions to the philosophy of science through the discovery of new laws of nature. The key factor is novelty, as refining existing knowledge does not lead to a departure from established concepts. Geometry, celestial mechanics, mathematical analysis, thermodynamics, electrodynamics, relativity theory, quantum mechanics, mathematical logic, and other branches of mathematics and physics have all played the role of “philosophy generators” at different times.

However, the era of extensive scientific development seems to be coming to an end. Transdisciplinary research is likely to take the lead. It focuses on synthesizing knowledge from various fields and applying scientific approaches to the humanities, social sciences, and other subjects that lack their own theoretical framework. Therefore, it is not surprising that over the past few decades, one of the main sources of new perspectives on the structure of the world has been **synergetics**, which has been focused on identifying universal mechanisms for the structure and

functioning of systems of various natures [1–4]. Indeed, synergetics has proven to be very useful for explaining and predicting non-standard effects in physics, chemistry, and biology. However, in the early 21st century, situations began to emerge where even synergetics proved to be ineffective, as the paradigms it united did not encompass a range of significant phenomena. A careful analysis of the reasons for the discrepancy between the experiment and the theory revealed a class of these experiments in which phenomena similar in type to **catastrophes** (“not scary” and “scary”) appeared. But in 1989, P. Buck et al. discovered a new type of catastrophe related to phenomena that involved **balancing on the edge of chaos and order**. A detailed analysis showed that a new, additional paradigm, called **self-organized criticality**, was required to explain them. Which was based on one of the modes in the already created concept of “Complexity”. As mentioned above, this concept itself (outside of the nano sciences) was formulated at the aforementioned Santa Fe conference, where it was understood and accepted that all experiments falling under the three paradigms (**self-organization, dynamic chaos, and self-organized criticality**) work particularly well with combinations of “nano” and its immediate successors, such as fractality, low dimensionality, chirality, and hierarchical structures (see Fig. 2 and 3). One of the properties of phenomena that seemed inaccessible was the so-called emergence, namely, the **process of the birth of something new**. A set of properties was identified that could only be explained by self-organized criticality, including the idea of scale invariance, which guaranteed large fluctuations at low frequencies, and more importantly, at small sizes such as nanoscale. Thus, it was discovered that “order through chaos” (Prigozhin) is more easily achieved at small sizes. An important element was the emergence mentioned above, flicker noises in different systems, regardless of their nature, non-secondary statistics related to the tail of the distribution, as well as the concept of “**integrity**”, which together led to the most important concept: open nonlinear systems characterized by the concept of integrity (i.e., a **single property** combining all the elements of an object), so that in the case of decay, avalanche-type fluctuations (“those” catastrophes) occur in these systems, the frequency of which (probability) has a uniform universal expression, with (gives exactly these values for a huge number of phenomena). The fundamental task of theoreticians was to build a model for various complex objects, after which (if successful) the mechanisms of the phenomenon are considered to be understood! It is very important that it is in nano objects, in the case of non-equilibrium processes, that the above probability was very often realized.

3. Achievements [2–4]

With particular success all these three paradigms (i.e. the whole concept of Complexity) were implemented in relation to the so-called hierarchical structures (the term itself was proposed, many years ago, by the cybernetician Ashby).

A characteristic scheme of all five structures, including hierarchical structures, is implemented in a variety of variants of Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Scheme of the extended concept of Complexity of the modern RPCM, in relation to radiation effects in complex environments (living and non-living Nature). Both basic concepts of synergetics and synergistics have been implemented in the five paradigms of all known radiation processes at the moment (by 2026).

A number of approaches were proposed to analyze these groups of phenomena. In our opinion, the methods of Stratanovich and Ito (80s of the XX century) proved to be the most productive. It is extremely important that this approach turned out to be unified for **non-living and living objects**.

4.1. An example from radiobiology [2,4]

In particular, it was on the basis of this approach – hierarchical structures we studied the destruction of RNA of the Sars-2V virus, which was the causative agent of pneumonia Covid-19. The complete mechanism of destruction in both quantitative and qualitative aspects is described in a series of our works – see the review of the works of the Nanotechnology Development Center for 2022. This mechanism of RNA destruction turned out to be associated with the effect of X-ray radiation, the absorption of a quantum of which causes K-ionization of a phosphorus atom, followed by an Auger cascade and a Coulomb explosion that destroys RNA. Thus, the concept we adopted was as follows: the primary platform of the hierarchical structure corresponded to the K-level of the phosphorus ion, and each

subsequent platform was involved in the Auger cascade, which led to the Coulomb explosion of the RNA molecule (all details are presented in this section below). This, in turn, leads to the inactivation of the coronavirus.

4.2. Example from radiation technology (based on LSF) [3]

Another important example of the implementation of the concept of “synergetics” but already on the example of an object of non-living Nature was the study of the radiation accident of the spacecraft “Phobos-Grunt” [2–3]. A detailed theoretical analysis based on the ideas of Complexity (synergetics) is presented by us in a number of publications, where you can find details and theory and “experimental” data. Another important and more modern example is the technological operations implemented in the Big Solar Furnace (Uzbekistan) [3]. The radiation treatment in this device meets all the properties of radiation Complexity. Indeed, it simultaneously implements a combined effect of the following 4 factors:

1. A wide (solar) spectrum of electromagnetic waves (from infrared to ultraviolet radiation);
2. Throughout this spectrum, there is an extremely high intensity of electromagnetic radiation;
3. The temperature in the focus reaches a value close to 30,000C;
4. It creates a negative temperature gradient along the radius from the center of the focus.

The LSF technique allows for the application of these factors in the desired combinations. We have discovered that under radiation exposure conditions, the LSF achieved a state of matter that could be classified as a fracton medium, with clumps of material of different sizes and dimensions. The individual chains had the correct dimensionality. Using powder fillers, it was possible to regulate the percolation properties of controlled thermal conductivity, which proved useful for a variety of technical applications. Interestingly, the observed properties and effects could be explained by a wide range of theories, including percolation theory and partial differential equations with fractional exponents (strange kinetics).

4. Prospects [4]

The tangible effectiveness of the Complexity approach already at the current stage of development of the RPCM (a small part of which was given above) makes it possible to classify in detail the **present** and **the future** of this whole new methodology, including its implementation – see Fig. 4.

The most important elements of this table are the following: 1) at the present stage, the importance of the structure of irradiated objects has turned out to be no less than the role of chemical bonds; 2) the Complexity methodology is implemented in two concepts: synergistics – based on nonlinearity and b) synergetics – due to nonlinearity and disequilibrium; both types of concepts naturally fit into 5 paradigms (“self-organization”, “dynamic chaos”. “self-organized criticality”, as

well as “inadequacies” and “network structures”. It is very important that these findings relate to radiation effects in both living and non-living objects.

We believe that this classification (Fig.4) is very well in line with Niels Bohr’s prediction: “the key to fruitful development often lies in the appropriate choice of definitions.”

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带控制求解右侧不连续非线性微分方程线性边值问题的渐近方法
**ASYMPTOTIC METHODS FOR SOLVING LINEAR BOUNDARY
VALUE PROBLEMS FOR NONLINEAR DIFFERENTIAL
EQUATIONS WITH DISCONTINUOUS RIGHT-HAND SIDES WITH
CONTROL**

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摘要：本文研究了求解具有不连续右端项和控制元素的非线性微分方程中出现的线性边值问题的渐近方法。此类模型在控制理论、力学、经济学以及技术和应用系统等领域有着广泛的应用，因此本研究具有重要意义。

关键词：渐近，不连续函数，Heaviside 函数，Dirac delta 函数，连续函数，控制，唯一解，扰动方程。

Abstract. This paper investigates asymptotic methods for solving linear boundary value problems arising in nonlinear differential equations with discontinuous right-hand sides and control elements. The relevance of this study stems from the wide application of such models in control theory, mechanics, economics, and technical and applied systems.

Keywords: Asymptotics, discontinuous function, Heaviside function, Dirac delta function, continuous function, control, unique solution, perturbed equation.

Consider the nonlinear differential equation in the form

$$\varepsilon y' = f_0(x, y) + \theta(P_1)f_1(x, y) + \varepsilon A_1 b(B)u, \quad \begin{array}{l} 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ 0 < x_1 < 1 \end{array} \quad (1)$$

$$y(0) = b_0, \quad y'(1) = b_1, \tag{1_0}$$

where $f_0(x, y), f_1(x, y)$ — specified continuous functions

b_0, b_1, A_1 — constants, $0 < \varepsilon \ll 1, P_1 = x - x_1$

$$\theta(P_1) = \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq x_1 \\ 1, & x > x_1 \end{cases}, \quad \theta'(P_1) = \delta(P_1) - \text{Dirac delta function}$$

$$\delta(x-x_1) \begin{cases} 0, & x \leq 1, \\ \infty, & x > 1, \end{cases}$$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x-x_1) dx = 0.$$

Rewrite equation (1) in the form

$$\varepsilon y' - \varepsilon [y(x_1 + 0) - y(x_1)] \delta(P_1) = f_0(x, y) + \theta(P_1) f_1(x, y) \varepsilon A_1 v(P_1) \tag{1_1)(1_2)}$$

Equating the coefficients of $\delta(P_1)$

$$y(x_1 + 0) - y(x_1) = A_1 \tag{1_3}$$

where A_1 — we call this the control equation.

Then the equation (1) has the form:

$$\varepsilon y' = f_0(x, y) + \theta(P_1) f_1(x, y), \quad 0 < x \leq 1$$

$$y(0) = b_1, \quad y(1) = b_2, \tag{1_4}$$

For $x \leq x_1$:

$$\varepsilon y' = f_0(x, y) \quad 0 < x \leq x_1$$

$$y(0) = b \tag{1_{4.0}}$$

Assuming $\varepsilon = 0$

$$f_0(x, y(x)) = 0 \tag{1_5}$$

The nonlinear algebraic equation (15) has a certain solution $v(x)$.

The solution of the equation (1₄) is sought in the form:

$$y = v_0(x) + \Pi_0 \left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon} \right) + \varepsilon \xi_0(x, \varepsilon) \tag{1_6}$$

Determine the initial condition for the function $\left[\Pi_0\left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon}, \xi_0\right)\right]$ in the form

$$b = \delta_0(0) + \Pi_0(0) + \varepsilon \xi_0(x, \varepsilon)$$

from here $\Pi_0(0) = b - v_0(x)$, $\xi_0(x, \varepsilon) = 0$ (1₇)

By substituting 1₆ into (1₇) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon \delta' &= \dot{\Pi}_0 + \varepsilon^2 \xi_0' = f_0(x, v + \Pi_0 + \varepsilon \xi_0) = \\ &= (f_0(0, v(0) + \Pi_0) + (f_0(x, v_0(x) + \Pi_0) - f_0(0, v_0(x) + \Pi_0)) - \\ &\quad - f_0(x, v(0) + \Pi_0) + (f_0(x, v_0(x) + \Pi_0 + \varepsilon \xi_0) \end{aligned} \quad (1_7)$$

Define the unknown functions $[\Pi_0, \xi_0]$ in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_0 &= f_0(0, v(0) + \Pi_0), \\ \Pi_0(0) &= b - v(0). \end{aligned} \quad (1_8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon \xi_0' &= -v_0' + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} (f_0(x, v_0(x) + \Pi_0) - f_0(0, v_0(x) + \Pi_0)) + \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} (f_0(x, v(0) + \Pi_0 + \varepsilon \xi_0) - f_0(x, v_0(x) + \Pi_0)) \end{aligned} \quad (1_9)$$

$$\xi_0(0, \varepsilon) = 0$$

Consider the equation (1₉)

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Pi}_0(\tau) &= f_{0y}'(0, v_0 + \Pi_0) \Pi_0 \\ \Pi_0(0) &= b - v_0(0) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

In the nonlinear term $f_{0y}'(0, v_0 + \Pi_0(\tau))$ instead of $\Pi_0(\tau)$ we substitute $\Pi_0(0) = b - v_0(0)$, then equation (2) can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Pi}_0(\tau) &= f_{0y}'(0, b) \Pi_0(\tau) \\ \Pi_0(0) &= b - v_0(0). \end{aligned} \quad (2_0)$$

Assume that $f_{0y}'(0, b) \leq -\alpha_0 = \text{const}$, $\alpha_0 > 0$

$$\dot{\Pi}_0'(\tau) = -\alpha_0 \Pi_0(\tau), \quad \Pi_0(0) = b - v_0(0). \quad (2_1)$$

The equation admits a solution

$$\Pi_0(\tau) = e^{-\alpha_0 \delta} (b - v_0(0)), \quad \tau = \frac{x}{\varepsilon} \tag{2_2}$$

By substituting (2₂) into the nonlinear term (2) we obtain $f'_{0y}(0, v_0(0) + e^{-\alpha_0 \tau} (b - v_0(0))) \rightarrow f'_{0y}(0, v_0(0))$ при $\tau \rightarrow +\infty$ ($0 < x \leq 1$), $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$

Then equation (2) can be written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_0(\tau) &= f'_{0y}(0, v_0(0))\Pi_0(\tau), \\ \Pi_0(0) &= b - v_0(0). \end{aligned} \tag{2_3}$$

Since $f'_{0y}(0, v_0(0)) \leq -\alpha = const$, $\alpha > 0$

$$\dot{\Pi}_0(\tau) = \alpha \Pi_0(\tau) \qquad \qquad \qquad \Pi_0(0) = b - v_0(0),$$

the equation admits a solution

$$\Pi_0(\tau) = e^{-\alpha \tau} (b - v_0(0)), \tag{2_4}$$

We introduce the notation:

$$\begin{aligned} g_0(x, \varepsilon) &= -v'_0(x) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} [f_0(x, v_0(x) + \Pi_0) - f_0(0, v_0(0)\Pi_0)] = \\ &= -v'_0(x) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} [f'_{0y}(x, v_0(x) + \theta \Pi_0) - f'_{0y}(0, v_0(0) + \theta_0 \Pi_0)]\Pi_0(0) = \\ &= -v'_0(x) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} f''_{0xy}(\tilde{x}, v_0(x) + \theta_0 \Pi_0)x \Pi_0 \frac{x}{\varepsilon}, \quad 0 < \theta \leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

The estimate holds

$$|g_0(x, \varepsilon)| \leq |v'_0(x)| + \frac{|x|}{\varepsilon} |\Pi_0| |f''_{0xy}| \leq C_0 = const.$$

Nonlinear differential equation(19) We write it in the form

$$\varepsilon \xi'_0 = g_0(x, \varepsilon) + f'_{0y}(x, v_0 + \Pi_0)\xi_0 + \varepsilon' \gamma_0(x, \xi_0, \varepsilon) \tag{2_4}$$

where $|\gamma_0(x, \xi_0, \varepsilon)| \leq C_0 |\xi_0|^2$.

$$\varepsilon \xi'_0 = f'_{0y}(x, v_0)\xi_0 + f'_{0y}(x, v_0 + \Pi_0) - f'_{0y}(x, v_0)\xi_0 + \varepsilon \gamma_0'(x, \xi_0 \varepsilon + g_0(x, \varepsilon)) \tag{2_5}$$

$$\xi_0(0, \varepsilon) = 0$$

The solution of the equation is equivalent to the solution of the perturbed equation

$$\xi_0(x, \varepsilon) = \int_0^x e^{-\frac{\alpha}{\varepsilon}(x-s)} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} [g_0(s, \varepsilon) + f'_{0y}(s, v_0 + \Pi_0)f'_{0y}(s, v_0)]\xi_0 + \varepsilon\gamma_0(s, \xi_0\varepsilon)] ds \quad (2_6)$$

The estimates hold

$$|\xi_0| \leq C_0 + C_0(b - v_0(0)|\xi_0| + C_0\varepsilon|\xi_0|^2) \quad (27)$$

For

$$b - v_0(0) \leq \frac{1}{2C_0}, \quad 0 < \varepsilon < \frac{1}{16C_0^2}$$

$$|\xi_0| \leq 4C_0 \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1$$

Then the nonlinear integral equation (2₆) has a unique solution. This solution can be found by the method of successive approximations.

Consider the nonlinear integral equation (14) for $x > x_1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon y' &= f_0(x, y) + f_1(x, y) & x_1 < x < 1 \\ y(1) &= b_2 \end{aligned} \quad (2_6)$$

Assuming $\varepsilon = 0$ from (2₆) we obtain

$$f_0(x, v) + f_1(x, v) = 0 \quad (2_9)$$

It is assumed that the functional-algebraic equation (2₉) admits a solution $v = v_1(x)$.

The solution of the equation (2₆) is sought in the form

$$y = v_1(x) + \Pi_1 \left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon} \right) + \varepsilon \xi_1(x, \varepsilon). \quad (3)$$

Determine from (3) the initial conditions

$$b_2 = v_1(1) + \Pi_1(0) + \varepsilon \xi_1(1, \varepsilon)$$

Hence $\Pi_1(0) = b_2 - v_1(1), \xi_1(1, \varepsilon), \quad (3_0)$

Substituting (13) into (28), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon v_1' + \dot{\Pi}_1 \varepsilon^2 \xi_1' &= f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) + f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) = \\ &= f_0(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1) + f_1(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1) + \\ &+ [f_0(x, v_1(x) + \Pi_1) + f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f_0(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1)) - f_1(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1)] + \\ &+ [f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) + f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) - f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) \end{aligned} \quad (3_1)$$

We define the unknown functions $[\Pi_1, \xi_1]$ in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Pi}_1 &= f_0(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1)) + f_1(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1)) \\ \Pi_1(0) &= b_2 v_1(1), \end{aligned} \tag{3_2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon \xi'_1 &= g_1(x, \varepsilon) + \\ &+ \frac{1}{\varepsilon} [f_0(1, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) + f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) - f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1)] \end{aligned} \tag{3_3}$$

$$\xi_1(1, \varepsilon) = 0.$$

Where $g_1(x, \varepsilon) = -v'_1(x) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon} f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) + f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f_0(1, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f_1(1, v_1 + \Pi_1)$

We introduce the notation $\varphi(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1)) \equiv f_0(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1) + f_1(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1)$.

Then the equation (3₂) is rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\Pi}_1(\tau_1) &= \varphi(1, v_1(1) + \Pi_1(\tau_1)), \tau = \frac{x-1}{\varepsilon} \\ \Pi_1(a) &= b_2 - v_1(1). \end{aligned} \tag{3_4}$$

It is assumed that $\frac{\partial \varphi(1, v_1(1))}{\partial y} \leq \alpha_1 = \text{const} > 0$

Then the equation (3₄) admits a solution:

$$\Pi_1(\tau_1) = e^{\alpha \tau_1} (b - v_1(1)).$$

or

$$\Pi_1\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right) = e^{\frac{\alpha(x-1)}{\varepsilon}} b - v_1(1), \quad x_1 \leq x < 1. \tag{3_5}$$

The following estimate holds:

$$|g_1(x, \varepsilon)| \leq C_1 = \text{const}.$$

Consider the function:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} [f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) + f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1) - f_0(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f_1(x, v_1 + \Pi_1)] = \\ = f'_{0y}(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) + f'_{0y}(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) \xi_1 + \varepsilon \gamma_1(x, \xi, \varepsilon) \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

The following estimate holds:

$$|\gamma_1| \leq C_1 |\xi_1|^2$$

Substituting (3_κ) into (3_ε), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon \xi'_1 = g_1(x, \varepsilon) + [f'_{0y}(x, v_1) + f'_{0y}(x, v_1)]\xi_1 + [f'_{0y}(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) + f'_{0y}(x, v_1 + \Pi_1)] - \\ - f'_{0y}(x, v_1) + f'_{0y}(x, v_1)]\xi_1 + \varepsilon \gamma_1(x, \xi, \varepsilon) \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$\xi_0(1, \varepsilon) = 0$$

The following estimates hold:

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \left(f'_{0y}(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) + f'_{0y}(x, v_1) \right) + \left(f'_{0y}(x, v_1 + \Pi_1) - f'_{0y}(x, v_1) \right) \right| \xi_1 \leq \\ \leq C_1 |\Pi_1| |\xi_1|, f'_{0y}(x, v_1) + f'_{0y}(x, v_1) \leq \alpha_1 = \text{const} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

The solution of equation (3_ε) is given by:

$$|\xi_1| \leq \int_1^x e^{\frac{\alpha_1}{\varepsilon}(x-s)} \frac{1}{\varepsilon} [C_1 + C_1 |b_2 - v_1(1)| |\xi_1| + \varepsilon C_1 |\xi_1|^2] ds.$$

From this, under $|b_2 - v_1(1)| \leq \frac{1}{2C_1}$, $0 < \varepsilon < \frac{1}{16C_1^2}$, $|\xi_1| \leq 4C_1 = \text{const}$.

The following theorem is established.

Theorem. Let:

1. function $f_\kappa(x, y)$, $\kappa = 0, 1$ — continuously differentiable functions;
2. $\frac{\partial f_0(x, v_0)}{\partial y} \leq -\alpha_0 = \text{const}$;
3. $\frac{\partial f_0(x, v_1)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial f_1(x, v_1)}{\partial y} \leq -\alpha_1 = \text{const} > 0$.

Then, under $0 < \varepsilon < \varepsilon_n$ the original equation (1), (11) admits the solution:

$$\begin{aligned} y(x, \varepsilon) = \begin{cases} v_0 + \Pi_0 \left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon} \right) + \varepsilon \xi_0(x, \varepsilon), & x \leq x_1 \\ v_1 + \Pi_1 \left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon} \right) + \varepsilon \xi_1(x, \varepsilon), & x > x_1 \end{cases} = \\ = v_0 + \Pi_0 + \varepsilon \xi_0 + \theta(P_1) (v_1 + \Pi_1 + \varepsilon \xi_1 - v_0 + \Pi_0 - \varepsilon \xi_0) \end{aligned}$$

$$A_1 = v_1(x_1) + \Pi_1 \left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon} \right) + \varepsilon \xi_1(x_1, \varepsilon) - v_0(x_1) - \Pi_0 \left(\frac{x_1}{\varepsilon} \right) \varepsilon \xi_1(x, \varepsilon),$$

furthermore, as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, this solution converges to the discontinuous solution

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} y(x, \varepsilon) = v_0(x) \theta(P_1) (v_1 - v_0) = \begin{cases} v_0(x), & 0 < x \leq x_1 \\ v_1(x), & x_1 < x \leq 1 \end{cases}$$

Example 1

$$\varepsilon y' + y - 2\theta \left(x - \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) y = 1 + \theta \left(x - \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) + \varepsilon_1 A_1 \delta \left(x - \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) \quad (1),$$

$$0 < x = 1$$

$$y(0) = b_1, \quad y(1) = b_2, \quad (1_0),$$

where $0 < \varepsilon \leq 1, b_1, b_2$ — given constants, $\theta \left(x - \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) = \begin{cases} 0, & \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \\ 1, & > \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \end{cases}$

$$\theta' \left(x - \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) = \delta \left(x - \frac{1}{\varepsilon}\right) \begin{cases} 0, & x \neq x_1 \\ \infty, & x = x_1 \end{cases}, A_1 - \text{управление пока неизвестно.}$$

Equation (1) can be rewritten as:

$$\varepsilon y' + \varepsilon \left[y \left(\frac{1}{2} + 0\right) - y \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \right] \delta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) + y - 2\theta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) y = 1\theta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) + \varepsilon A_1 \delta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$y(0) = b_1, \quad y(1) = b_2,$$

Equating the coefficients of $\delta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)$:

$$y \left(\frac{1}{2} + 0\right) - y \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = A_1 \quad (1_2),$$

$$\varepsilon y' + y - 2\theta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) y = 1 + \theta \left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right) \quad 0 < x \leq 1 \quad (1_3),$$

$$y(0) = b_1 = 2, \quad y(1) = b_2 = 3,$$

For $x \leq \frac{1}{2}$ from (1₃), is obtained:

$$\varepsilon y' + y = 1 \quad (1_4),$$

$$y(0) = 2$$

Solution (1₄), is sought in the form: $y = 1 + \Pi_0 \left(\frac{x}{\varepsilon}\right)$ (1₅),

With the initial condition:

$$\Pi_0(0) = 1$$

By substituting (1₅) into (1₄), is obtained:

$$\Pi_0(\tau) + \Pi_0(\tau) = 0, \quad \Pi_0(\tau) = e^{-\tau}, \quad \tau = \frac{x}{\varepsilon}$$

Solution (1₅) is expressed in the form:

$$y = 1 + e^{-\frac{x}{\varepsilon}} \quad (16),$$

For $x > \frac{1}{2}$ from (13) is obtained:

$$\varepsilon y' - y = 2, \quad \frac{1}{\varepsilon} < x \leq 1 \quad (17),$$

$$y(1) = 3$$

$$y(x) = -2 + \Pi_1\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right), \quad (18),$$

$$3 = -2 + \Pi_1(0), \quad \Pi_0(0) = 5,$$

Substituting (1₈), into (1₇):

$$\dot{\Pi}_1 - \Pi_1 = 0$$

$$\Pi_1(0) = 5 \quad \Pi_1\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right) = 5e\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right)$$

$$y(x) = -2 + 5e\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right), \quad \frac{1}{2} < x < 1$$

The unknown constant is determined from the equation

$$A\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = -2 + 5e^{\frac{1}{2\varepsilon}} - 1 - e^{-\frac{1}{2\varepsilon}} - 3 + 5e^{-\frac{1}{2\varepsilon}}$$

Thus, the solution:

$$y(x, \varepsilon) = \begin{cases} 1 - e^{-\frac{x}{\varepsilon}}, & 0 < x \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \\ -2 + 5e^{\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right)}, & \frac{1}{2} < x < 1 \end{cases} = 1 + e^{-\frac{x}{\varepsilon}} + \theta\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)\left(-2 + 5e^{\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right)} - 1 - e^{-\frac{x}{\varepsilon}}\right) =$$

$$= 1 + e^{-\frac{x}{\varepsilon}} + \theta\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right)\left(-3 + 5e^{\left(\frac{x-1}{\varepsilon}\right)} - e^{-\frac{x}{\varepsilon}}\right)$$

$$A_1 = -3 + 5e^{-\frac{1}{2\varepsilon}}$$

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} y = 1 - 3\theta\left(x - \frac{1}{2}\right), \quad 0 < x < 1$$

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 1} A_1 = -3$$

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科佩特达格野生药用植物的天然原材料及其合理利用
**NATURAL RAW RESOURCES FOR WILD MEDICINAL PLANTS IN
KOPETDAG AND THEIR RATIONAL USE**

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摘要：研究的野生药用植物具有开发草药产品的潜力。对科佩特山脉药用植物区系中一些具有重要生态意义的关键物种的生物资源和植物化学特性分析表明，它们在土库曼斯坦制药工业中具有潜在的应用价值。

关键词：药用植物，生物资源，生物储备，植物生物量，精油，科佩特山脉。

Abstract. *The studied wild medicinal plants are promising for obtaining herbal medicinal products. Biological resources and phytochemical characteristics of some ecologically significant key species from the medicinal flora of Kopetdag revealed the resource possibilities of their use in the pharmaceutical industry of Turkmenistan.*

Keywords. *Medicinal plants, biological resources, biological reserve, phytomass, essential oil, Kopetdag.*

Introduction. An urgent task of modern pharmacy and biochemistry is to expand the nomenclature of medicinal plant raw materials, the sources of which are widespread medicinal plants of the local flora. Despite significant success in the synthesis of chemical drugs and their application, plants continue to be one of the promising sources for obtaining medicines.

In recent years, medicinal and other useful plants of mountainous Turkmenistan, as sources of biologically active compounds and objects of economic use, have been investigated very intensively. Despite the relatively small areas occupied by the mountain ecosystems of Turkmenistan, the plant communities of this natural region are distinguished by the largest flora of medicinal and other groups of useful plants [1].

Research methods. Determination of the natural reserve of medicinal raw materials – according to standard methodology. Ethnomedical aspects of the studied species of medicinal plants of Kopetdag during expeditionary trips in 2020–2024 collected factual material and data from a verbal survey of the local population about the use of endemic medicinal plants in Turkmen folk medicine (“Ethnobotanical” and “Ethnomedical questionnaire”) [2–5; 7; 8].

Kopetdag dorema (*Dorema kopetdaghense* M. Pimen.) – is a perennial herbaceous plant of the celery family 150–200 cm high. Taproot monocarpic. The stem is cylindrical, tapering, round, branching in the middle into a pyramidal panicle, slightly pubescent. Leaves are grayish-pubescent, ternate-dissected, their segments in turn twice pinnately dissected into oblong-lanceolate sections. Umbels are 5–12-flowered, almost sessile. Blooms in May-June, bears fruit in June-July.

Grows in the foothills and the lower mountain belt. Settles on stony and fine-earth-rubby slopes, terraces, dry riverbeds.

In the Central Kopetdag noted: Germab, Gokdere, Archabil gorge, Vannovskiy, Neftonovskiy, Yablonovskiy, Kurtsuv, Babazav, Dushakerekdag, Heyrabad, Karaagach, Mergenolen, Kurkulab Arvaz, Gaudan, etc.

In the Central Kopetdag, dense thickets of the plant, despite widespread distribution, are infrequent. We described one of such sites in the Suncha tract. Here, an area of about 30 hectares is occupied under the thickets of Kopetdag dorema. Plant density ranges from 5–6 to 30–35 per 100 m².

The average weight of a raw root is 2080.3 g. The above-ground mass of plants is 929.6 g. The yield of air-dry raw materials is 30 and 28%, respectively.

Taking the number of plants on the massif as 36,000 thousand (on average 12 plants per 100 m²), we assume that the total biological reserve of air-dry raw materials at the site is 22.5 tons of underground and 9.4 tons of above-ground phytomass.

The above-ground mass of Kopetdag dorema contains essential oil 0.09–0.12%, coumarins, flavonoids. In the roots were found: resin 19%, terpenoids, coumarins (umbelliferone).

Dorema root extract has weak antitumor properties. Resin can be used in the paint and varnish industry. In general, the useful (including medicinal) properties of Turkmenistan’s doremata are still insufficiently studied [1]. The wide distribution of some species of the genus, as well as sufficiently high raw material reserves, make doremata promising objects for in-depth research and practical use.

For harvesting dorema roots, perennial, well-developed vegetative individuals are used, and for harvesting grass – generative shoots as well.

Roots are best dug after the plant finishes vegetation.

The grass is harvested at the moment of maximum development of the leaf mass, before it dries out. Cut leaves and shoots are pre-crushed and dried in small stacks in the shade.

Roots after digging are cleaned from soil residues and immediately crushed into pieces, no larger than 5–10 cm. The roots are dried in the shade or in the sun by active drying, spreading them in a thin layer and constantly turning them over. Dry raw materials are stored in bales or bags in dry, well-ventilated rooms separately from raw materials of other medicinal plants.

Thus, using the accumulated experience, when harvesting raw materials, we recommend annually putting into operation no more than 15–20% of plants on the commercial site, which ensures normal self-renewal of dorema thickets and its stability in the herbage.

Badkhyz wormwood (*A. badhys* Krasch. et Lincz. ex Poljak.) from the Asteraceae family is a semi-shrub 30–45 cm high. Subendemic of Turkmenistan [1; 6].

The root is taproot, woody. Infertile shoots are shortened, woody in gray bark. Fruiting shoots are numerous, white-tomentose, hard, twig-like. Leaves are densely cobweb-pubescent 1–2 cm long. The panicle is narrowly pyramidal. Blooms in August, bears fruit in November [6]. The total area occupied by wormwood is estimated at no less than 300 thousand hectares.

Grows abundantly in sandy and clay deserts, on the foothill plain and mountains. In the Central Kopetdag it is noted in its extreme southeastern part, while in the Eastern it dominates everywhere, occupying an area of over 200 thousand hectares.

For medicinal purposes, the tops of the stems (with leaves and flowers) of wormwood are harvested. Their collection should be carried out during flowering (August–September), tying into bundles; drying and harvesting – under a canopy in the open air according to a generally accepted technique or in a well-ventilated room, hung or laid out in a thin layer on paper or cloth. Artificial drying is carried out in dryers with artificial heating at a temperature of 40–50°C. The yield of dry raw materials is 23–24%. The finished raw materials are packed in canvas or paper bags. Stored in a dry, ventilated place out of direct sunlight.

The chemical composition is practically not studied. The above-ground mass of the plant is used in the production of non-alcoholic beverages. In Turkmen folk medicine, the green part is used for anemia and other diseases.

The productivity of the raw mass in the Manysh area, where the plant forms practically pure thickets against the background of ephemerum, is 8 tons/100 hectares, and the volume of possible annual harvesting is 8.2 tons.

Trispheric ungernia (*Ungernla trisphaera* Bunge) is a perennial bulbous herbaceous plant of the Amaryllidaceae family (*Amaryllidaceae* Jaume) 30–50 cm high. The bulb is very large, ovoid-conical, 15–20 cm long, covered with numerous black membranous shells. Leaves are strap-shaped 15–20 mm wide, glaucous, rosette-shaped. The stem is stocky. The spathe is membranous, colored light brown at the top, longer than the pedicels. Blooms in August, bears fruit in September [6].

Trispheric ungernia inhabits from the foothill plain to the middle mountain belt. Most often found on loess fine-earth slopes of the foothills. Usually these are sparse clumps, but the plant is relatively abundant in clumps. Noted in the Central and Eastern Kopetdag.

In distribution areas, ungernia usually grows in scattered clumps, without forming thickets. Such clumps stretch in a narrow strip along the foothills from the Eastern Kopetdag to the Archabil (Firuza) area in the Central Kopetdag, occupying an area of about 160 hectares. The largest coenopopulation is described in the area of the settlements of Pervomayskiy, Kalininsk and Kurykhovdan on an area of about 50 hectares. The average plant density is 10,450 individuals per 1 ha with a biological reserve of air-dry raw materials (leaves) of 8.4 centners. The biological reserve of raw materials on the entire area of the massif was 420 centners. In order to maintain a high vitality of the population, during the harvesting of raw materials, 1/10 of the plants is left for self-renewal, and the turnover of harvests is planned at an interval of 3 years. Under such an operation mode of the thickets, the volume of possible annual harvesting of raw materials is predicted in the amount of 126 centners.

Leaves and bulbs of trispheric ungernia contain the main alkaloid – galanthamine, as well as lycorine, hordenine, tazettine, pancratine. The sum of alkaloids reaches a maximum in the early period of leaf development and gradually decreases towards the end of vegetation.

In medical practice, galanthamine is used as an agent that relieves the residual effects of poliomyelitis, polyneuritis, radiculitis, as well as in traumatic injuries of sensory and motor nerves. Galanthamine is used to treat intestinal and urinary bladder atony and in functional X-ray diagnostics for stomach and intestinal diseases.

Ungernia leaves are harvested when they reach their maximum length – 30–35 cm. Usually in this case, collection begins in mid-April and ends by the beginning of their yellowing. Leaves are cut with knives or sickles, but not plucked by hand, as this partially damages the growing point of the bulb. The cut leaves are first stacked in small piles 2–3 cm thick. In this form, the raw materials are laid out in a thin layer on a tarpaulin or an open area and turned over 2–3 times a day with rakes or pitchforks, preventing them from getting wet. The leaves should be dried quickly, then they remain green. If drying lasts 4–5 days, the leaves turn yellow and black. In the finished raw material, the moisture content must not exceed 12%, galanthamine must be at least 0.03%. The shelf life of raw materials is 2 years.

Jungarian mullein (*Verbascum songaricum* Schrenk) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the figwort family (*Scrophulariaceae* Juss.) 60–150 cm high, densely covered with ash-gray hairs, highly branched in the upper part. Basal leaves are almost sessile or short-petiolate. Flowers are in clusters, the corolla is yellow, densely hairy on the outside. Blooms and bears fruit in May–August.

Dzungarian mullein inhabits rocky cliffs in the grass-forb mountain steppe, less often on fallow lands. Noted in Hojakala, Germab, Gaudan, Nohur, Gokdere (Chuli), Gendivara, Yablonovskiy, Kurtusuv, etc. [6].

Anthropogenic regression of the vegetation cover in Kopetdag noticeably increases the coenotic significance of mullein in the structure of plant communities from the foothills to the juniper belt. Its abundance often reaches values allowing mullein to form independent communities or act as a subdominant in a wide variety of formations. Thus, in the Dushakerekdag area, Dzungarian mullein in the rank of a subdominant, and more often an assectator, participates in the composition of feather grass-wormwood-fescue, grass-wormwood-juniper and feather grass-fescue-wormwood associations. On Sayvan in the hawthorn formation, mullein is part of the forb-wildrye-hawthorn association, in the maple formation – the redbud-wormwood-maple.

On the Sayvan massif, the total area with the participation of mullein occupies an area of about 50 hectares, including those with dense thickets – 30 hectares. The average density of plants is 25 per 100 m². The average weight (from 100 repetitions) of one model plant is 750 g. Dry raw material yield is 35%. According to our data, the biological reserve of the above-ground mass of mullein on an area of 30 hectares amounted to about 197 centners, the exploitable reserve (90% of the biological reserve) – 177 centners, and the volume of possible annual harvesting – 88.6 centners. In each site, harvesting of plant raw materials should be carried out no more than once every 3 years.

Thickets of Dzungarian mullein of resource significance were also described: Yablonovka-Kurtusuv massif – 25 ha, Suncha tract – 15 ha, in the Germab-Kheyabad section – 500 ha, in the Dushakerekdag area – 200 ha. The projected reserves of Dzungarian mullein raw materials in the Central Kopetdag on a commercial area of 1000 hectares amount to 300–350 tons.

In the roots of the plant, triterpene saponins and alkaloids 0.07% were found. The above-ground part contains essential oil, iridoids, triterpene saponins, alkaloids, coumarins, flavonoids; in stems triterpene saponins and alkaloids 0.07–0.09%, in leaves – alkaloids and other nitrogen-containing compounds 0.09–0.18%, anabasine, plantagonin, acetamide, vitamin C, coumarins 2.15%, flavonoids 0.5%. Buds, flowers, fruits and seeds contain triterpene saponins, alkaloids, coumarins and flavonoids.

It is shown that the decoction and infusion of flowers have a pressor effect and stimulate cardiac activity. Dry leaves and their decoction, as well as the juice of

fresh leaves – an analgesic and wound-healing agent for burns and tumors, ulcers. The ethereal extract exhibits antifungal activity. Insecticide and ichthyocide.

The entire above-ground mass (grass) and flowers can serve as medicinal raw materials for mullein. Both are best harvested during the mass flowering of the plant – at the end of May, the first decade of June. In the first case, the plants are cut whole, in the second – only the peduncles. The plants are laid on a tarpaulin in a layer of 25–30 cm and dried in the shade. Drying is considered complete when the stems break easily under light pressure. Dry stems are crushed and packed in bags of 10–15 kg. The peduncles are threshed with sticks. Separated flowers are packed in bags and stored in a dry room on racks.

Wedge-leaved ziziphora (*Ziziphora clinopodioides* Lam.) is a semi-shrub of the Lamiaceae family (*Lamiaceae* Lindl.) 20–50 cm high. Perennial parts of the shoots are woody, branched. Annual twigs are numerous, thin, herbaceous. The whole plant is short-pubescent. Leaves are from ovate-oblong to oblong and oblong-lanceolate, short-pointed at the apex. Inflorescences are located at the tops of the stems, capitate, multi-flowered. The corolla is light lilac. Blooms in May–July, bears fruit in July–August [6].

We investigated in detail two sites with ziziphora thickets of interest from the point of view of harvesting raw materials. They are located in the western part of the Central Kopetdag.

The first massif is located on a gentle southeastern slope near the Goshaarcha locality, adjacent to the buffer zone of the Sunt-Hasardag State Nature Reserve. The tract and the adjacent territory have served as a distant pasture for many years, which directly affects the vegetation cover.

We identified the structural composition of the ziziphora-thyme association on a transect area of 100 m² (25x4 m). By size, the plants were divided into classes: I – bush diameter over 50 cm, II – from 50 to 30 cm, III – from 30 to 10 cm. In the Goshaarcha tract, an area of 10–12 hectares is occupied by ziziphora thickets, including potentially highly productive ones – 5–6 hectares, on which the exploitable reserve of raw materials was calculated. The volume of possible annual harvesting of raw materials was taken by us as 4/5 of the exploitable. 1/5 of the adult plants remains for seed self-renewal of the thickets.

The exploitable reserve of raw materials on an area of 6 hectares was: ziziphora – 12.48 centners. The volume of possible harvesting is 9.98 centners.

The second commercial massif of thickets is located 3–4 km south of the Sayvan settlement. It occupies the territory of degraded pastures at altitudes of 1300–1400 m above sea level. Ziziphora communities are part of the forb-grass formation prevailing on the Sayvan-Sumbar plateau. The area of thickets here is estimated at 50 hectares, half of which is suitable for harvesting raw materials.

The area of the commercial array of thickets was established by us at 25 hectares. The exploitable raw material reserve was: ziziphora – 95.3 centners, the volume of possible annual harvesting – 76.2 centners.

Under the conditions of the Central Kopetdag, the essential oil content in the aerial part of ziziphora is quite stable and amounts to 0.50–0.56%. Among other biologically active compounds, alkaloids, flavonoids, coumarins, lactones and saponins were found in ziziphora. Seeds contain up to 10% fatty oil.

Ziziphora raw materials are traditionally used in perfumery and medicine, especially for obtaining menthol. As a medicinal plant, it is used for throat diseases in children, stomach pain, nausea, as a diuretic. Flower extract is recommended for stomach catarrh. The multi-purpose use of ziziphora raw materials led to the introduction of the plant into culture.

It has been established that after the industrial harvesting of raw materials, ziziphora thickets are restored within 1–2 years. Harvesting of raw materials is carried out during the period of mass flowering of plants. Above-ground shoots are cut at a height of 2–3 cm from the soil surface. Plants must not be pulled out by the roots. The collected raw materials are dried in the open air, but necessarily in the shade, spread in a layer of 5–7 cm on a tarpaulin and mixed frequently. During the drying process, the raw material loses up to 43% of its essential oil, therefore, for the purpose of its extraction, it is desirable to process the plants fresh. The shelf life of dry raw materials is 3 years.

Transcaspian thyme (*Thymus transcaspicus* Klok.) is a semi-shrub of the Lamiaceae family 10–20 cm high. The plant is highly branched from the base, the stems are ascending, highly branched. Herbaceous flower-bearing stems are whitish from dense pubescence. Leaves are oblong-ovate or ovate. Flowers are twisted into dense heads located at the ends of branches. The corolla is pink or almost white. Blooms in June-July, bears fruit in July-August [6].

In the Goshaarcha tract, an area of 12 hectares is occupied by thyme thickets. The exploitable reserve of raw materials was: thyme – 17.70 centners, the volume of possible annual harvesting – 14.16 centners.

In thyme herb organic acids 8.38–8.54%, essential oil 0.3–1.2%, saponins, alkaloids 0.03–0.08%, vitamins: C and carotene, tannins 2.34–4.56%, coumarins, flavonoids 0.28–0.49% were found.

Herb infusion, liquid extract, thyme essential oil is a good antiseptic and disinfectant. Essential oil exhibits antibacterial activity. Since ancient times it has been used as a spicy plant.

Methods of harvesting, drying and storage of raw materials are similar to wedge-leaved ziziphora.

Lavender-leaved betony (*Stachys lavandulifolia* Vahl) is a semi-shrub of the Lamiaceae family 15–30 cm high with branching woody shoots, with numerous

ascending short stems. The plant is pubescent with long white hairs. Leaves are from lanceolate to linear, also pubescent. Flowers are 4–6 in whorls. The corolla is bright pink. Blooms in April–June (July), bears fruit from July.

Lavender-leaved betony grows in the steppe and semi-steppe mountain belts, on rocky slopes and on a fine-earth-rubbly substrate, at altitudes from 600 to 2800 m above sea level. It is very typical for the plant to settle and develop along fissures of faults and cracks on rocky platforms, where humus accumulates and favorable conditions are created for seed renewal. Such ribbon coenoses, forming peculiar micro-clumps, create the most productive communities of lavender-leaved betony.

In the Central Kopetdag, lavender-leaved betony often grows in the same formations as Turkmen betony, but they practically do not form joint communities. The plant prefers open communities of the petrophytic series. Nevertheless, the characteristic plant species accompanying Turkmen betony can also be cited for its congeneric participant.

The raw material resources of lavender-leaved betony in the Central Kopetdag are limited. Its communities usually represent strongly thinned clump-type thickets. Usually such clumps are formed due to the growth of rhizomes of several mother plants, each of which forms a clone with 5–10 above-ground (partial) shoots, 7–12 cm high. Both vegetative and generative individuals are represented in the clumps in approximately the same ratio. If the total area of plant distribution on the massif is 100–120 hectares, then only 1–2 hectares can be of interest as an object for harvesting raw materials (Table 1).

Table 1. Yield of raw mass of lavender-leaved betony in the Central Kopetdag.

Suyulikli massif

Replication	Number of plants per 100 m ²	Raw material weight of model plant, g/100 m ²		Raw material weight of model plant, g/100 m ²		Stock of raw materials, dry c/ha
		raw	a dry	raw	a dry	
1	54	144.7	69.5	781.4	375.3	3.8
2	103	210.4	101.0	217.1	1040.3	10.4
3	41	98.0	47.0	401.8	192.7	1.9
4	62	142.3	68.3	882.3	423.5	4.2
5	30	70.1	33.	210.3	100.8	1.0
Mean:	58	133.1	3.9	888.6	426.5	4.3

As can be seen from the table, on the Suyulikli massif on an area of 1 ha, the exploitable reserve of lavender-leaved betony raw materials was 4.3 centners, and the volume of possible annual harvesting was 3.4 centners of air-dry raw materials.

Besides the described massif, lavender-leaved betony in the Central Kopetdag with relatively high abundance is noted in the area of Dushakerekdag, Chopandag, Arvaz.

In the herb of lavender-leaved betony found: essential oil 0.04–0.15%, iridoids (ajugol, ajugoside, harpagide, etc.).

A decoction of inflorescences is an ancient Persian remedy for stomach cramps and diarrhea. In Turkmen folk medicine, a decoction of lavender-leaved betony and chamomile is often used as a labor-stimulating agent.

The raw material for lavender-leaved betony is the aerial part (grass), harvested during the period of mass flowering of plants (April–June). Plant stems are cut at ground level, trying not to damage the root system. At least 1/5 of the plants are left for self-renewal. The collected raw materials are dried in the open air in the shade to a moisture content of 13%. It is stored in dry adapted rooms on racks.

Common harmel (*Peganum harmala* L.) is a perennial herbaceous plant of the Nitrariaceae (Peganaceae Tiegh.) family 40–70 cm high. A plant with a strong odor. The taproot is up to 2–3 m long, multi-headed, bearing many stems. Stems are bare, smooth, herbaceous, furrowed, highly branched. Leaves are deeply dissected with narrow lobes. Flowers are at the ends of branches. The corolla is whitish-yellow. Blooms in May–July, seeds ripen in late July, August [6].

Harmel is widely distributed on the plains of the desert, foothills and mountains up to 2800 m above sea level. A ruderal weed growing everywhere on clay and sandy loam degraded soils. Occurs mainly in the form of thickets, especially on pastures and heavily grazed ranges, in watering and cattle resting areas. In oases it is often represented on fallows, near dwellings and along roads.

As a weed, ruderal plant, harmel in the Central Kopetdag is quite widespread, although in density of thickets, productivity and occupied area it is inferior to its plain communities. Quite dense accumulations of harmel were described by us in the Sayvan-Desht area, where they occupy an area of at least 200 hectares. Harmel occupies about 10–12 hectares in the Tejeve tract, and in the Kurichay area near the Suncha settlement, it forms almost pure thickets in combination with Kopetdag wormwood on an area of 200–250 hectares (Table 2).

Thus, if we take the surveyed area of harmel thickets in the Sayvan-Desht, Tejeve and Kurichay areas for 500 hectares, and the average seed yield for 150 kg/ha, then their total reserve in this territory will be 750 centners, and the volume of possible annual harvesting – 500 centners.

The medicinal raw material in harmel is usually the seeds, which contain 3.5–6% total alkaloids, 60% of which is harmaline, about 30% harmine and in small amounts harmalol, peganine and deoxypeganine. The herb of the plant contains 1.5–3% alkaloids, 60% of which is peganine and vasicinol. Other alkaloids were also found in the plant in small amounts. The roots of the plant also contain

alkaloids – 2.15–2.70%, the main one being harmine. Seeds, in addition, contain coloring matter and 17/14.3% fatty oil.

Table 2. Resource characteristic of common harmel thickets in the Central Kopetdag

Plants	Amount per 100 m ²	Height, cm	Crown diameter, cm	Seed yield		
				of one plant	100 m ² /g	kg/ha
Tejeve tract						
I class	11	38	75x75	22.2	244.2	24.4
II class	11	38	50x40	10.3	113.3	11.3
III class	8	25	35x30	6.4	51.2	5.1
Total:	30				408.7	40.8
Kurichay tract						
I class	10	45	70x80	42.2	422.0	42.2
II class	118	30	45x50	12.4	1463.2	14.3
III class	101	20	25x30	8.8	888.8	88.9
Total:	230				2774.0	277.4

The drug deoxyepiganine hydrochloride obtained from harmel has an anticholinesterase property and is used to treat various forms of myopathy and myasthenia gravis, as well as a laxative for chronic constipation and intestinal atony. In Turkmen folk medicine, a decoction of the aerial part is used for neurasthenia, epilepsy, syphilis, malaria, gastrointestinal diseases. Externally – baths for scabies, rheumatism, skin diseases. Enhances potency. Lactogenic. Seeds are a sedative and hypnotic, abortifacient and diuretic. Juice resolves cataracts on the eyes. Insecticidal and poisonous plant.

Harvesting of harmel seeds is carried out at the moment of their full biological maturity – starting from the second half of August. On clean and dense thickets, mechanized harvesting of seeds is possible. The upper part of the plant shoots with fruit capsules is mowed or cut with a sickle. They are then taken to the kharman and after additional drying (if necessary), the seeds are threshed and winnowed in the usual way. Clean seeds are packed in bags of 20–25 kg. Stored in a dry and ventilated room on racks separately from other medicinal plants.

The above-ground part (grass) of harmel is harvested early in spring during mass budding and the beginning of plant flowering. Raw materials are dried in the shade under canopies. The grass is harvested on the same plot with an interval of 1–2 years. Shelf life of raw materials is 2 years.

Subcapitate dragonhead (*Dracocephalum subcapitatum* (O. Kuntze) Lipsky) is a perennial herbaceous plant or semi-shrub of the Lamiaceae family 15–30 cm

high, with a strong woody rhizome, numerous stems, velvety-pubescent. Stems are simple, unbranched, woody in the lower part. Leaves are entire and with entire margins, about 10–12 mm long, covered with pitted glands. Flowers are arranged in twos at the tops of the stems. The corolla is up to 25 mm long, hairy, whitish-yellowish. Blooms in June–July, bears fruit in July–August [6].

Dragonhead grows on rocky and rubbly slopes and rocks at an altitude of 1000–2800 m above sea level in the belt of steppes, upland xerophytes and juniper forests. Occurs only in the South-Western and Central Kopetdag.

In the South-Western Kopetdag the plant occurs on Hasardag, Yoldere, Aydere, etc. In the Central Kopetdag dragonhead is noted near Nohur, Karavul, in Ipaykala, Arvaz, Sarymsakly, Degirmenli (Cool), Suyulikli, Misinev, Germab, Dushakerekdag, Kheyrabad, Chaek, Chopandag, Gaudan, Asylma, etc. [6].

Does not form thickets of industrial significance.

In the above-ground mass of dragonhead found essential oil 1.38–3.31 % of original composition, saponins, alkaloids, coumarins 0.43 %, flavonoids 0.27 %.

Essential oil exhibits antibacterial activity. Raw materials are included in the formulation of new soft drinks, can be used in the perfumery industry.

Harvesting of raw materials should be limited.

Thus, the studied species of wild medicinal plants of Kopetdag are promising for obtaining herbal medicinal products. Biological resources and phytochemical characteristics of some ecologically significant key species of medicinal plants of the Kopetdag flora revealed the resource possibilities of their use in the pharmaceutical industry of Turkmenistan.

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非平衡热力学视角下的地球气候变化
EARTH'S CLIMATE CHANGE FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF
NONEQUILIBRIUM THERMODYNAMICS

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摘要：本文基于非平衡热力学系统演化的一般规律，分析了影响大气状态和相应气候的过程。结果表明，从非平衡热力学的角度来看，大气中发生的这些过程与瑞利-贝纳德对流过程中发生的过程非常接近。本文通过比较不同自然因素和人为因素对地球气候的影响，分析了它们在大气中产生的熵值。结果表明，由于温室效应增强，目前到达大气层上边界的入射太阳辐射比向外辐射的长波辐射多 0.436 W/m^2 ；由于反照率降低，反射的短波辐射比入射的长波辐射多 0.0475 W/m^2 。全球海洋加速变暖的原因在于大气中二氧化碳浓度加速增长，而二氧化碳在海洋中的溶解度降低又加剧了温室效应，并通过反馈机制加速了海洋-大气系统温度的升高。本文从非平衡热力学的角度解释了大气温度在二氧化碳浓度持续增加的情况下出现的停滞现象。

关键词：地球气候，非平衡热力学，滞后现象，熵产生，人为过程，全球变暖停滞

Abstract. *Based on the general laws of evolution of nonequilibrium thermodynamic systems, the processes influencing the state of the atmosphere and the corresponding climate are analyzed. It is shown that from the standpoint of nonequilibrium thermodynamics, the processes occurring in the atmosphere are close to the processes occurring during Rayleigh-Bénard convection. The effects of different natural and anthropogenic factors on the Earth's climate are compared by the amount of entropy production in the atmosphere from each of them. It is shown that the incoming solar radiation at the upper boundary of the atmosphere currently exceeds the outgoing long-wave radiation into space by $0,436 \text{ W/m}^2$ due to an increase in the greenhouse effect and the reflected short-wave radiation by $0,0475 \text{ W/m}^2$ due to a decrease in albedo. The accelerated warming of the World Ocean is explained by the accelerated growth of CO_2 concentrations in the atmosphere due to a decrease in its solubility in the ocean, which increases the greenhouse effect and accelerates the growth of the temperature of the*

ocean-atmosphere system due to feedback. From the standpoint of nonequilibrium thermodynamics, the pauses that arise in the growth of the atmospheric temperature with a continuing increase in the concentration of CO_2 in it are explained.

Keywords: *Earth's climate, nonequilibrium thermodynamics, hysteresis, entropy production, anthropogenic processes, pause in global warming*

Introduction. Climate change on Earth is caused by natural and anthropogenic factors. Natural factors include those that alter Earth's climate without human intervention and over which humans currently have no influence, such as changes in solar activity or Earth's orbit, volcanic eruptions, and asteroid impacts.

Anthropogenic impacts on climate are caused by human activity, such as changes in atmospheric thermal pollution, Earth's albedo, the magnitude of the greenhouse effect, and others. There are threshold values for these impacts, which when exceeded lead to significant and rapid climate change. Feedback loops are also observed in nature, which can either amplify or mitigate the initial impact.

General patterns of natural processes. To determine how natural and anthropogenic processes influence Earth's climate and compare the effects, first we must understand the nature of the ice ages, which dramatically alter the climate. It has been established that the alternation of glacial and interglacial periods in Earth's history was accompanied by changes in the atmosphere. Earth's climate reflects its state and is determined by numerous processes. It has also been established that a glaciation process, once started, develops according to its own laws unaffected by numerous climatic factors during interglacial periods [1].

The atmosphere is Earth's gas-forming shell constrained from one side by its surface and from the other by the outer space. In such a thermodynamic system, processes far from equilibrium occur. General laws governing the evolution of far from equilibrium thermodynamic systems were first formulated and their applicability to processes occurring in both inanimate and animate nature was demonstrated through experimental and computational methods in [2, 3]. These laws are based on a general principle formulated as an axiom on the pursuit of perfection in natural processes: *of all possible steady states of a system permitted by the laws of nature, the thermodynamics of irreversible processes, boundary conditions, and other physically justified conditions, the state with the lowest possible entropy production is the most probable.* In thermodynamics, entropy production is defined as the amount of entropy generated (or emerging) within a thermodynamic system per unit time $P_s = d_i S / dt$, where the change in entropy $d_i S$ is equal to the elementary reduced heat $\delta Q / T$ absorbed by the system; T is temperature; t is time. Let us demonstrate, using some examples, the general laws governing the evolution of nonequilibrium thermodynamic systems with heat exchange processes.

In [2], a nonequilibrium thermodynamic system is considered, consisting of a large volume of water at atmospheric pressure boiling under natural convection conditions on a flat, heat-transferring vessel bottom bounded by insulated sidewalls (Fig. 1). Two main regimes of water boiling were experimentally established: developed nucleate boiling and film boiling. The transition from one boiling regime to another is determined by the heat flux density q , which is the amount of heat passing through a unit area of the heat-transferring surface per unit time. According to [2, 4], entropy production in a nonequilibrium thermodynamic system in a steady state can be determined by the balance of entropy outflow from $J_{s,out}$ and inflow $J_{s,in}$ into the system:

$$P_s = \frac{d_i S}{dt} = J_{s,out} - J_{s,in}; \quad \Pi S = q \left(\frac{1}{T_X} - \frac{1}{T_\Gamma} \right), \quad (1)$$

where, for the case under consideration $J_{s,out} = q / T_X$; $J_{s,in} = q / T_\Gamma$; T_X, T_Γ are the temperatures of the cold and hot boundaries, respectively; ΠS is the specific entropy production per unit heat-transferring surface in accordance with the heat flux q . This definition of the values of entropy flows is applicable to quasi-steady states of nonequilibrium thermodynamic systems with heat and mass transfer processes.

Fig. 1. Water boiling in a large volume

Fig. 2. ΠS as a function of for two boiling regimes in a large volume of water

Based on the experimental data presented in [5], the dependences of specific entropy production ΠS on q for nucleate and film boiling regimes were determined using (1). These dependences are shown in Fig. 2. In this case, specific entropy production represents the amount of entropy produced per unit time per unit area of the heat-transfer surface. A developed nucleate boiling regime corresponds to

a lower value of specific entropy production, while film boiling corresponds to a higher value. These boiling regimes differ in their vaporization pattern: the hydrodynamic structure near the heat-transfer surface.

During developed nucleate boiling, a large number of vaporization centers form on the heat-transfer surface. However, the liquid continues to flow across the heating surface between these centers, and its boundary layer is intensively mixed by the vapor bubbles formed within it. During film boiling, the liquid is separated from the heat-transfer surface by a layer of water vapor (see Fig. 1), which has a lower thermal conductivity. As a result, the heat transfer rate becomes much lower than during nucleate boiling. The transition from nucleate boiling to film boiling occurs when the heat flux density reaches the first critical value q_{K1} (Fig. 2). This transition from a state with lower specific entropy production to a state with higher production is disruptive, accompanied by an abrupt change in both the hydrodynamic pattern near the heat-transfer surface and the thermodynamic and thermal parameters. It is characterized by a non-stationary boiling pattern. Various combinations of film and nucleate boiling regimes form in different zones of the heat-transfer surface, alternating chaotically.

In [5], it was also shown that by slowly increasing the heat flux through a specially selected heat-transfer surface depleted of nucleation sites, it was possible in some experiments to almost double the normal critical value q_{K1} . The ability to delay the transition from a steady state with a lower entropy production value to a steady state with a higher value is a common property of all nonequilibrium thermodynamic systems.

With further increases in $q > q_{K1}$, film boiling will be maintained with increasing as per the upper curve in Fig. 2. With a decrease in $q < q_{K1}$, the reverse transition of the thermodynamic system from a state with higher entropy production to a state with lower production occurs when the difference between the entropy productions of these two states reaches a certain minimum positive value. This corresponds to the heat flux density decreasing to a second critical value q_{K2} , which is significantly lower than q_{K1} . Thus, hysteresis can be clearly observed in thermal phenomena associated with the transition from one state of a thermodynamic system to the other. The nonequilibrium thermodynamic system under consideration conforms to the general laws of evolution presented in [2]. Other nonequilibrium thermodynamic systems with heat exchange processes behave similarly.

Let us consider Rayleigh–Bénard convection [2] by filling a frying pan with a layer of glycerin of a certain height and placing it on the stove. Depending on the heating temperature, or more precisely the Rayleigh number Ra , which includes the temperature difference between the hot T_T and cold T_X boundaries of the liquid, various steady states of fluid appear in the layer in the form of: hexagonal Bénard cells (Fig. 3 a, b); two-dimensional cells resembling counter-rotating rolls

(Fig. 3 c); three-dimensional cells and other ordered structures [6]. Each stationary state corresponds to its own value of entropy production, and transitions from states with lower entropy production to states with higher production occur when certain critical values of Rayleigh numbers Ra_1 , Ra_2 , Ra_3 etc. are reached in the experiment.

Fig. 3. Schematic presentation of convection cells: *a* – hexagonal Bénard cells; *b* – Bénard cells photography; *c* – two-dimensional rolls

Fig. 4 shows the entropy production as a function of the Rayleigh number for four steady states. The pattern in the graphs is similar to that shown in Fig. 2 but differs in the number of realized steady states, each with its own structure.

In the state corresponding to curve 0 in Fig. 4, with the liquid layer heated slowly, convection currents are absent, and the supplied heat is completely removed via heat transfer. As the heating temperature increases, convection currents appear, and when the Rayleigh number Ra_1 is reached, a new steady state is formed, corresponding to curve 1 in Fig. 4. This state features a honeycomb-like structure of fluid flow, called Bénard cells. With a further increase in heat flux, the resulting flow structure is initially maintained but then the Bénard cells begin to collapse, forming unsteady states. Through these states, the thermodynamic system, at the Rayleigh number Ra_2 , transitions to a new steady state with a roll-like

structure of fluid flow. This flow corresponds to curve 2 in Fig. 4 with the structure in Fig. 3 c. At the Rayleigh number Ra_3 , a new stationary flow structure is formed, etc. Fig. 4 clearly demonstrates that with an increase in the value of the Rayleigh number, the thermodynamic system transits from a state with lower entropy production to a state with higher entropy production (upward arrows).

Fig. 4. Changes in entropy production as a function of Rayleigh number

Experiments [6] note that when the heat flow into the thermodynamic system under consideration decreases, and consequently the Rayleigh number, its reverse transition (downward arrows) from a steady state with greater entropy production to a steady state with less entropy production occurs at lower Rayleigh numbers than the forward transition. In Fig. 4, the reverse transitions correspond to the Rayleigh numbers marked with a prime Ra'_1, Ra'_2, Ra'_3 . Thus, the transitions between two steady states of a nonequilibrium thermodynamic system exhibit hysteresis, as in the system considered previously.

Earth's atmosphere as a thermodynamic system. Let us apply the aforementioned general laws governing the changes in the states of nonequilibrium thermodynamic systems to Earth's atmosphere. Entropy production in Earth's atmosphere depends on a large number of factors influencing its thermal balance, particularly on the magnitudes of energy fluxes passing through the upper and lower boundaries of the atmosphere and the heat fluxes emerging within.

Through the upper boundary, the energy flow is entering the atmosphere primarily in the form of radiant solar energy. Periodically, energy may also flow due

to other phenomena, such as asteroids. Radiant energy from Earth's surface and atmosphere, as well as reflected solar energy, is transferred from the atmosphere into space.

Through the lower boundary, the atmosphere and Earth exchange radiant energy and heat mass flows caused by thermal conductivity, evaporation, and convection. Energy from Earth's interior, released during tectonic shifts and volcanic eruptions, is intermittently released into the atmosphere. Over the past century, Earth has been mined for mineral resources such as oil, gas, coal, uranium ore, and others with an increasing intensity. The energy of these resources is transferred as heat into the atmosphere because of human activity. The increasing use of solar, wind, and hydrogen energy significantly increases thermal pollution of the atmosphere compared to hydrocarbon energy [7].

The ongoing mass exchange processes alter the composition of the atmosphere and cause its pollution by aerosol formations. This reduces atmospheric transparency and, consequently, weakens solar radiation and other radiant fluxes. Changes in atmospheric composition, namely the concentrations of water vapor, CO_2 , CH_4 , and a number of other gases, alter the atmosphere's absorption capacity for infrared radiation, which affects the greenhouse effect. The increasing mass of living organisms and decaying organic matter also affects both the gas composition of the atmosphere and heat fluxes. Photosynthesis has a significant impact on atmospheric composition.

In a quasi-steady state, the structure of the atmosphere and its corresponding climate change insignificantly. In this case, the entropy flux out of the atmosphere, according to equation (1), must be greater than the entropy flux into it by the amount of entropy production in the atmosphere. Quasi-steady states of the atmosphere are quite unstable. Numerous factors influence both the incoming and outgoing entropy fluxes and the entropy production within the atmosphere. When entropy production within the atmosphere reaches critical values, significant changes occur in its structure and, consequently, in its climate. The atmosphere transitions to another quasi-steady state, differing from the initial one in both structure and thermodynamic and other parameters. Of all possible states, the transition to a state with the lowest possible entropy production is the most probable.

Geophysicists conventionally distinguish four groups of cycles, including the periodicity of ages during which glacier area increases (ice ages) or decreases [1]. Ultrashort cycles, lasting from tens to hundreds of years, and short cycles, lasting hundreds and thousands of years, are occurred due to changes in the parameters of Earth's orbit and solar activity. Long cycles, lasting millions of years, and super-long cycles, lasting over hundreds of millions of years, correlate with volcanic and tectonic activity on Earth of varying intensity.

The atmosphere, as a thermodynamic system, is a thin layer of gas compared to Earth's diameter. It exchanges heat flows from Earth and space. The

Rayleigh-Bénard convection discussed above occurs in a horizontal layer of liquid, also thin, heated by a heat flow from below. From the upper layer of liquid, the heat flow is transferred to the atmosphere. From the perspective of nonequilibrium thermodynamics, the processes occurring during Rayleigh-Bénard convection are similar to those in the atmosphere. Based on this, Fig. 5 shows the hypothetical pattern of changes in atmospheric entropy production as a function of the sum of heat fluxes Q into the atmosphere.

Fig. 5. Estimated entropy production as a function of heat flux for possible atmospheric heating and cooling cycles.

As heat fluxes increase, so does atmospheric entropy production and its temperature, leading to a decrease in the area of glaciers on Earth. Ultrashort cycles occur when atmospheric entropy production reaches the first critical value. In this case, the atmosphere transitions up the arrow 1 from the quasi-steady state interglacial state, corresponding to curve 0 in Fig. 5, to quasi-steady state 1. The transition from a state with lower entropy production to a state with higher entropy production, as shown previously, occurs through non-steady-states and can begin earlier or later depending on the rate of increase in heat flux into the atmosphere.

In the transition range, the structure of the atmosphere changes chaotically determined by wind directions and intensities, the number of cyclones and anticyclones, convection heat and mass flows, and other parameters. This chaotic change in the state of the atmosphere leads to chaotic climate change on Earth.

If, upon transition to quasi-steady state 1, heat flux into the atmosphere no longer increases, processes in the atmosphere and on Earth will tend to decrease entropy production in order to return the thermodynamic system to its initial state.

A decrease in entropy production in the atmosphere is possible due to the outflow of radiant energy into space and heat exchange with the ocean. According to the fundamental principles of nonequilibrium thermodynamics, the reverse transition is possible only through hysteresis. Therefore, this transition must occur when the heat flux, and consequently the entropy production in the atmosphere, is below the first critical value. The reverse transition corresponds to an ultra-short ice age 1–1' of Earth's life (the section of the graph between the upward arrow 1 and the downward arrow 1' in Fig. 5).

If the positive influx of thermal energy into the atmosphere persists during the atmosphere's transition to state 1, the increase in entropy production and atmospheric temperature will continue. When entropy production reaches critical value 2, a short ice age 2–2' of Earth's life is possible. It should be noted that there may be significantly more ultra-short and short cycles of alternating glacial and interglacial periods, as well as the causes of their formation (states n_i in Fig. 5). The abrupt, chaotic climate change on Earth that has begun in recent years heralds the beginning of a transition to one of these states.

For long and ultra-long cycles to occur, entropy production in the atmosphere must reach higher critical values. This may be caused by volcanic activity, high-energy asteroids on Earth, detonation of a certain number of nuclear weapons in the atmosphere, or the simultaneous action of all these factors and a number of others, such as the overheating of ocean waters. It should be noted that when the atmosphere transitions to a state corresponding to long cycle 3 or superlong cycle 4 in Fig. 5, intermediate states may not be realized. This is due to the fact that when a large amount of thermal energy enters the atmosphere in a relatively short period of time, the intermediate states do not have time to be realized, as they are overlapped by a higher state (see [2]).

During ultrashort and short cycles, atmospheric temperature can decrease due to atmospheric conditions that enhance heat exchange with the lower-temperature ocean. For example, through increased wind intensity and direction, which will lift increasing amounts of cold deep ocean water to the surface. This can also occur through an increase in the number of cyclones, hurricanes, rainfall, tornadoes, and storms, as well as changes in ocean currents and atmospheric circulation. During long and super-long cycles, reducing atmospheric temperature, and consequently ocean waters, will require the removal of large amounts of thermal energy. In this case, powerful cyclonic currents can form in the atmosphere, pushing greenhouse gases to the periphery and lowering the pressure at the vortex's center. This will allow large amounts of infrared radiation to escape into space through the vortex's internal channel, cooling the atmosphere and ocean.

Apart from the circulation currents formed in the atmosphere, other currents leading to profound ocean cooling are also possible. To confirm this, Fig. 6 shows

a photograph of a giant hexagon with a transverse dimension of 25,000 kilometers, located at the north pole of Saturn. The hexagon resembles a Bénard cell (see Fig. 3 a, b), whose straight walls are formed by a vortex-like flow extending deep into the atmosphere. The upper layers of Saturn's atmosphere have a temperature of 100–160 K, while inside the planet the temperature rises to 12,000 K. This flow allows the hot lower layers of the atmosphere to quickly rise to the cold upper layers, simultaneously releasing heat into space through thermal radiation.

Fig. 6. Photo of Saturn's north pole

The hexagonal structure at Saturn's north pole was first observed on the images transmitted by Voyager 1 and Voyager 2 space probes.

Comparison of the climatic effect of natural and anthropogenic factors.

We will compare the influence of certain natural and anthropogenic factors on the increase in entropy production in the atmosphere. We will determine the entropy production in the atmosphere caused by to solar radiation.

Fig. 7 shows the heat balance of the Earth as per [8]. According to this work, the energy flux density of radiation from the Sun to the atmosphere-Earth system was 341 W/m^2 . Part of this radiation, namely 102 W/m^2 in the visible range of light was reflected back into space (albedo). The Earth and the atmosphere were not heated by this energy. The remaining part $341 - 102 = 239 \text{ W/m}^2$ was absorbed by the atmosphere (78 W/m^2) and the Earth's surface (161 W/m^2). Of the absorbed radiation, 80 W/m^2 were spent on water evaporation and 17 W/m^2 on convection heat exchange.

Fig. 7. Earth's heat balance (March 2000 – May 2004)
All heat fluxes in W/m², averaged over time and over the Earth's surface.

The energy of these thermal processes was transferred to the atmosphere. Thermal radiation from the Earth's surface amounted to 396 W/m², of which 40 W/m² was emitted through the atmosphere into space, 356 W/m² was absorbed by the atmosphere, and a portion of this heat flux (333 W/m²) was reradiated back to the Earth's surface, creating a greenhouse effect. The total amount of thermal radiation from the atmosphere and from the Earth's surface into space was 199 + 40 = 239 W/m². Considering that in this case, the atmosphere, as a thermodynamic system, is in a quasi-steady nonequilibrium state, we will consider it possible to determine the entropy production in it using equation (1), i.e., by the difference in the outgoing entropy fluxes into space $J_{s,out}$ and incoming as a result of solar radiation $J_{s,in}$. We assume the upper boundary of the atmosphere to be the upper boundary of the stratosphere, with an average temperature of 230 K, since more than 90% of the mass of water vapor and air is located within this boundary. From space,

the Earth receives radiation from the surface of the Sun, which has a temperature of ≈ 6000 K.

Based on this, we write the specific entropy production in the atmosphere caused by solar radiation fluxes as

$$\Pi S_{sun} = 239 \left(\frac{1}{230} - \frac{1}{6000} \right) = 0,9993 \text{ W}/(m^2K). \quad (2)$$

This entropy production also includes entropy production from other processes in the atmosphere due to incoming solar energy.

The energy expended on photosynthesis and soil formation accounts for less than 1% of the total heat balance shown in Fig. 7. Due to its small value, it is not included in the balance. However, because this energy can accumulate over long periods of time in the Earth's crust, forming shale, coal, oil, and other organic matter, and then, with the help of humanity, be rapidly converted into other forms, it has a significant impact on the atmosphere.

The solar radiation flux reaching the upper boundary of the Earth's atmosphere is not constant. It varies both in time and space depending on changes in the Earth's orbit around the Sun, the tilt of its axis, and solar activity. In [9], a matrix of changes in solar radiation reaching the upper boundary of the atmosphere from 1900 to 2100 was calculated, not accounting for the changes in solar activity. The calculations revealed a slight downward trend in solar radiation over the period under consideration, as well as significant interannual fluctuations, time and space dependent, most clearly manifested in the 19-year cycle and not exceeding 0,08% of the average value.

In [10], based on the calculation results, an estimate was provided of the change in solar energy received by the Earth over the past 500,000 years due to changes in its orbit and the tilt of its axis. According to the calculations, we are currently living in an interglacial period and are approaching the next glaciation, with an average rate of insolation decrease of approximately 0,2–0,4% per thousand years. From the above it follows that the current change in the structure of the atmosphere accompanied by global warming is not caused by a change in the solar energy reaching the upper boundary of the Earth's atmosphere.

Let us consider other natural factors influencing the Earth's climate and estimate the magnitude of their impact using changes in atmospheric entropy production. Significant climate changes have occurred on Earth in the past due to intense volcanic activity and asteroid impacts. For example, during the eruption of Tambora (Indonesia), one of the most powerful volcanoes in the last two centuries, which began on April 5, 1815 and lasted 10 days, the energy released was $Q_{tamb} = 1,4 \cdot 10^{20}$ J [11]. The eruption released large quantities of volcanic gases (including water vapor and CO_2), ash, and other aerosols into the stratosphere.

The volcanic eruption led to a decrease in global temperature by 0,4–0,7 °C. In the spring and summer of 1816, cool weather persisted in Europe, with prolonged frosts, thunderstorms, severe floods, and crop failures. For this reason, the year was called the “Year Without a Summer”.

When discussing the energy released into the atmosphere by a given process, we must consider both the time it took and the area covered. For example, [12] demonstrated that when a thermotropic liquid crystal is irradiated with a laser, its structure does not change immediately throughout the crystal’s entire volume, but rather first in an area (domain) where the temperature reaches a critical value. Similarly, in the case of a volcanic eruption, entropy production can quickly reach critical values only in a certain domain around the volcano, and within this domain, a change in the atmospheric structure will occur, which will affect the climate of the entire Earth. If volcanic eruptions are short-lived, then prolonged ice ages do not occur, as, for example, in the case of decreased insolation due to changes in the Earth’s orbit and the tilt of its axis.

If we assume that in a certain region of the atmosphere (domain) around the Tambora volcano, over 10 days of the eruption a state of the ongoing process close to steady state was established, then the specific entropy production (per unit of the Earth’s surface area $F_{earth} = 5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \text{ m}^2$) in this domain can be estimated using equation (1). Assuming the volcanic eruption temperature equal to the lava temperature $T_r = 1400 \text{ K}$, we shall write the specific entropy production due to the Tambora volcano eruption as

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi S_{tamb} &= \frac{Q_{tamb}}{F_{earth} \cdot t} \left(\frac{1}{T_x} - \frac{1}{T_r} \right) = \frac{1,4 \cdot 10^{20}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 10 \cdot 24 \cdot 3600} \left(\frac{1}{230} - \frac{1}{1400} \right) = \\ &= 0,1155 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

It follows that when the specific entropy production reaches a critical value, corresponding to equation (3), the Earth’s climate begins to change. Climate change will be affected by the state of the atmosphere prior to the volcanic eruption.

The impact of asteroids with a radius greater than 1 km on Earth can have consequences similar to those of large volcanic eruptions, and in some cases even more severe. The impact of an asteroid approximately 10 km in diameter on the Yucatan Peninsula (Mexico) 65 million years ago resulted in the formation of a crater 180 km in diameter and a release of energy $Q_{ast} = 5 \cdot 10^{23} \text{ J}$ [13]. The asteroid’s impact released large quantities of hot rock, dust, and other aerosol particles into the stratosphere. The resulting strong earthquake generated a powerful seismic wave that circled the globe several times, as well as a high-temperature shock wave propagating through the atmosphere. All of this led to significant changes in the structure of the atmosphere and, consequently, the climate on Earth. The average annual air temperature dropped significantly. This event, many scientists

believe, led to the extinction of dinosaurs and other animals. Let us assume, as in the case of the Tambora eruption, that 60 days after the asteroid impact, in a certain atmospheric domain near the impact site, the thermal processes had approached a quasi-steady state so closely that the specific entropy production in this domain can be estimated using equation (1). Then, assuming the temperature at the impact site to be $T_f = 4000$ K, we find the entropy production in the atmospheric domain caused by the asteroid impact.

$$\Pi S_{ast} = \frac{Q_{ast}}{F_{earth} \cdot t} \left(\frac{1}{T_x} - \frac{1}{T_f} \right) = \frac{5 \cdot 10^{23}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 60 \cdot 24 \cdot 3600} \left(\frac{1}{230} - \frac{1}{4000} \right) = 0,775 \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

We can see that the specific entropy production in the atmosphere due to an asteroid impact is of the same order of magnitude as the specific entropy production caused by the solar radiation flux. It should be noted that the specific entropy production from an asteroid impact was calculated assuming that a quasi-steady state in the domain was established within 60 days. It will then decrease over time, as the energy from the impact spreads throughout the atmosphere and escapes beyond its boundaries.

Large asteroids rarely fall to Earth, while volcanoes and earthquakes occur with varying intensity throughout the year. Approximately 50–60 volcanic eruptions occur annually on the Earth's surface, of which large ones, such as Mount Tambora discussed above, are rare. The thermal energy released by small volcanoes annually, according to [14], is approximately: $Q_{volc.earth} = 0,5 \cdot 10^{19}$ J/year.

Then, the specific entropy production due to average annual volcanic eruptions on the Earth's surface will be:

$$\Pi S_{volc.earth} = \frac{0,5 \cdot 10^{19}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 3,1536 \cdot 10^7} \left(\frac{1}{230} - \frac{1}{1400} \right) = 0,113 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

For further calculations we assume $1 \text{ year} = 3,1536 \cdot 10^7$ s.

Modern underwater volcanic activity significantly exceeds that of terrestrial volcanoes. Underwater volcanoes erupt approximately 12–15 times more volcanic material annually than terrestrial volcanoes. Therefore, it can be assumed that the average annual thermal energy they release will be 14 times higher than that of terrestrial volcanoes and will amount to $Q_{volc.earth} = 0,7 \cdot 10^{20}$ J/year. These heat fluxes are absorbed by ocean waters, and their impact on the Earth's atmosphere and climate is manifested through an increase in its temperature.

Over 100,000 earthquakes are recorded on Earth annually, and according to [15], they release an average of $Q_{ear.en} = 0,575 \cdot 10^{18}$ J/year. It should be noted that ~75% of this energy is released by a few destructive earthquakes lasting several minutes. The energy of earthquakes is expended on destruction, heating, and the seismic wave generation. Some oceanic earthquakes are

accompanied by powerful waves, or tsunamis. Most of the energy from these earthquakes is absorbed by the land and ocean. Due to the small temperature difference between T_r and T_x , entropy production in the atmosphere due to annual earthquakes can be neglected.

Let us consider the main anthropogenic processes influencing the Earth's climate. We will assess the impact of global energy on the growth of entropy production in the atmosphere. The impact of carbon-based energy can be determined by the amount of primary energy consumed by humanity. According to [16], global primary energy consumption in 2023 was $Q_{carb.en} = 0,62 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year. This energy is transferred to the atmosphere after being consumed. Assuming an average fuel combustion temperature of 2800 K and that all this thermal energy is transferred from the atmosphere to the ocean, with a surface temperature of 288 K, the specific entropy production in the atmosphere due to humanity's use of carbon-based energy is

$$\Pi S_{carb.en} = \frac{0,62 \cdot 10^{21}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 3,1536 \cdot 10^7} \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{2800} \right) = 0,12 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

The amount of energy produced by solar and wind energy is accounted for separately from primary energy. According to [16], electricity production from these sources increased by 13% in 2023, reaching $0,416 \cdot 10^{20}$ J/year. We will assume that all this energy is generated by solar power plants, as their share in electricity production exceeds that of wind power plants.

Due to the low efficiency of silicon solar panels, the amount of thermal energy released into the atmosphere will be approximately 7 times greater than the electricity they generate, amounting to $Q_{sol.en} = 0,2912 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year. After the electrical energy generated by the solar panels is consumed, the thermal energy is released into the atmosphere and then transferred to the ocean. The specific entropy production in the atmosphere due to solar energy is written as

$$\Pi S_{sol.en} = \frac{0,2912 \cdot 10^{21}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 3,1536 \cdot 10^7} \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{6000} \right) = 0,05985 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

The specific entropy production in the atmosphere in 2023 due to the use of hydrocarbon and solar energy amounted to

$$\Pi S_{en} = \Pi S_{carb.en} + \Pi S_{sol.en} = 0,1799 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

In 2021, the global hydropower plants capacity reached 1360 GW. At the same time, the thermal energy released into the environment per year, was equal to $Q_{HPP} = 0,4515 \cdot 10^{20}$ J/year, assuming an efficiency of 0,95. In the same year, the thermal energy released into the environment from the use of nuclear power plants amounted to $Q_{NPP} = 0,5797 \cdot 10^{20}$ J/year. The total amount of thermal energy

released into the environment per year from most types of energy resources consumed by humanity amounted to

$$Q_{en\Sigma} = Q_{carb.en} + Q_{sol.en} + Q_{HPP} + Q_{NPP} = 1,014 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ J/year.}$$

Let us determine the entropy production in the atmosphere due to a decrease in the Earth's albedo. The paper [7] presents the results of studies on changes in the Earth's reflectivity conducted since 1998 by astrophysicists from the California Observatory and the results of similar studies using satellite data. According to the laboratory data, the Earth's albedo decreased by an average of 0,03 W/m² per year over the 20-year observation period, while according to satellite data, it decreased by 0,065 W/m². In our calculations, we use the average value equal to 0,0475 W/m². This value corresponds to the average annual increase in solar radiant energy absorbed by the Earth due to the decrease in albedo.

The specific entropy production due to the decrease in albedo was

$$\Pi S_{alb} = 0,0475 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{6000} \right) = 0,157 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ W/(m}^2\text{K)}.$$

The additional energy absorbed by the Earth's surface during the year due to the decrease in albedo was

$$Q_{alb} = 0,0475 \cdot 5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 3,1536 \cdot 10^7 = 0,76396 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ J/year.}$$

Fires occurring worldwide, whose area increases over the years due to global warming, reduce the Earth's albedo and significantly increase both heat emissions and the amount of greenhouse gases released into the atmosphere.

Let us determine the entropy production in the atmosphere due to thermal emissions during forest fires. Depending on the forest type, age, undergrowth, humidity, etc., the amount of heat released into the atmosphere during the combustion of 1 hectare of forest varies. We assume that the combustion of 1 hectare of forest releases $1,4 \cdot 10^{12}$ J of thermal energy. In 2021, fires destroyed 18,8 million hectares of forest in Russia [17]. This same year, severe fires occurred in many countries around the world. Since data on the wildfire area could not be found even for large countries, and the forest area in Russia is approximately 20% of the area of all forests in the world, we further assume the total area of wildfires in all countries to be equal to 50,76 million hectares. The amount of heat released into the atmosphere during the 3 hottest months worldwide was $Q_{for,fire} = 50,76 \cdot 10^6 \cdot 1,4 \cdot 10^{12} = 0,71 \cdot 10^{20}$ J. Assuming wood combustion temperature of 1200 K and that the heat flux from combustion is primarily diverted to the ocean, we will write the specific entropy production due to forest fires using equation (1):

$$\Pi S_{for,fire} = \frac{0,71 \cdot 10^{20}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14} \cdot 3 \cdot 30 \cdot 24 \cdot 3600} \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{1200} \right) = 0,4724 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ W/(m}^2\text{K)}.$$

Thermal pollution of the atmosphere also occurs during the decomposition (rotting) of organic matter. Organic matter on Earth is formed through photosynthesis, which occurs in plant cells using primarily solar energy in the visible spectrum of light. Carbohydrates (glucose) synthesized by plants are the main source of energy for most organisms on Earth. After the end of their life cycle, decomposition of organic matter begins, releasing thermal energy. The decomposition of organic matter lags behind the synthesis process, leading to its accumulation in the Earth's interior and the formation of fossil fuels.

The share of heat flux due to the decomposition of organic matter is increasing, both due to the increasing amount of organic matter on Earth and global warming, which disrupts the integrity of organic matter stored in permafrost. It is not possible to estimate the magnitude of this flow at present.

Let us determine the specific entropy production in the atmosphere from warm-blooded living organisms. According to the UN, the world population in 2024 was ~ 8,2 billion people and it continues to increase. The average heat output power of an adult, depending on the type of load, varies from 100 W (at rest) to 300 W (brisk walk) [18] at the same comfortable temperature. We assume a heat output power of 150 W in the calculations. The total heat output power from all humans on the planet will equal $1,23 \cdot 10^{12}$ W. The thermal energy released by humans into the atmosphere will be $0,3879 \cdot 10^{20}$ J/year. The specific entropy production in the atmosphere by humans, assuming that body temperature is $36,7^\circ\text{C}$, and the heat flux is absorbed by the ocean with a surface temperature of 288 K, can be written as

$$\Pi S_{hum} = \frac{1,23 \cdot 10^{12}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14}} \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{(273 + 36,7)} \right) = 0,5868 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

The exact amount of heat generated by other warm-blooded organisms living on Earth is very difficult to determine, as the heat they generate depends on, for example, their weight, muscle activity, and the number of living individuals, which is sometimes difficult to determine. It is possible to roughly estimate the total heat output of only some animals raised by humans. Using open data, it can be estimated that the heat output of other warm-blooded organisms on Earth will be $1,6 \cdot 10^{12}$ W, and the thermal energy released by them over a year will be equal to $0,505 \cdot 10^{20}$ J/year. The specific entropy production in the atmosphere due to the heat flux from animals (taking into account that the normal temperature for most is $39,5^\circ\text{C}$) will equal

$$\Pi S_{anim} = \frac{1,6 \cdot 10^{12}}{5,1 \cdot 10^{14}} \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{273 + 39,5} \right) = 0,855 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

The total specific entropy production in the atmosphere from all warm-blooded organisms living on Earth will equal

$$\Pi S_{w-bl} = 0,5868 \cdot 10^{-6} + 0,855 \cdot 10^{-6} = 0,144 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ W}/(m^2K).$$

The total thermal energy released by all warm-blooded organisms will equal

$$Q_{w-bl} = 0,3879 \cdot 10^{20} + 0,505 \cdot 10^{20} = 0,8929 \cdot 10^{20} \text{ J/year.}$$

The values of some heat fluxes and selected parameters presented in this article may be further adjusted as new experimental data and calculation methods are obtained. However, this will not change the essence and conclusions of the article.

Let us determine the total annual amount of thermal energy Q_{anthr} entering the atmosphere-ocean system due to the anthropogenic factors discussed above. We assume that the thermal pollution of the system due to the decomposition Q_{decomp} of organic matter differs little from the thermal energy Q_{w-bl} . We also assume that the thermal pollution of the system due to ongoing wars on Earth Q_{war} , due to the lack of data on the amount of explosives and gunpowder used, is equal to $Q_{war} = Q_{for,fire}$. Then

$$Q_{anthr} = Q_{en\Sigma} + Q_{alb} + Q_{for,fire} + Q_{w-bl} + Q_{decomp} + Q_{war} = 2,0985 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ J/year.}$$

The total annual amount of these energies is capable of melting a 3-meter-thick ice sheet occupying a square field with sides measuring 1,500 km. The more glaciers melt, the lower the albedo, and the melting process accelerates due to feedback. This leads to an accelerated temperature rise in both the atmosphere and oceans. The World Ocean accumulates most of this energy, including that from melting glaciers. Due to the Ocean's large mass and its heat capacity compared to the atmosphere, it acts as a temperature regulator and prevents the atmosphere from warming rapidly. For example, if the entire atmosphere were cooled by 30 °C and this energy were transferred to a 100-meter-thick layer of the Ocean, the water within would warm by only 1 °C.

During the long Ice Age, the World Ocean released so much energy into space via infrared radiation that its temperature at its deepest points ranges from 2 °C to 4 °C, despite the periodic eruptions of numerous underwater volcanoes and the flow of water from geothermal vents on the seafloor, with temperatures reaching 400 °C. In addition, heat flows from the Earth's hot interior and radiogenic heat generated by the radioactive decay of isotopes in the mantle also flow to the oceanic crust via thermal conductivity. According to [19], the average heat flow from the oceanic crust to the ocean is equal to

$$q_{int} = 0,0625 \text{ W}/m^2; Q_{int} = 1,005 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ J/year.}$$

Analysis of oceanographic observations, including those conducted since 2003 using the *Argo* global system, which measures the temperature in the upper 2000-meter water layer, has shown (see, for example, [20]) that the warming of the World Ocean not only continues but is accelerating. For example, while the average annual increase in heat in the upper 2000-meter water layer over the 50-year observation period from 1955 to 2004 was $\sim 3,9 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year, over the subsequent 15 years from 2005 to 2020, this value increased almost threefold to $10,2 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year. In 2024, the heat content in the upper 2,000 meters of the ocean reached another all-time record.

Ocean warming is accelerating due to a number of factors. Due to the anthropogenic factors mentioned above, thermal energy enters the atmosphere-ocean system equal to $Q_{anthr} = 2,0985 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year. Due to natural factors, in a year without cataclysms, thermal energy enters the system from both volcanic eruptions and earthquakes, as well as energy from the Earth's interior, in a total amount of

$$Q_{nat} = Q_{volc.earth} + Q_{volc.ocean} + Q_{ear.en} + Q_{int} = 1,081 \cdot 10^{21} \text{ J/year.}$$

A significantly larger portion of the thermal energy generated by these factors is accumulated by the ocean, while a smaller portion is lost to the atmosphere and land, and also to space as thermal radiation. In our calculations, we assume that all of this thermal energy enters the ocean.

The increase in ocean heat content in 2020 was $10,2 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year, of which $3,18 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year was due to the aforementioned anthropogenic and natural factors. The remaining increase, $7,02 \cdot 10^{21}$ J/year ($0,436 \text{ W/m}^2$), most likely occurred due to a decrease in long-wave (thermal) radiation from the Earth's surface and atmosphere to space. Incoming solar radiation (341 W/m^2 in Fig. 7) exceeded outgoing longwave radiation by $0,436 \text{ W/m}^2$ due to the increased greenhouse effect, and reflected shortwave radiation by $0,0475 \text{ W/m}^2$ due to the decreased Earth's albedo. The thermal balance at the upper boundary of the atmosphere was disturbed.

Assuming that this disturbance will have little effect on the specific entropy production values calculated using formula (1) for steady states, we determine the specific entropy production due to the increased greenhouse effect.

$$\Pi S_{gr} = 0,436 \left(\frac{1}{288} - \frac{1}{6000} \right) = 0,144 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}).$$

The sum of the specific entropy production in the atmosphere for a number of the anthropogenic processes discussed above will be

$$\Pi S_{anthr} = \Pi S_{gr} + \Pi S_{en} + \Pi S_{alb} + \Pi S_{for.fire} + \Pi S_{w-bl} = 0,1826 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ W}/(\text{m}^2\text{K}).$$

This value is close to the specific entropy production in the atmosphere due to the eruption of Mount Tambora ΠS_{tamb} (see equation (3)), which caused the

currently observed chaotic transition of the atmosphere to another quasi-steady state, and, consequently, chaotic climate change. Upon completion of the transition, for example, to the n_i state in Fig. 5, as shown above, the intensification of heat exchange between the atmosphere and the ocean will increase, which should lower the atmospheric temperature due to cold deep ocean waters or prevent it from warming.

Fig. 8 shows the change in global surface temperature [21], calculated using an algorithm averaging results recorded by tens of thousands of weather stations. Intervals are visible when the global temperature remained virtually unchanged while CO_2 concentrations in the atmosphere continued to increase.

Fig. 8. Global temperature changes from 1950 to 2013. The mean value from 1961 to 1990 is taken as zero. Lines indicate near-surface temperatures: the dashed line indicates data from the HadCRUT database (HadCRUT4 version); the solid line indicates data from the NASA GISTEMP database; and the thick solid line indicates the mean value over the period.

Such intervals have been called pauses in global warming. Transitions from one global temperature to another occur quickly in accordance with the general laws of evolution, and a further decrease in temperature does not occur due to the accelerated increase in the influx of heat into the atmosphere, which exceeds its outflow into the ocean.

When the ocean exhausts its ability to absorb additional thermal energy from the atmosphere, its structure will radically change in accordance with the above,

and a prolonged ice age will set in, during which the ocean will begin to cool due to thermal radiation into space, for example, through the internal channels of powerful vortices forming in the atmosphere.

The long-term accelerated warming of the World Ocean observed in the experimental data is consistent with the accelerated increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, confirming the conclusions of earlier studies. For example, in [22], the increase in atmospheric carbon dioxide concentration is explained by a decrease in its solubility in ocean waters with increasing temperature. Also, in [7], it is demonstrated in several ways that fossil fuels are not responsible for the increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentration, which is caused by rising ocean temperatures.

As ocean temperatures rise, the concentration of CO₂ and water vapor in the atmosphere rises, which increases the greenhouse effect and atmospheric temperature. An increase in atmospheric temperature, with some lag, leads to an increase in ocean temperature due to heat flowing into the ocean. This, in turn, leads to an increase in atmospheric CO₂ and water vapor concentrations, and the warming process accelerates due to feedback, as is currently observed.

Conclusion. The ocean and atmosphere are a single, interconnected system with a continuous exchange of heat, fresh water, and gases. The ocean absorbs excess CO₂ from the atmosphere and releases it when there is a shortage. Rising ocean temperatures lead to a decrease in the amount of CO₂ dissolved in water and the precipitation of CaCO₃, which, along with marine organisms, precipitates as limestone deposits. Large deposits of limestone have formed in the Earth's interior. The simultaneous increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentration leads to proliferation of vegetation on Earth and increased plant productivity. At the same time, photosynthesis increases the uptake of atmospheric carbon dioxide and the production of hydrocarbons, which accumulate in Earth, forming deposits of fossil fuels. Thus, nature itself participates in regulating the CO₂ content in the atmosphere and ocean. Therefore, if anthropogenic impacts on nature are reduced and CO₂ absorption from the atmosphere is increased by expanding vegetation and accelerating limestone formation, which absorbs some of the CO₂ from the ocean, for example, by increasing coral formations, the concentration of CO₂ in the ocean-atmosphere system may decrease. This will increase the flow of thermal radiation from the Earth's surface to space and lower the temperature of the system. To preserve human civilization for as long as possible, it is necessary to:

- stop the accelerated influx of heat into the atmosphere, including by ending wars on Earth. It should be especially noted that humanity has accumulated so much energy stored in nuclear warheads that the simultaneous release of even a portion of it would lead to an increase in atmospheric entropy production exceeding many natural disasters that have occurred on Earth;

- limit humanity's consumption of energy resources and meet growing demand through the development of alternative energy-saving and environmentally friendly technologies;
- change the development priorities of modern society, eventually transitioning to a society of intellectuals and rational users of material goods;
- demonstrate maximum concern for environmental conservation by stopping pollution, reducing deforestation, and preventing large-scale forest fires, etc.

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关于东外贝加尔地区详细地质年代学研究的问题
**ON THE ISSUE OF DETAILED GEOCHRONOLOGICAL STUDIES
OF EASTERN TRANSBAIKALIA**

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摘要：本文探讨了应用U-Pb同位素定年法研究东外贝加尔地区上二叠统一下三叠统阿克沙-伊林组地层的必要性。由于采用相对地层划分和对比方法获得的数据有限，因此本研究具有重要意义。现有研究主要依赖于生物地层学数据，这不足以全面了解该地层的地质历史和沉积环境。

本研究对象为上二叠统一下三叠统阿克沙-伊林组地层。由于该地层区域长期以来一直受到关注，因此对其进行研究具有重要意义。本研究旨在探讨阿克沙-伊林组的沉积特征和条件，以及利用碎屑锆石U-Pb定年法重建沉积环境和古地理背景的可行性。

本研究旨在论证阿克沙-伊林组同位素年代学方法在获取该地区地质历史及沉积地层形成条件方面的完整数据方面的应用价值。研究目标包括：研究并描述阿克沙-伊林组现有的地层数据；识别信息缺失之处；描述U-Pb定年方法及其适用范围、应用条件和局限性；研究U-Pb定年方法在陆源地层研究中的应用经验；评估其在阿克沙-伊林组研究中的适用性。

本文仅提出同位素年代学方法在未来研究中的应用建议。基于对现有数据的比较以及其他年代学研究的经验，我们认为在所研究的地层范围内，U-Pb定年方法是可行的。本文作者仅采用分析研究方法，但不仅分析了现有数据，还将其与类似研究进行了对比。

考虑到U-Pb定年法的各项特点、其在沉积条件重建方面的应用经验以及数据扩充的必要性，结论是支持采用U-Pb同位素定年法对阿克沙-伊林组进行研究。

关键词：地层学，生物地层学，定年方法，同位素方法，U-Pb定年法，沉积条件重建，地球化学研究，激光剥蚀电感耦合等离子体质谱法（LA-ICP/MS），阿克沙-伊林组，陆源地层，外贝加尔地区。

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the need to apply the U-Pb isotope dating method to study the Aksha-Ilin series of the Upper Permian–Lower Triassic of Eastern Transbaikalia. The relevance of the study is due to the limited data obtained by applying relative methods of stratigraphic division and correlation of strata. Existing studies rely mainly on biostratigraphic data, which does not allow us to obtain a complete picture of the geological history and sedimentation conditions.*

The object of study is the Aksha-Ilinsky series of the Upper Permian – Lower Triassic. Its study is questionable due to the long-standing research conducted on its territory. The subject of the study is the features and conditions of sedimentation of the Aksha-Ilinsky series, the possibility of using U-Pb dating of clastic zircon grains to reconstruct sedimentation conditions and paleogeographic settings.

The aim of the work is to substantiate the application of the method of isotopic geochronology of the Aksha-Ilin series to obtain more complete data on the geological history of the region and the conditions of formation of sedimentary strata. The objectives of this study included: to study and describe the existing stratigraphic data on the Aksha-Ilin series; to identify a lack of information; to describe the U-Pb dating method, its capabilities, conditions of use and limitations; to study the experience of using the U-Pb dating method for the study of terrigenous strata; assessment of the expediency of its use for the study of the Aksha-Ilin series.

This article is only about the proposal of isotope geochronology methods for future research. Based on a comparison of the available data and based on the experience of other geochronological studies, it is concluded that U-Pb dating is advisable within the framework of the studied stratum. The authors use only analytical research methods in this article, however, the authors not only analyze existing data, but also compile them with similar studies.

Taking into account all the features of the U-Pb dating method, the experience of its application regarding the reconstruction of sedimentation conditions, and the need to expand data, the conclusion is in favor of using U-Pb isotope dating methods of the Aksha-Ilin series.

Keywords: *stratigraphy, biostratigraphy, dating methods, isotopic methods, U-Pb dating, reconstruction of sedimentation conditions, geochemical studies, LA-ICP/MS laser ablation method, Aksha-Ilinsky series, terrigenous strata, Transbaikalia.*

Introduction. The stratigraphy of Eastern Transbaikalia has a long history, grounded primarily in geological survey data and, to a lesser extent, in thematic research. The geochronological component of stratigraphy is based mainly on paleontological data [1]. The question of subdividing rock sequences into stratigraphic units continues to generate debate, since for most formations only the stratotype locality is indicated, rather than the position of the stratotype itself within the section.

The lack of data in the stratigraphic subdivision of sequences hampers their thorough study, including the identification of mineral resource associations [2, 3]. Stratigraphic data make it possible to understand the history of many geological processes occurring in a specific territory. Knowledge of this history, in turn, allows conclusions to be drawn regarding the patterns of mineral resource distribution. Forecasting and prospecting for mineral resources is a strategically important task. From this perspective, the reconstruction of sedimentary conditions is of particular interest.

Experience in studying the reconstruction of sedimentary conditions shows that one of the most effective methods is U-Pb dating of detrital zircon grains. This method not only enables stratigraphic correlation but also facilitates the construction of a sedimentation model [4].

The problem of stratigraphic subdivision and correlation of Permian–Triassic sequences in Eastern Transbaikalia remains pressing. This is due to the limited scope of the methods employed. Conclusions regarding the age of sequences have been drawn on the basis of the biostratigraphic method.

The present study examines the Aksha-Ilin Series of the Upper Permian – Lower Triassic, as it is widely distributed across Eastern Transbaikalia; however, data from geological surveys indicate that it remains insufficiently studied and that there is a significant information deficit.

The Aksha-Ilin Series may be of value in terms of manganese deposits. The paleofacial conditions of its formation support this conclusion [7]. In addition, the series is distinguished as part of the Middle Onon Terrane [8], which forms part of the large western fragment of the Aginsk Accretionary Wedge [9]. The Middle Onon Terrane was identified relatively recently; prior to this, it was included within the Onon Terrane. The study of the Aginsk Accretionary Wedge, and in particular its constituent elements, is of interest from the perspective of investigating its role in the formation of the Mongol–Okhotsk Orogenic Belt.

Methodology and Methods. U-Pb isotopic dating of detrital zircons can be applied to various types of sequences depending on the research objectives. When applying this method, it is important to understand that the objective largely determines the study itself: sample collection, preparation techniques, and interpretation. The results obtained do not always meet expectations, since the process of interpreting the data is quite specific and plays a decisive role [2]. Sound interpretation and its tools determine the value of the research.

When discussing the reconstruction of sedimentary conditions, it is appropriate to consider methods based on Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) and Laser Ablation ICP-MS (LA-ICP/MS) [3]. SHRIMP instruments are the most relevant for such studies. However, what we are dealing with are not the true atomic U/Pb ratios in the material under study, but ionic Pb^+/U^+ ratios, which differ substantially. Further measurements are carried out by comparing the obtained values against reference standards.

It should be noted at the outset that the method described is highly imprecise. U-Pb zircon dating by LA-ICP/MS does not yield high-precision data on the age of rocks [11]. However, applying radioisotopic dating methods for the precise determination of sequence ages in terrigenous deposits is not meaningful. What can ultimately be obtained is a crystallization date for the substrate from which the sedimentary rocks are composed – but that is not the goal of such studies. Herein lies the fundamental difficulty of using radioisotopic methods for dating sequences.

What can ultimately be obtained is a crystallization date for the substrate from which the sedimentary rocks are composed. That is not the objective of the study. Herein lies the fundamental difficulty of using radioisotopic methods for dating sequences. We seek to determine the age of the sequence itself – in other words, the moment of sedimentation – yet in practice we easily end up with a crystallization date for the substrate, which points instead to regional geological processes or to the formation of “parent” igneous complexes. The use of radioisotopic methods for precise dating is worth discussing in certain cases when dealing with igneous rocks [16, 17]. Working with terrigenous sequences may be more complicated.

Metamorphic rocks are most accurately dated by U-Pb methods when they have reached a high degree of metamorphism. Until that degree is reached, it is impossible to say with certainty what date has actually been obtained. A common situation is that we are left with two assumptions: either the date truly reflects the formation of the substrate itself, or it reflects the moment of metamorphism [5]. Other interpretations are also possible depending on the approach taken, as there can be quite a large number of interpretive variants in U–Pb isotopic dating.

In order to carry out a sound interpretation, it is necessary to draw on all available data; no known fact about the sequence under study should be overlooked. It is critically important here to combine radioisotopic data with data from biostratigraphy and palynology. Radioisotopic methods cannot in any way replace biostratigraphic ones, even though biostratigraphic methods are relative while radioisotopic methods are absolute. Combining data from various methods facilitates a well-grounded interpretation of U–Pb isotopic dating results.

The Aksha-Ilin Series was actively studied approximately 25–30 years ago. The key publication presenting the stratigraphy of Eastern Transbaikalia and containing information on the sequence in question was released in 2002. Since then, information on the Aksha-Ilin Series has not undergone significant revision. Current state geological maps describing this series are largely based on data from the 2000s.

The study of the stratigraphy of the Aksha-Ilin Series was based on the application of the biostratigraphic method and palynological data. No other sources of stratigraphic data are currently available; the formations of the Aksha-Ilin Series were studied in outcrops and surface exposures.

The problem with the existing data on the Aksha-Ilin Series lies in their age. Questions arise regarding the reliability and completeness of information on the composition and structure of the series.

The series under study comprises the Aginskoye, Zutkuleyskoye, and Tulutayskoye formations. The Aginskoye Formation lies at the base of the series. The formation consists predominantly of sandstones, with lesser amounts of gravelites, conglomerates, and siltstones. At its base, thin interbeds of volcanogenic-sedimentary rocks are encountered, along with metabasalt bodies and olistostromes. The Late Permian–Early Triassic age of the Aginskoye Formation was determined by the biostratigraphic method based on organic remains.

The Zutkuleyskoye Formation conformably overlies the Aginskoye Formation and is composed exclusively of terrigenous rocks forming rhythmically structured packages. Its deposits are attributed to the Early Triassic based on plant fossil remains.

The Tulutayskoye Formation, which completes the series section, consists of terrigenous rocks. It contains few organic remains, and its Early Triassic age has been accepted on the basis of its conformable position above the Zutkuleyskoye Formation. However, palynological data reveal a minor inconsistency. Palynological assemblages have been identified in the Lower Tulutayskoye Subformation. Among forms with a broad age range, palynomorphs characteristic of the Triassic are present. A distinctive feature of the assemblage is the presence of forms characteristic only of the Upper Triassic, as well as forms first appearing in the Upper Triassic. The main difficulty in dating lies in the small quantity of organic remains; the palynological assemblages represented in the formation are extremely sparse.

At present, the experience with U–Pb isotopic dating of detrital zircons is quite extensive [2, 3, 4], and it is therefore possible to draw on a large body of research studies that have, to varying degrees, achieved their stated objectives in order to justify the need for this type of investigation.

Drawing on these examples and the arguments presented in this article, it can be concluded that the application of U–Pb dating of detrital zircons is justified for the Aksha-Ilin Series. There are grounds to believe that this research method will supplement the existing data and provide a more complete body of information for the study of this series.

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现成图像假说——“创伤记忆”在生物体信息和物质组织一般原则发展概念中的作用

THE HYPOTHESIS OF A READY-MADE IMAGE – “MEMORY OF TRAUMA” IN THE CONCEPT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF GENERAL PRINCIPLES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF INFORMATION AND MATTER IN LIVING ORGANISMS

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摘要。在任何层面的调节机制出现持续性功能失调的情况下，都会出现熵增性质的不稳定病理过程，我们将其定义为“创伤记忆”——包括生理和心理两方面。改变患者的个体世界观，为参与调节病理过程的专家提供了更多机会，激活了个体经验的修正，从而改善了颞下颌关节功能障碍、肌筋膜疼痛综合征及相关系统性疾病的症状。必要时，肿瘤患者首先会形成“目标意象”。“现成意象假说”弥补了这一空白：主观体验是副交感神经系统产生的信号的内在属性；丘脑传递的是已形成的现象，而非创造现象。“创伤记忆”的治疗方法已被各个医学领域的专家所采用。

关键词：创伤记忆、牙科恐惧症、疼痛、恐惧情绪、医疗技术、图像、神经元、丘脑、杏仁核。

Abstract. *In cases of functionally persistent dysregulation in regulatory mechanisms at any level, unstable pathological processes of an entropic nature emerge, which we define as 'Memory of Trauma' – both physical and psychological. Modification of the patient's individual worldview provides additional opportunities for specialists involved in modulating pathological processes, activates the correction of individual experience, and consequently modifies the symptomatology of temporomandibular joint dysfunctions, myofascial pain syndromes, and related systemic diseases. When necessary, a 'target image' is primarily formed in oncology patients. The 'Hypothesis of a Ready-Made Image' addresses the gap: subjective experience is an intrinsic property of signals generated at the level of the parasympathetic nervous system; the thalamus distributes an already formed phenomenon rather than creating it. The methodology of working with 'Memory of Trauma' is utilized by specialists across various domains of medical practice.*

Keywords: *Memory of Trauma, dentophobia, pain, fear emotion, medical technology, image, neuron, thalamus, amygdala.*

Introduction

At the foundation of any anti-entropic system are three conceptually fundamental processes: the capacity to organize, to compete, and to increase in complexity. Ordering is the restriction of freedom: freedom of movement, freedom of interactions, freedom to assume various forms and states; it is the capacity to reduce entropy and to create structure from chaos. The ordering process is characterized by a reduction in entropy, which is possible only through microscopic coupling of processes. This state is steady-state; the concentrations of reactants and products remain constant due to continuous influx of reactants and efflux of products at identical rates; simultaneously, such a system tends toward zero entropy and, consequently, a high degree of adaptability to the environment. A system can leave a stationary state for various reasons: changes in temperature, environmental composition, the influx of new components in the form of material or informational objects, and others. Stationary states of micro- and macrosystems constitute the foundation for the existence of living organisms, requiring a continuous influx of energy and exchange of matter. In cases of instability and nonlinearity of such states (1,2), a complex system may disintegrate into multiple simpler systems, leading to competition among them for energy and matter, which corresponds to the onset of pathology within the organism.

At the level of spatial conformation (isomerism) of molecular structures, the rate of chemical reactions in coupled processes occurs on the femtosecond scale (0.000 000 000 000 001 sec). With an average number of molecules on the contact surface of the human retinal lattice exceeding 1 quadrillion, the scale of such microprocesses in the human body is difficult to conceive; all of these are sources of coded signals (4), which, in our opinion, constitute the «gray signal» (noise),

a first-order information flow. Such signals undergo quantitative and qualitative selection at the level of the optic nerve disk, where the number of rhodopsin molecules amounts to 80 million, indicating the complexity and compression of signals and the formation of complex information represented as a simple feature, i. e., second-order information. The reaction time during photon absorption by 11-cis-retinal, subsequent conformational change of the protein, and activation of the optic nerve is 200 femtoseconds (3), demonstrating extraordinarily high speeds. Disordering, degradation, and disorganization occur concurrently with ordering.

Competition constitutes a fundamental principle of selection at all levels: molecules compete for chemical bonds, cells for nutrients, neurons for trophic factors and synaptic connections, and organisms for environmental resources. Through natural selection (Darwin's theory), structures exhibiting maximal efficiency and minimal free energy evolve. Structures that have been defeated in this competition undergo processes of disordering, degradation, disorganization, or reassignment under more resilient evolutionary mechanisms.

In a living organism, considered as a thermodynamic system, increasing complexity is only possible with an abundance of free energy and the presence of mechanisms for information retention (memory, genome, culture, etc.). A more complex system necessitates the emergence of hierarchical processes, specific differentiation, and integration, wherein energy expenditures are directed toward the formation of more complex anti-entropic structures. The paradox is that the organism seeks to reduce free energy (entropy), while simultaneously, to transition into another, more efficient state, a substantial expenditure of free energy is required. All three processes – ordering, competition, and complexification – operate within any material system, from quarks to the biosphere as a whole(1). In living organisms, these manifest within the function of the nervous system. In our view, the movement of information within the nervous system, involving filtration and integration, must be considered as a fourth, key process in anti-entropic regulation.

Research objective

To substantiate “Memory of Trauma” within the framework of the new hypothesis of a ready-made image.

Materials and methods

The study utilized the most prominent hypotheses and theories concerning the functioning of the nervous system; data analysis and integration were conducted to formulate a single, coherent hypothesis that resolves major paradoxes and gaps in neuroscience. Specific components of the hypothesis were tested and refined using various artificial intelligence models.

In the external environment, there are infinitely many objects emitting signals (photons, sound waves, molecules, etc.); the human organism perceives only a part of them. For example, vision processes the largest volume of data about the external

environment and is associated with the perception of spatially remote objects and processes (5). Bottom-up signal processing occurs according to the systemic principle. At the cellular level, bipolar and ganglion cells integrate signals from numerous photoreceptors via synaptic connections and perform signal summation through convergence of 120 photoreceptors onto one bipolar cell, and several bipolar cells onto one ganglion cell (6, 7, 8).

Hierarchical neuronal processing of the ascending signal flow from a group of cells occurs through thousands of dendrites of a single neuron, where pacemaker activity mediates the subsequent stage of selective signal processing (9). Dendritic cluster, spatial, frequency, resonance-oscillatory, electromagnetic, and other integrations of signals from thousands of synapses result in the convergence of simple features into a complex information packet; these signals sum on dendritic branches and form subcellular computational units, representing third-order information. Frequency coding of signals in the neuron is estimated to range from 1 Hz to 2000 Hz, with a bandwidth capacity on the order of 10^3 bits/sec (10). This allows the neuron to process multidimensional data (color, shape, direction of object movement, line angle, simple sound, etc.) in parallel (11,12), which, in our view, indicates the convergence of primary object representations by the neuron of the peripheral nervous system (PNS), corresponding to fourth-order information. Accordingly, the total sensory input flow from the PNS to the CNS (central nervous system), comprised of qualitatively integrated images, is estimated at 1 billion bits/sec (13) and represents the result of selection of signals received from the organism's cells by the neuron.

The conduction time of a complex signal from the skin pain receptor to the spinal cord via unmyelinated C-fibers is 0.005–0.02 seconds. The signal passes through 1–2 synapses to the neuronal ganglion, where the newly received sensory information is compared with the consolidated information of a group of interconnected neurons for threat to survival, and if matched, reacts via direct synapses with motoneurons, bypassing the higher levels of the nervous system (14). The avoidance reaction duration is 0.02–0.1 seconds (hand retraction upon burn). Information in the nervous system is processed sequentially from molecules, cells, neurons, to neuronal ensembles of spinal ganglia. Considering the assumption that signs and simple images are already formed in PNS neurons, such a model resolves the paradox of temporal binding (Binding problem) and reaction speed, since nerve impulse velocity is too slow to explain instantaneous responses to critical physical environmental factors by conventional means. The emergence of such a reaction requires the formation of a complete structure of features. For example, in burns or trauma, there is exposure to temperature and pressure at their critical thresholds, damage to the cell membrane, alterations in the physical and chemical parameters of the local environment, and conformational changes in molecular systems, accompanied by a sequential intensification of signals and the generation of an informational,

structurally complex flow. A qualitative selection process occurs, integrating into features and converging into a coherent representation of the death of a specific cell, which elicits a response in the synapses of the neuron's dendritic system; when the quantitative magnitude of the information flow from the group of dendrites within the neuron is high, excitation arises as a response to the holistic image of the actual event – the death of a group of cells. When similar information arises simultaneously from other neurons, their summation and integration into a complex image occur, followed by its comparison with the template of the neuronal ensemble at the level of spinal ganglia, thus generating fifth-order information. Upon a match according to the 'key-lock' principle of a complex data packet, excitation is triggered in the motoneuron pathway to initiate withdrawal from the traumatic agent (15); simultaneously, a qualitatively converged, specific holistic image-symbol representing the death of a particular body region is transmitted to the CNS. This represents a fundamental property of the incoming signal to the CNS, where it is compared with the worldview (metamodel of the world).

If the continuous stream of information transmitted from the PNS to the CNS is regarded as a packet of high-level signal-symbols, then in this model the brain is not the center for controlling chaos but rather a global center of spatiotemporal navigation, representing an evolutionarily faster and more energy-efficient system. Such an approach resolves many impasses in modern brain science.

In contemporary neurobiology, it is well recognized that the neuronal code comprises not only spikes but also frequency-based, resonant, electrical, and magnetic interactions, reflecting a packet flow of information from PNS neurons that carries numerous unique profiles as image-reflections of components of the external and internal environments. Considering the thalamus from the standpoint of resonant system physics, wherein each nucleus possesses its own frequency selectivity, the information flow passing through it in the form of signal packets (features, images) either induces resonance within the corresponding nucleus or passes through without eliciting a response (analogous to light unabsorbed by the medium). In this case, information within such a structure is not blocked but interacts – not by a single 'key-lock' parameter, but through a spectrum of interference characteristics that excite specific nuclei and generate echoes in the cerebral cortex, while the remaining information is not filtered out but simply fails to activate the system when mismatched and dissipates without eliciting an elaborated cortical response. This perspective eliminates the central mystery formulated by D. Chalmers. Chalmers describes how subjective experience (qualia) arises from objective physical processes in the brain. The 'ready-made image hypothesis' closes the gap: subjective experience is an inherent property of signals generated at the PNS level, embedded in the pattern at the receptor level, while the thalamus distributes the ready-made phenomenon instead of creating it. Similarly, the problem of binding and perceptual

invariance is eliminated. In the standard model, the brain integrates discrete features of an object (color, shape, motion, etc.), which are processed in different brain areas, into a unified percept. In our model, such spatial integration is not necessary; peripheral sensory systems generate integral images from the outset, where all features are already combined within a single package. In the case of invariance, for instance, if the retina has been preconfigured by evolution and ontogeny to represent a specific color gamut of the object, the brain does not need to compute the constancy of a particular color; the object is perceived immediately in its essential form rather than as a projection. The main paradox of neuroscience is resolved: how the nonmental (electricity) gives rise to the mental (image). It does not arise; it is originally present at the input to the system. In the thalamus, this information flow is distributed to the corresponding cortical regions.

In the new paradigm, the function of the thalamus is fundamentally transformed. It ceases to be a 'relay' and becomes what in computer science is termed a 'semantic dispatcher'; it does not construct the image but selects from numerous parallel inputs arriving from the periphery the most competitive and relevant ones, thereby generating a sixth-order information flow. This explains the party effect, when multiple conversations reach the thalamus as ready-made semantic images, but only one is allowed into consciousness while the others are discarded, rather than their sounds simply being muted. The thalamus possesses powerful feedback connections with the cortex, which outnumber the ascending connections. It compares the ready-made image received from the sensory organs with the predicted image transmitted down from the cortex. When a 'hot' signal arrives from the hand, while the cortex expected 'warm', the thalamus does not simply relay the signal but integrates the ready-made image arriving from the sensory organs with the predicted image sent down by the cortex, transmitting the mismatch – that is, the combined image of 'danger + prediction error'.

Based on the premise that worldview (the metamodel of the world) is distributed across specific fields of the cerebral cortex, and that the thalamus processes ready-made images originating from the PNS, temporal binding of information occurs in the thalamus through the retention of a simple image, while the information packet continues to propagate along thalamo-cortical pathways, generating a resonant echo within the cortex. The sensory image from a finger prick and the motor response last fractions of a second; the subcortical pathway enables processing of threatening stimuli without cortical involvement within 0.01–0.025 seconds, resulting in the execution of an unconscious action. To become aware of pain, it is necessary to retain this pattern and cycle it through thalamocortical loops, like an echo, transforming an instantaneous packet of signals from a neuron into a resonating strategic image in the cortex, where the already occurred event, to which a protective reaction was initiated, is supplemented with details, resulting in an ongoing experience (qualia),

which constitutes seventh-order information. This can explain the slower conscious awareness reaction, lasting 0.3–0.5 seconds, to which the organism has already responded with a faster action.

In standard anatomy, the thalamus is divided into specific, associative, and nonspecific nuclei. In our hypothesis, this division acquires a new functional significance. Specific nuclei are not merely relays but are strictly evolutionarily imprinted genetic templates, simultaneously serving as axioms of worldview. For example, the visual tract constitutes ready-made knowledge about the geometry of space, whereas the somatosensory tract concerns the boundaries of the body. The flow of images is distributed along evolutionarily calibrated pathways. Images requiring semantic interpretation are distributed across the corresponding cortical fields of the associative nuclei. It follows that the architecture of thalamic pathways, projecting ready-made images into strictly defined cortical areas evolutionarily designated for operating specifically with these symbols, constitutes a worldview distributed throughout the entire brain.

Considering the new hypothesis within the framework of predictive coding (K. Friston) and applying logical correction, we arrive at the following conclusions. The thalamus, initially configured to the minimal sufficient pattern capable of eliciting resonance in the thalamic nucleus, evaluates the entire incoming fifth-order information flow for signs of threat. Upon matching a data packet corresponding to a fragment of an image – such as a characteristic bend, movement, or frequency characteristic of a sound – resonance occurs in the thalamic nucleus: it is a snake! Withdraw the hand! This explains why the phobic reaction arises instantaneously, prior to the cortex completing full analysis: the thalamus has already responded to key danger indicators and initiated the amygdalar loop and the motor loop at the level of the spinal ganglia. Meanwhile, the fifth-order informational package is divided into fragments and continues its progression to other cortical regions: to the temporal cortex – where object-specific features are evaluated (what is this?); to the parietal cortex – where spatial features are assessed (where is this located?); to the premotor cortex – where motor features are analyzed (what should be done with this?). In each region, cortical processing of the fragment occurs, details are extracted from the mental representation, and the fragment is supplemented. A descending flow of the eighth order arises, and refined, contextualized versions of fragments enter the thalamus: for instance, this is a snake, it is venomous, and it moves toward you, which leads to an amplification of resonance in the thalamic nucleus and triggers an autonomic storm; alternatively, this is a branch, it moves due to the wind, no resonance occurs, the fragments of information dissipate, no new information loop is formed, and the autonomic response is inhibited by the cortex. Thus, each «thalamus-cortex» loop constitutes a cyclic feedback loop of image reconstruction, whereby each loop adds contextual information and filters out noise.

Using dentophobia as an illustrative case, we examine phobic avoidant behavior within the following model. “Memory of Trauma” (16), as a consequence of the primary perception of a traumatic event, is encoded in the PNS in the presence of pain – the sensation arising from actual cell death (inflammation, injection, pressure or rotation of an instrument, forced retention, etc.); all components forming the image (pain, sound, jaw vibration, tension of the masticatory muscles, white coat, dental odors) are embedded in the PNS. Such an informational package is already identified as threatening at the brainstem level and upon entry into the thalamus. Subsequently, the presence of a sufficient subset of signs matching the dentophobic ‘key’ (transient tooth pain) activates the thalamo-amygdalar pathway, triggering a vegetative response (heart rate increases or decreases, blood pressure rises or falls, etc.). This response is initiated prior to cortical recognition, before the thought ‘I am afraid’ can be articulated. As a result of the functioning of thalamocortical pathways, the image fragments disseminated by the thalamus to specific brain regions are supplemented with attributes and, with the aim of minimizing cognitive dissonance, the data package is returned to the thalamus in the form of a safe context: ‘the threat from the dentist is greater than the threat of caries.’ The prefrontal cortex generates a spatial pathway for avoidance of danger, socially acceptable and logically justified actions: ‘I have urgent work..., now is not the best time...,’ thereby unconsciously rationalizing avoidant behavior. With each cycle, dentophobia intensifies, the activation threshold of the amygdala decreases, and the number of key indicators, both as representations of danger (such as scheduling a medical appointment or passing by a dental clinic) and as avoidance strategies, increases. ()

This model of thalamic and amygdalar function is tactically advantageous, as evolutionarily significant signal packets (images) are competitively selected, thereby reducing energy expenditure for data processing at subsequent stages and enabling rapid spatial withdrawal from threats to cellular and organismal viability. Strategically, such a function may lead to an error in prediction, a discrepancy between actions and actual events, dissonance with the environment, and cause the system to enter a state of increased entropy (an increase in free energy), that is, the development of pathology.

Therefore, the “Memory of Trauma” represents a highly efficient, highly organized resonant circuit within a complex molecular-cellular structure, governed by the nervous system, shielded from correction, and designed for rapid spatial evasion of danger. The development of phobia occurs due to a vicious loop of error; it progresses as a result of the image received from the PNS and the confirmation of its prediction within a closed thalamo-amygdalar circuit containing an erroneous context that does not correspond to reality.

The dominant function of such a circuit never deactivates and leads to systemic exhaustion due to the high energy consumption required to maintain this structure in

a state of tension. Consequences include bruxism, phobias, myofascial pain, over-activation of facial muscles, and primarily dysfunctions of the temporomandibular joint. A sharp decline in quality of life.

Results

As a result of studying the principal hypotheses and theories of brain function, dissecting them into discrete logical sequences, and assembling them into a unified cause-and-effect chain, a new hypothesis concerning ready-made images emerged. The brain is conceived not as a computer for complex, energy-intensive computations nor as a mirror reflecting reality, but as a navigation system for safe routes through reality. The purpose of such a system is survival through safe navigation of the surrounding world by threat assessment; images arising in the PNS act as road signs, thalamo-amygdalar loops provide a mechanism for rough danger evaluation, and thalamocortical loops offer the possibility of route correction or the search for a new path. “Memory of Trauma” represents a cyclical thalamo-amygdalar loop, which, lacking corrective mechanisms within thalamocortical loops, results in a navigational catastrophe. Between 2014 and 2025, over 13,000 patients with various diseases, primarily dental in nature, including more than 200 diagnosed with oncology, were observed in clinical settings. All aforementioned patients were assessed during consultations for the presence of “Memory of Trauma”.

Discussion of results

The traditional paradigm holds that functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) reflects the energetic and computational expenditures involved in stimulus processing. From the perspective of the hypothesis of ready-made images, regions of elevated fMRI activation reflect a complete correspondence between the image from the thalamus and the cortical prediction; consequently, no further processing is necessary, thalamocortical loops are not engaged, and no energy is expended on correction. BOLD signal surge zones arise when the incoming image and cortical prediction do not coincide, necessitating an energy-intensive thalamocortical process of neuronal model reconstruction with concomitant demands for increased blood flow and oxygen. For example: we see a sugar bowl on the table expecting the taste of sweetness, but the PNS transmits an image of saltiness; as a result, a complete discrepancy occurs between the expected and the actual. In such cases, fMRI will demonstrate hyperactivation presenting as subjective surprise, followed by a correction of the gustatory aspect of the worldview. Evolution has developed a rapid and energy-efficient mechanism for correcting pre-existing evolutionary and individual representations, wherein stability is maintained by incoming ready-made images that rigidly anchor us in objective reality without the expenditure of free energy. Adaptability, in turn, is sustained through feedback loop comparisons between the incoming image and the internal representation of one’s worldview, allowing correction exclusively in those areas where mismatches occur, thereby

channeling free energy precisely to these domains without necessitating a complete restructuring of the entire worldview system. When the traumatic image in memory is modified through mental representations and a new, safe exit from the event, the perception of future events changes, and the response of muscle structures shifts from tension to relaxation.

Conclusion.

In the standard model, the brain integrates discrete features of an object (color, shape, motion, etc.), which are processed in different brain areas, into a unified percept. In our model of the 'Ready-made Image,' such spatial binding is not required; peripheral sensory systems from the outset create holistic images in which all features are already integrated within a package. These images are not building materials for an internal copy of the world but serve as landmarks in reality. Safety priority is architecturally ensured: thalamo-amygdalar loops, upon detecting the slightest fragment of a danger image, can intercept control and redirect behavior via an avoidance pathway. The fact that spatial orientation takes place in reality rather than in a static world underscores the primary challenge of the brain: the world is in constant flux, necessitating continuous recalibration of the worldview. In this context, phobia represents a systemic navigational failure, where an outdated, previously effective map is not updated to reflect changes and becomes perceived as the sole path. The navigational system loses plasticity; the brain ceases to verify reality and persistently follows the same avoidance route, even when it leads to catastrophe (in the case of dentophobia: damaged teeth, gastrointestinal disorders, etc.). Further research is required to elucidate the relationship between material and mental (conscious and unconscious) processes, along with the development of psychological interventions aimed at modifying the organism's system of perceiving information from both the external and internal environments. The methodology of working with 'Memory of Trauma' is utilized by specialists across various domains of medical practice. During the procedure, it is established that with full consent and trust, the properties of the organism's systems change in reverse order – from the image and the central nervous system to the manifestations and associated specific cellular systems and molecular structures – via resonance-oscillatory interrelations. Consequently, the signaling architecture of the nervous system and the integrally connected muscular system is altered, with relaxation of the latter indicating a qualitative transformation of the traumatic experience encoded in memory and the acquisition of novel perceptive properties by molecular structures.

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儿童急性肾功能衰竭舒张压昼夜节律的年龄相关特征
**AGE-RELATED FEATURES OF THE CIRCADIAN RHYTHM
OF DIASTOLIC BLOOD PRESSURE IN ACUTE RENAL FAILURE
IN CHILDREN**

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摘要：在最初的13天内，第2组（7至18岁）患者的舒张压（DBP）昼夜节律平均值与第1组相比，差异具有统计学意义，达18%，略高于同龄正常值。两组间DBP昼夜节律平均值的差异主要与幼儿（3岁以下）和7岁以上儿童的血流动力学解剖生理年龄相关特征有关。在幼儿期长期强化治疗的背景下，观察到DBP昼夜节律的平均水平、振幅和日波动范围均持续显著增加。研究发现，舒张压（DBP）的动态变化与肾小球滤过率（GFR）最准确的内源性标志物胱抑素 C 之间存在显著的正相关性（0.81），表明 GFR 直接依赖于 DBP 水平，即 DBP 升高会降低 7 岁以上儿童的肾小球功能。相反，在幼儿期，这种相关性为 -0.42，几乎不存在。在幼儿期，急性肾功能衰竭（ARF）的发生主要归因于 GMT 参数的升高（0.83）以及脱水的负面影响。

关键词：昼夜节律，舒张压，急性肾功能衰竭，儿童。

Abstract.. *Within the first 13 days, patients in group 2 (ages 7 to 18 years) demonstrated a statistically significant difference in the mesor level of the DBP circadian rhythm compared to group 1 by 18%, which slightly exceeded age norms. The difference in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP between groups was primarily related to anatomophysiological age-related characteristics of hemodynamics in children of early childhood (under 3 years) and older than 7 years. In the context of prolonged intensive therapy during early childhood, a sustained significant inclination to increases in the mean level, amplitude, and daily range of fluctuations of the circadian rhythm of DBP was observed. A strong direct correlation was identified between the dynamics of DBP and the most accurate endogenous marker of glomerular filtration rate (GFR), cystatin C (0.81), indicating a direct dependence of GFR*

on DBP level, whereby an increase in DBP decreases the function of the glomerular apparatus in children older than 7 years. In contrast, at an early age this correlation was (-0.42) and was practically absent. At an early age, the leading role in the development of ARF was attributed to the increase in the GMT parameter (0.83) , along with the negative effects of dehydration.

Keywords: circadian rhythm, diastolic blood pressure, acute renal failure, children.

Relevance

Acute renal failure in children is a critically severe condition. It is a nonspecific syndrome that is fatal without urgent medical intervention. Symptoms progress over the course of 2 days. Due to impaired kidney function, blood creatinine concentration rises rapidly. The level of this substance directly depends on the severity of ARF. Acute impairment of kidney function manifests suddenly, as it is most often a complication of another disease. The symptomatology resembles poisoning. Weakness, nausea, vomiting, and fever develop. Due to impaired renal excretory function, urea concentration increases in the urine, and oliguria progressively intensifies over 2–14 days. Oliguria may transition to the stage of ‘clinical recovery.’ At this stage, diuresis is restored, and symptoms of intoxication diminish. However, the child remains in a weakened state, so there is a risk of relapse. If the acute form is not treated in a timely manner, chronic renal failure develops. Another cause of its occurrence is inadequately treated infections of the urinary system. Symptoms of chronic renal failure in both infants and older children depend on the disease stage: latent–asymptomatic; Azotemic – manifest symptoms of systemic intoxication, as well as disorders of the digestive and cardiovascular systems; Decompensated – edema and urinary disturbances develop; Terminal – life-threatening complications occur, kidney function ceases, and the child requires organ transplantation or dialysis.

At present, the most advanced and promising early non-invasive markers of ARF include: lipocalin-2; interleukin-18 (Il-18) in urine; kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM-1) in urine; cystatin C in serum. Cystatin C, although classified among biomarkers of acute kidney injury, is not a direct marker of parenchymal damage but reflects changes in glomerular filtration rate. Cystatin C is currently recognized by the global medical community as the most accurate endogenous marker of glomerular filtration rate (GFR). Cystatin C significantly surpasses creatinine in its diagnostic characteristics and is practically independent of both muscle mass and the child’s age. A meta-analysis encompassing 46 articles and 8 unpublished brief reports, including observational results from approximately 4,500 patients and control group subjects, demonstrated that cystatin C provides a more accurate estimation of the actual (measured) GFR values than creatinine. The correlation coefficient between

cystatin C concentration and GFR was 0.92, compared to 0.74 for creatinine and GFR. Cystatin C is a non-glycosylated protein belonging to the family of cysteine protease inhibitors, identical to post-gamma-globulin; It was first identified in patients with renal failure as a protein in cerebrospinal fluid and urine. It is a protein that: is synthesized at a constant rate by all nucleated cells; is freely filtered through the glomerular membrane; and is completely metabolized in the kidneys; It is not secreted by the proximal renal tubules. According to numerous investigations, under normal conditions serum levels of Cystatin C are determined by a constant rate of its synthesis, which is practically independent of age, sex, or weight; and a constant rate of its elimination from the body, predominantly determined by renal function. In renal pathology, its blood level increases. The more severe the renal pathology, the worse Cystatin C is filtered by the kidneys, and the higher its blood level. Correction of this condition is performed exclusively by dialysis. Without dialysis, there is an increased risk of fatal outcomes, bacterial infection, and development of other complications [1–6]. Due to insufficient information regarding the management of children during extracorporeal blood purification, we aimed to investigate age-related features and assess changes in the circadian rhythm of DBP during comprehensive intensive therapy for renal failure.

Aim of the Study

To investigate age-related features of the circadian rhythm of diastolic blood pressure in acute renal failure in children.

Materials and Methods

Hemodynamic and respiratory system monitoring data were analyzed in 16 children with diseases complicated by renal failure during the phases of oliguria and anuria. Comprehensive intensive therapy included, alongside etiopathogenetic treatment, prosthetic support of respiratory and urinary system functions. Continuous hourly monitoring was performed in two age groups. Group 1 comprised children aged 0.8 ± 0.4 years, including 5 boys and 4 girls. In group 2, examination data of patients aged 13.9 ± 3.2 years were studied; among them, 2 boys and 5 girls. In group 1, the following were identified: pneumonia – focal in 4 cases, polysegmental in 1 case, bilateral; complicated by sepsis in 2 cases, AKI, acute kidney injury in the oligo-anuric stage in 3 cases, HUS in 2 cases, toxic-metabolic encephalopathy in 4 cases, acute respiratory insufficiency of grade 2–3 in 6 cases. Background conditions in 4 children included polycystic kidney disease, congenital nephrotic syndrome, nephromegaly, and AKI in the convalescent stage. In group 2 – systemic lupus erythematosus – 3 cases, Stevens-Johnson syndrome – 1 case, pneumonia – 6 cases, sepsis – 4 cases, rhabdomyolysis complicated by ARF – 1 case, acute nephritis – 1 case, chronic renal failure (CRF) in exacerbation stage – 6 cases, sepsis – 1 case, AKI – 2 cases, congenital malformation – single kidney – 1 case. All patients underwent extracorporeal blood purification (ECBP).

The age-related difference was reflected in the duration of comprehensive intensive therapy, with patients in group 1 staying in the intensive care unit (ICU) for an average of 21.2 ± 12.2 days, while patients in group 2 stayed 12 days less on average (Table 1). Patients in group 1 received 12 ± 7 sessions, whereas group 2 received 6 ± 1.7 sessions, i.e., 50% fewer. In all patients, the CYSC parameter was studied during the first 2 days.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Average values of the phase components of the circadian rhythm of DBP, mmHg

	Mesor	At the acrophase	At the bathyphase	Amplitude	Daily range
Group 1, 10 days	66±2	74±4	58±3	8±4	16±5
Group 2, 10 days	76±1*	84±2*	69±2*	7±1	15±3
Group 1 (11–37 days)	68±3	82±6	56±3	13±4	26±5
Group 2 (11–13 days)	78±1*	84±2	68±2*	7±2	16±3*

Table 2. Dynamics of the mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP, mmHg

days	Group 1	Group 2
1	66±5	78±3*
2	71±2	76±3
3	66±2 ^{'''}	76±3*
4	65±2 ^{'''}	75±2*
5	67±3	76±3*
6	63±3 ^{'''}	73±2*
7	67±4	75±3*
8	67±2	79±2*
9	63±3 ^{'''}	76±3*
10	65±2 ^{'''}	78±5*
11	66±5	78±4*
12	71±4	77±3
13	66±3	79±6*

* – difference is significant relative to the indicator in group 1

''' – significant relative to the indicator on day 2

During the first 13 days, patients in group 2 exhibited a significant difference in the mesor level of the circadian rhythm of DBP compared to group 1 by 18%, somewhat exceeding age-related norms. The tendency for an increase in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP on day 2 in group 1 was due to the instability of the achieved

therapeutic effect. From day 3 onwards, the mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP was consistently reduced compared to day 2 by 7%, 8%, 10% (day 6), 11% (day 9), and 8% (day 10). This reduction was achieved through a combination of adequate anti-inflammatory, vasoactive, and detoxification therapies addressing the identified homeostatic disturbances in children under 3 years of age (Table 2). During the subsequent observation period, from day 14 to day 37, the mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP in group 1 ranged around 67 ± 3 mmHg on day 14, gradually increasing to 76 ± 7 mmHg by day 37. The detected 20% increase in the mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP in group 2 ($p < 0.05$) was primarily associated with anatomophysiological age-related hemodynamic features in children older than 7 years (Table 2).

Table 3. Mean circadian rhythm (MCR) of DBP, mmHg

Hours	Group 1, days 1–10	Group 2, days 1–10	Group 1, days 11–37	Group 2, days 11–13
8	69±4	80±5*	70±4	81±1 *
9	65±3	76±3*	69±5	79±3 *
10	69±4	75±3 *	68±5	80±4 *
11	64±3	76±4 *	68±6	77±5
12	65±2	76±2 *	69±7	75±4
13	65±4	77±3 *	70±6	74±3
14	65±3	78±3 *	69±5	79±3 *
15	67±3	77±4 *	68±6	83±4 *
16	64±5	76±4 *	69±6	83±5 *
17	65±4	77±4 *	69±5	82±3 *
18	66±2	78±3 *	72±6	82±3 *
19	66±3	78±3 *	71±5	81±3 *
20	66±4	76±3 *	68±6	82±5 *
21	67±3	76±2 *	67±6	78±2 *
22	67±4	77±3 *	67±6	79±5
23	67±3	78±2 *	70±7	77±1
24	66±3	76±2 *	66±5	72±5
1	66±3	74±2 *	67±6	73±4
2	66±3	72±4 *	67±6	73±1
3	64±3	74±2 *	64±6	74±6
4	65±2	75±3 *	66±7	76±2
5	66±3	76±3 *	67±6	73±6
6	65±1	76±3 *	69±5	78±1*
7	66±3	77±3 *	69±6	76±5

* – significant difference relative to the value in group 1.

The circadian rhythm of DBP during the first 10 days in the second group of children was significantly higher throughout the day compared to the first group, on average by 11 % (Fig. 1). In the subsequent days, this significant difference in the second group persisted during daytime, but almost disappeared between 11:00 and 13:00, as well as during nighttime hours from 22:00 to 05:00, due to a tendency for increased DBP in patients of the first group during these times (Table 3). Thus, insufficient effectiveness of comprehensive intensive therapy during the night was identified (Fig. 2), which contributed to a sustained tendency toward deterioration of renal excretory function. This was associated with impaired glomerular filtration activity amid reduced perfusion parameters and increased peripheral vascular spasm between 11:00 and 13:00 and during nighttime in children with early-age ARF.

Fig.1. Circadian rhythm of DBP at 10 days, mm

Hg Fig.2. Circadian rhythm of DBP at 11-37 days, mm Hg

During daytime and nighttime over the first 10 days, the average level of the circadian rhythm of DBP in the second group was 10 mm Hg higher than in the first group ($p < 0.05$), being 76 ± 1 mm Hg and 66 ± 1 mm Hg, respectively (Fig.1). In the subsequent days of intensive therapy, despite a general tendency for the values to increase, the significance of this age-related difference was maintained. Thus, between the 11th and 37th days, the variability level of the circadian rhythm of DBP in Group 1 was 68 ± 1 mmHg, and in Group 2 it was 78 ± 1 mmHg (Fig. 2). Therefore, despite more prolonged intensive therapy during early age, there remained a longer-lasting, pronounced tendency toward an increase in the average level of the circadian rhythm of DBP.

Fig. 3. Dynamics of the amplitude of the circadian rhythm of DBP, mmHg.

Fig. 4. Diurnal fluctuations of DBP, mmHg.

The increase in amplitude (Fig. 3) and 24-hour range (Fig. 4) of fluctuations in the circadian rhythm of DBP indicated a prolonged inflammatory process in the renal parenchyma against the background of complex intensive therapy, including sufficiently effective renal replacement therapy (monitored by creatinine, urea, electrolytes, and blood acid-base balance). The most prolonged inversion of the circadian rhythm of DBP was observed during the first 10 days in group 2 (accounting for 50%) (Table 4), which practically disappeared in the subsequent days. These findings can be explained by adequate compensatory reactions of adaptive systems related to the more advanced age-related anatomical and functional characteristics of children in Group 2.

Table 4. Projection of the acrophase of the circadian rhythm of DBP

	9–11 h	12–22 h	23–7 h (inversion)
Group 1, 10 days	30%	50%	20%
Group 2, 10 days	10%	40%	50%
Group 1 (11–37 days)	31%	46%	23%
Group 2 (11–13 days)	33%	67%	0

Fig. 7. Correlation relationships of DBP.

A strong positive correlation was identified between the dynamics of DBP and the most accurate endogenous marker of glomerular filtration rate (GFR), Cys C (0.81), indicating a direct dependence of GFR on DBP levels, where increased DBP reduced the function of the glomerular apparatus of the kidneys in children older than 7 years (Fig. 7). In contrast, this relationship was absent in early age, showing a correlation coefficient of -0.41 . A strong negative correlation between DBP and procalcitonin – a marker of bacterial infections – in the context of a tendency toward an increased mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP (-0.99) indicated a secondary role of infectious disease in the development of ARF in older children. A statistically significant inverse correlation of blood glucose level (-0.91) and ALT (-0.94) with DBP during biochemical fluctuations within physiological limits reflected the risk of hepatocyte energy deficiency under conditions of increased peripheral vascular tone in ARF in older children. Strong positive correlations between DBP and AST (0.91), DBP and ESR (0.94), DBP and blood leukocytes (0.71), and DBP and the number of segmented neutrophils (0.95) confirm the pathogenetic role of the systemic inflammatory response of the body in the development of nephritis and ARF in the second group of children. In early

childhood, an increase in the GMT indicator (0.83) was identified as a leading factor in the development of ARF, indicating the negative impact of dehydration.

Conclusion. During the first 13 days, patients in group 2 exhibited a significantly higher mesor of the circadian rhythm of DBP compared to group 1 by 18%, slightly exceeding age-related normative values. The difference in DBP measurements between the groups was primarily related to the anatomical and physiological age-specific hemodynamic characteristics in children over 7 years old. Following more prolonged intensive therapy in early childhood, there remained a sustained and pronounced tendency toward increased mean level, amplitude, and daily range of fluctuations in the circadian rhythm of DBP. A strong direct correlation was identified between the dynamics of DBP and the most accurate endogenous marker of glomerular filtration rate (GFR), cystatin C (0.81), indicating a direct dependence of GFR on DBP level, whereby an increase in DBP decreases the function of the glomerular apparatus in children older than 7 years. At an early age, this correlation was absent. At an early age, the leading role in the development of ARF was attributed to the increase in the GMT parameter (0.83), along with the negative effects of dehydration.

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使用非医用材料进行牙科自我治疗的风险
**RISKS OF SELF-TREATMENT IN DENTISTRY
WHEN USING NON-MEDICAL MATERIALS**

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摘要：临床牙科实践中一个令人担忧的趋势日益明显，即由于在线市场和平台上销售的未经认证的牙科材料广泛存在，导致患者自行治疗病例增多。患者无菌条件下自行使用此类“填充物”，且不遵循龋洞预备的基本原则，从而为龋病的进展、继发龋的发生以及炎症并发症的出现创造了有利条件。本研究旨在评估患者自行使用未经认证的材料对牙齿硬组织和牙周组织的影响，并分析其应用可能导致的并发症。研究方法包括分析主要在线市场（包括 OZON、Wildberries 和 Yandex Market）上的牙科产品。重点关注作为自我修复牙齿产品（临时修复材料、装饰嵌体、贴面复制品）销售的产品，以及用于临床环境之外的口腔卫生用品。此外，还对上述在线平台上发布的用户评论进行了内容分析。研究人员特别关注附有照片证据的评论，以便直观地评估使用这些产品的效果，并识别牙齿硬组织和牙周组织可能出现的临床改变。使用未经认证的材料进行牙齿自我修复不仅无法解决根本问题，反而会加剧问题。缺乏专业监督以及这些材料的易得性，为可能损害患者健康的各种做法的泛滥创造了有利条件。研究结果强调了提高公众对牙科自我治疗风险的认识的必要性，以及及时咨询合格牙科保健人员的重要性。

关键词：未经认证的材料，自我治疗，并发症，公众意识

Abstract. *An alarming trend is increasingly evident in clinical dental practice, characterized by a rise in self-treatment cases among patients due to the widespread availability of uncertified dental materials sold via online marketplaces and platforms. The application of such 'fillings' is performed independently by*

patients, outside of aseptic conditions and without compliance with fundamental principles of carious cavity preparation, thereby creating favorable conditions for the progression of the carious process, the development of secondary caries, and inflammatory complications. The objective of this study is to assess the effects of uncertified materials used independently by patients on the hard dental tissues and periodontal tissues, as well as to analyze potential complications resulting from their application. The methodology involved an analysis of dental products available on major online marketplaces, including OZON, Wildberries, and Yandex Market. Primary focus was placed on products marketed as agents for self-administered tooth restoration (temporary restorative materials, decorative inlays, veneer replicas), along with oral hygiene devices intended for use outside of clinical settings. Furthermore, a content analysis of user reviews posted on the aforementioned online platforms was conducted. Particular interest was given to reviews accompanied by photographic evidence, enabling visual evaluation of the outcomes of using these products and the identification of potential clinical alterations in dental hard tissues and periodontal tissues. The use of uncertified materials for self-administered dental restoration not only fails to address the initial issue but also predisposes to its aggravation. The absence of professional supervision and the accessibility of these materials create conditions conducive to the proliferation of practices potentially detrimental to patients' health. The results underscore the necessity of enhancing population awareness regarding the risks associated with self-treatment in dentistry, as well as the importance of prompt consultation with qualified dental healthcare providers.

Keywords: *uncertified materials, self-treatment, complications, population awareness.*

In recent years, a concerning trend has become increasingly evident in the clinical practice of dental professionals, characterized by a rise in patient self-treatment cases. Particular attention must be given to the proliferation of uncertified dental materials freely distributed through online marketplaces and platforms. This includes the so-called 'temporary fillings,' decorative overlays, veneer imitations, as well as instruments designed for self-administered procedures within the oral cavity. The availability of such products, their low cost, and aggressive promotion in advertising materials foster a false perception among patients regarding the possibility of substituting qualified dental care with self-administered manipulations. A significant proportion of these materials do not possess validated certification, and their composition is typically undisclosed by the manufacturer. The lack of data on biocompatibility, mechanical strength, polymerization shrinkage, and adhesive properties makes their application potentially hazardous to the tooth's hard tissues and the surrounding periodontal structures [7].

The installation of such ‘fillings’ is performed by patients independently, outside of aseptic conditions and without observing the elementary principles of carious cavity preparation. Consequently, infected tissues persist within the tooth cavity, marginal adaptation of the material is disrupted, and retentive zones for microorganisms are formed. This, in turn, establishes favorable conditions for the progression of the carious process, development of secondary caries, and inflammatory complications. The unknown chemical composition increases the risk of developing localized allergic reactions, irritation of the gingival margin, and chronic inflammation. In several observations, disruption of occlusal relationships can be inferred due to improper shape and height of self-fabricated restorations, which further exacerbate functional impairments and may result in overload of individual teeth [4].

Particular attention should be given to the use of commercially available instruments marketed as ‘scalars’ or as means for dental calculus removal. In the absence of adequate skills and comprehensive understanding of periodontal anatomy, the use of these materials may result in injury to the enamel, root cementum, as well as the surrounding soft tissues. This condition creates additional portals of entry for infection and facilitates the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases [8].

Therefore, the widespread use of uncertified dental materials and instruments by patients in domestic settings constitutes a significant medical and social concern. This issue requires not only clinical evaluation but also broader patient education regarding the potential risks and consequences associated with such self-treatment [1].

The objective of this study is to evaluate the effect of uncertified materials self-administered by patients on the hard dental tissues and periodontal tissues, as well as to analyze the potential complications resulting from their use [5].

Contemporary restorative dentistry predominantly relies on polymer composite materials, which over the past decades have become the cornerstone of direct tooth restorations. They possess several advantages, including high aesthetic properties, the capacity for adhesive bonding, and conservation of dental hard tissues. In addition, glass ionomer cements are widely employed; they are characterized by chemical adhesion to dental tissues and fluoride release, which is particularly important under conditions of increased cariogenic risk. A distinct category includes temporary restorative materials designed for the short-term restoration of the tooth cavity’s seal. Equally important are the physicochemical characteristics, including strength, wear resistance, and durability in the aggressive environment of the oral cavity. The material must preserve its properties when subjected to masticatory forces, moisture, and temperature fluctuations [2].

However, even when using certified materials and following clinical protocols, there remains a risk of complications arising both from the physicochemical properties of the materials and the conditions of their use. This highlights the critical importance of the quality of the materials utilized and suggests a markedly

increased risk associated with the application of uncertified substances of unknown composition [6].

The methodology involved an analysis of dental products available on major online marketplaces, including OZON, Wildberries, and Yandex Market. Primary focus was placed on products marketed as agents for self-administered tooth restoration (temporary restorative materials, decorative inlays, veneer replicas), along with oral hygiene devices intended for use outside of clinical settings. Furthermore, a content analysis of user reviews posted on the aforementioned online platforms was conducted. Particular interest was paid to reviews accompanied by photographic materials, which enabled a visual assessment of the outcomes following the use of these products and facilitated identification of potential clinical alterations in the hard dental tissues and periodontal structures [3].

The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- 1) availability of photographs of adequate quality, allowing visual evaluation of the condition of the teeth and adjacent tissues;
- 2) presence of distinct alterations (defects), the characteristics of which could be clinically analyzed and interpreted.

The selected cases were subjected to descriptive and comparative analyses supported by data from contemporary scientific literature, which enabled the formulation of hypotheses regarding the potential mechanisms underlying the observed alterations and complications.

All images and textual materials utilized in this work were sourced from publicly available repositories and were freely accessible at the time the study was conducted. During an additional stage of the research, efforts were made to establish contact with individual users who had posted testimonials. Participants consenting to engagement completed a questionnaire. Prior to initiating the questionnaire, they provided voluntary informed consent for the use of the submitted information for scientific purposes, in compliance with the principles of anonymity and confidentiality.

Special consideration should be given to portable devices marketed through online marketplaces and promoted as ‘ultrasonic scalers’ intended for self-administered removal of dental deposits. Although these devices externally resemble professional apparatus, their operating principles and technical characteristics significantly differ from those of clinically utilized systems.

The functioning of professional ultrasonic scalers is based on the generation of high-frequency vibrations within the range of 20,000–50,000 Hz, enabling effective removal of dental calculus and the bacterial biofilm matrix. A crucial component is also the water delivery system, which provides cooling to the working tip and facilitates the flushing of disrupted deposits and microorganisms. Furthermore, the aqueous environment participates in the generation of the cavitation effect – formation of microbubbles that promote destruction of bacterial structures and enhance the overall cleaning efficacy.

In portable devices commercially available without restrictions, these essential components are typically absent or implemented in a considerably simplified manner. Numerous models lack a fluid delivery system, thereby precluding both cooling of the working surface and adequate removal of dislodged deposits. This not only diminishes the efficacy of the procedure but also potentially increases the risk of thermal injury to dental and gingival tissues.

Moreover, the purported ‘ultrasonic’ specifications of such devices frequently fail to correspond to their actual technical parameters. Effective removal of dental calculus requires a stable oscillation frequency and sufficient power to produce the cavitation effect. In inexpensive portable devices, significant deviations in frequency and oscillation amplitude occur, resulting in decreased efficiency in the removal of dental deposits. Such devices, in fact, may operate solely as low-vibration mechanical instruments, failing to achieve comprehensive disruption of mineralized deposits.

From a clinical standpoint, this indicates that the use of such devices fails to accomplish the primary objective of the procedure – the removal of dental calculus and bacterial biofilm. Furthermore, in the absence of controlled application force and proper instrumentation technique, there is an increased risk of trauma to both hard and soft tissues. Even within professional practice, it is observed that the effectiveness of ultrasonic and manual scaling is comparable only when appropriate skills and methodological protocols are strictly followed (PMC). In cases of patient self-administration of treatment without prior training, the probability of inappropriate exposure significantly increases.

The absence of adequate sterilization, uncontrolled impact on the enamel and gingival margin, as well as the inability to properly manage subgingival deposits, pose additional risks. Specifically, there is a risk of traumatic gingival injuries, exacerbation of inflammatory processes, and the retention and compaction of dental deposits due to their partial disruption without complete removal.

Thus, portable devices sold on online marketplaces under the guise of ‘ultrasonic scalers’ predominantly fail to comply with the operational principles of professional equipment. Their application does not yield a clinically significant removal of dental deposits and may pose a risk of damage to oral tissues, rendering their use as an alternative to professional hygiene unjustified.

Conclusions

The conducted study determined that the use of uncertified materials for self-administered dental restoration constitutes a widespread practice that has demonstrated an increasing trend in recent years. An analysis of the assortment available on online marketplaces revealed the existence of a substantial number of offers for similar products. Furthermore, individual products are accompanied by a significant number of user reviews (up to 20,000 or more), and the total number of analogous listings amounts to several hundreds. This evidence indicates a high prevalence

of such items and supports the conclusion that their use is widespread. Based on the analysis of the clinical cases presented, it was determined that the independent utilization of such materials entails breaches of the core principles of therapeutic and prosthetic dentistry. The most frequently identified problems include the lack of anatomical tooth morphology, violation of contact points, inadequate marginal adaptation, and violation of occlusal relationships.

The identified disorders create conditions conducive to the development of various complications, including secondary caries, inflammatory periodontal diseases, traumatic occlusion, and functional overloads of the maxillofacial system. In some cases, attempts at self-prosthetic treatment are noted, involving the fabrication of constructions mimicking fixed partial dentures, as well as the unification of several teeth into a single unit, which significantly increases the risk of adverse consequences. Particular attention should be directed to the fact that the majority of the materials examined are marketed as decorative products and are not classified as medical devices. Additionally, information regarding their composition is frequently unavailable, preventing assessment of their safety upon contact with oral tissues.

The results of the conducted interview indicated that the principal reasons for self-administration of such materials are fear of dental procedures, limited financial resources, and insufficient patient awareness of the complexity and specific characteristics of dental treatment. Despite the limited number of clinical cases analyzed within the framework of the present study ($n=6-7$), the data obtained reflect only a small fraction of the overall problem. Considering the extensive distribution of such products, it is reasonable to assume that the number of patients resorting to these methods is substantially higher and may reach tens of thousands.

Therefore, the use of uncertified materials for autonomous dental restoration not only fails to address the underlying issue but also establishes conditions conducive to its aggravation. The absence of professional supervision and the accessibility of these materials create conditions conducive to the proliferation of practices potentially detrimental to patients' health. The results underscore the necessity of enhancing population awareness regarding the risks associated with self-treatment in dentistry, as well as the importance of prompt consultation with qualified dental healthcare providers.

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牙医和修复科医生对患者适应可摘式义齿问题的调查
**SURVEY OF DENTISTS AND PROSTHODONTISTS ON ISSUES
OF PATIENT ADAPTATION TO REMOVABLE DENTAL
PROSTHESES**

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摘要：可摘义齿在功能性使用或其他情况下，都会对与其直接或间接接触的口腔组织和器官产生显著影响。可摘义齿对牙周组织、义齿床黏膜、唾液腺功能、免疫反应和口腔微生物群的不良影响已有充分的文献记载。上述情况对于老年患者尤为重要，因为老年患者不仅牙弓缺损发生率高，而且机体（特别是口腔组织和器官）的适应能力显著下降，无法充分抵消可摘义齿治疗带来的不良影响。本研究对58位牙医和修复科医生进行了调查，旨在评估他们关于优化患者适应可摘义齿过程的方法的了解程度。55%的修复科医生在其临床实践中未使用双层基托（带弹性衬垫的基托）制作可摘义齿。为了加快患者对可摘义齿的适应过程，修复科医生最常推荐使用牙科粘合剂（100%）和局部抗炎药物，包括：氯己定（46%）、角质形成剂（14%）、含维生素制剂（12%）和复合凝胶（17%）。在可摘义齿的卫生维护方面，除了牙刷和牙膏外，主要推荐使用（速溶）片剂（60%）和可摘义齿专用消毒液（26%）。

关键词：适应性，可摘义齿，适应性改善，患者，弹性基托。

Abstract. *Removable prostheses exert a significant impact on the tissues and organs of the oral cavity with which they maintain direct or indirect contact, both during function and otherwise. The adverse effects of removable prostheses on the condition of periodontal tissues, the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, salivary gland function, immunological reactivity, and the oral microbiota are well documented. The foregoing is particularly pertinent for elderly patients, in whom, along with the high prevalence of defects of the dental arches, the adaptive capacity of the organism, specifically the tissues and organs of the oral cavity, is markedly diminished and does not adequately counteract the adverse effects associated with removable prosthetic treatment. A survey was conducted among 58 dentists and prosthodontists to assess their knowledge concerning methods to optimize the process of patient adaptation to removable dental prosthetic devices. 55% of prosthodontist dentists have not used in their practice the fabrication of removable dentures with a two-layer base (base with elastic lining). To accelerate the process of patient adaptation to removable dental prostheses, prosthodontist dentists most frequently recommended the use of dental adhesive agents (100%) and locally acting anti-inflammatory agents, including: chlorhexidine (46%), keratoplastics (14%), vitamin-containing preparations (12%), and combined gels (17%). For hygienic maintenance of removable dental prostheses, in addition to toothbrushes and toothpastes, (rapidly dissolving) tablets (60%) and disinfectant solutions for removable prostheses (26%) were primarily recommended.*

Keywords: *adaptation, removable dental prosthesis, improvement of adaptation, patients, flexible base.*

Despite the continuous development and advancement of treatment methods and technologies utilized in dentistry, the need for prosthodontic treatment among patients has gradually increased in recent years. Meanwhile, the proportion of removable dental prostheses in relation to the total volume of fabricated prosthetic constructions is also increasing. On average, approximately 57% of patients seeking prosthetic care require prosthetic treatment with removable dental prostheses [2]. According to WHO data, about one-third of patients either do not use the removable prostheses fabricated for them or use them only for a short period, indicating low effectiveness of the performed prosthetic treatment due to difficulties or inability of patients to adapt to these dental prostheses [3, 6].

Removable prostheses exert a significant impact on the tissues and organs of the oral cavity with which they maintain direct or indirect contact, both during function and otherwise. At the same time, any prosthesis in the oral cavity, regardless of its design and manufacturing quality, functions as an inadequate stimulus [1, 12]. Some patients exhibit heightened sensitivity to the structural materials used in the fabrication of the prosthesis base plastics. However, the occurrence of allergic

reactions is uncommon, and currently denture stomatitis is infrequently of allergic etiology [10].

The adverse effects of removable prostheses on the condition of periodontal tissues, the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, salivary gland function, immunological reactivity, and the oral microbiota are well documented. There is a high likelihood of the development of microcirculatory, inflammatory, and regenerative disturbances in the oral mucosa to some extent, particularly in elderly patients. Protective functions of the epithelium are diminished: leukocyte migration on the mucosal surface is suppressed, and epithelial cell desquamation markedly increases, which is especially evident at the initial stages of prosthesis use [5].

Removable prostheses adversely impact the specific resistance of the oral cavity. With the progression of inflammatory processes, there is a significant decline in immunological reactivity and the adaptive capacity of the organism, accompanied by disruption in the balance of several immune parameters. Furthermore, reductions in lysozyme and amylase levels in saliva have been observed, along with an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines in the oral fluid associated with the use of removable prostheses [4, 7, 8]. Inadequate prosthesis hygiene promotes contamination of the mucous membrane by microflora, which serves as a nidus for toxoinfection, leading to various pathological changes of both local and systemic nature [9, 13].

The above is especially pertinent to elderly patients, who, alongside the high prevalence of dental arch defects, exhibit significantly reduced adaptive capacity of the body, particularly of the oral tissues and organs, which does not sufficiently counterbalance the adverse effects associated with removable prosthodontics [11]. Therefore, the pursuit of new therapeutic approaches aimed at mitigating these effects of removable dental prostheses on the tissues of the prosthetic bed and, consequently, enhancing the adaptation process is, in our view, an extremely relevant objective in dentistry.

Assessing the level of awareness among prosthodontists regarding possible approaches to optimizing adaptation to removable dental prostheses remains a pertinent topic. A survey was conducted among 58 dentists and prosthodontists to assess their knowledge concerning methods to optimize the process of patient adaptation to removable dental prosthetic devices. The questionnaire was developed in accordance with the guidelines for designing survey questionnaires and conducting surveys, comprising 8 questions. All surveyed prosthodontist dentists had experience in prosthodontic treatment of elderly and senile patients presenting with complex anatomical and topographical conditions of the denture-bearing area. Analysis of the responses to the questions in the developed questionnaire:

Question 1: all surveyed prosthodontist dentists had experience in prosthodontic treatment of elderly and senile patients presenting with complex anatomical and topographical conditions of the denture-bearing area.

Question 2: 55 % of dentists and prosthodontists have not employed the fabrication of removable prostheses with a two-layer base (a base with an elastic lining) in their practice, whereas 45 % utilized this type of dental prosthetic construction under unfavorable anatomical and physiological conditions of the patients' oral cavity.

Question 3: For the fabrication of removable prostheses, dentists used domestic base materials in 69 % of cases and foreign-made materials in 31 % of cases.

Question 4: The most frequently used agents for hygienic care of removable dental prosthetic appliances were cleansing (rapidly soluble) tablets (60 %) and disinfectant solutions for removable prostheses (26 %). Fourteen percent of respondents did not prescribe any products beyond standard hygiene means and items (toothpaste and toothbrush).

Question 5: All practitioners recommended that their patients use dental adhesive agents to enhance retention of removable dental prostheses. Among them, 62 % of dentists and prosthodontists prescribe them, as indicated, only under unfavorable anatomical and physiological conditions, 31 % in the complete absence of teeth, and 7 % always, regardless of the clinical situation.

6th question: the most common forms of adhesive agents were creams and gels (69 %). Twenty-six percent of surveyed dentists and prosthodontists consider that the properties of adhesive agents do not depend on their form of release. The remaining respondents prescribe films (5 %).

Question 7: The most commonly prescribed topical agents by prosthodontist dentists to enhance adaptation to removable prostheses were: chlorhexidine (46 %), keratoplastics (14 %), vitamin-containing preparations (12 %), combined gels (17 %), herbal decoctions (5 %), and NSAIDs (2 %). Additionally, 4 % of respondents do not implement any local treatment.

Question 8: According to the majority of respondents, patient adherence to medical recommendations plays a significant role in the adaptation process (43 %). Fifteen percent of dentists and prosthodontists believe that patients with a lower pain threshold more frequently experience problems related to wearing removable prostheses, resulting in more difficult adaptation. Thirty-nine percent of those surveyed consider that the health status of the patient and the oral cavity negatively impacts the adaptation process to removable dental prostheses. Only 3 % of respondents consider that the primary role in this process is played by the dentist and dental technician.

Thus, the conducted survey of dentists and prosthodontists, aimed at assessing the level of awareness regarding methods to optimize patient adaptation to removable dental prostheses, demonstrated that 55 % of dentists and prosthodontists did not utilize the fabrication of removable prostheses with a two-layer base (a base with an elastic lining) in their clinical practice. To accelerate the process of patient adaptation to removable dental prostheses, prosthodontist dentists most

frequently recommended the use of dental adhesive agents (100%) and locally acting anti-inflammatory agents, including: chlorhexidine (46%), keratoplastics (14%), vitamin-containing preparations (12%), and combined gels (17%). For hygienic maintenance of removable dental prostheses, in addition to toothbrushes and toothpastes, (rapidly dissolving) tablets (60%) and disinfectant solutions for removable prostheses (26%) were primarily recommended.

The demand for prosthodontic care among elderly and advanced-age patients with dental arch defects has increased in recent years. Removable prostheses exert a significant impact on the tissues and organs of the oral cavity with which they maintain direct or indirect contact, both during function and otherwise. The investigation of new therapeutic interventions aimed at reducing the effects of removable dental prostheses on the tissues of the prosthetic bed in patients – and thereby improving the adaptation process – is, in our view, a highly relevant objective in dentistry. Assessing the level of knowledge among dentists and prosthodontists regarding methods to optimize patient adaptation to removable dental prostheses is both relevant and essential for evaluating awareness of these methods.

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医科大学学生结核病危险因素
**RISK FACTORS FOR TUBERCULOSIS AMONG MEDICAL
UNIVERSITY STUDENTS**

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摘要。引言：医学生结核病的发生发展受多种因素影响，包括学习和临床实践期间与结核病患者接触，以及影响学生免疫状态的社会经济和医学生物学因素。本研究旨在调查医科大学高年级学生结核病危险因素的存在情况和患病率，以制定预防策略。材料与方法：本研究于2022年至2026年间，通过面对面问卷调查的方式，对477名俄罗斯医科大学五年级和六年级学生（其中男生109名，女生368名）的结核病危险因素进行了分析。结果：所有医学生在结核病门诊的培训和临床实践期间均接触过结核病患者。研究发现，以下社会经济因素是结核病的危险因素：21.2%的学生居住在宿舍或租房，9.2%的学生有贷款或债务。69.2%的学生因兼顾学习和医疗机构工作而导致作息不规律。68.5%的学生饮食不规律，17.8%的学生蛋白质和维生素摄入不足，54.5%的学生食用干零食，10.5%的学生体重过轻。19.9%的学生吸烟，28.4%的学生不进行体育锻炼，39.6%的学生不参加体育运动。在医疗风险因素方面，3.6%的学生有结核病家族史，14.3%的学生患有慢性躯体疾病，2.5%的学生正在接受免疫抑制剂的长期治疗，38.4%的学生承受着持续的心理压力。结论。为预防医学生结核病，需要：在大学内创造良好的学习、休息和宿舍生活条件；组织健康饮食；营造良好的学生心理氛围；开展抗压项目和健康促进活动；并通过教育活动提高学生对接触病及其个人预防方法的认识。

研究局限性：研究对象为俄罗斯联邦公民，且均为医科大学学生。

关键词：医科大学学生；调查；结核病危险因素；预防。

Abstract. *Introduction The development of tuberculosis among students of medical educational institutions is influenced by contact with tuberculosis patients during their studies and clinical practice, as well as by socio-economic and medico-biological factors that determine the immune status of the students. The aim of the study is to examine the presence and prevalence of risk factors for tuberculosis among senior students of the medical university to determine prevention tactics. Materials and methods. An analysis of the presence of tuberculosis*

risk factors was conducted among 477 Russian medical university students in their 5th and 6th years through face-to-face surveys carried out in 2022–2026, including 109 male and 368 female students. Results. All medical students, during their training and clinical practice in the tuberculosis clinic, had contact with tuberculosis patients. The following socio-economic risk factors for tuberculosis were identified: 21.2% of students lived in dormitories or rented accommodation, and 9.2% had loans or financial debts. A suboptimal work and rest regimen resulting from the combination of studies and employment in healthcare institutions was observed in 69.2% of students. Irregular eating habits were reported by 68.5% of students, 17.8% had diets deficient in protein and vitamins, 54.5% consumed dry snacks, and 10.5% were underweight. Tobacco products were smoked by 19.9% of students, 28.4% did not engage in physical exercise, and 39.6% did not participate in sports. Among medical risk factors, it was established that 3.6% of students had a history of tuberculosis in blood relatives, 14.3% had chronic somatic diseases, 2.5% were receiving long-term treatment with immunosuppressants, and 38.4% were under constant psycho-emotional stress. Conclusion. For the prevention of tuberculosis among medical students, it is necessary to: create favorable conditions at the university for studying, resting, and living in dormitories; organize healthy nutrition; establish a favorable psychological climate within the cohort; implement anti-stress programs and health improvement tours, and increase the level of knowledge of students about tuberculosis, as well as methods of individual disease prevention through educational activities.

Study limitation(s). Medical university students, citizens of the Russian Federation.

Keywords: *medical university students; survey; risk factors for tuberculosis; prevention.*

Introduction

It is known that epidemiological, socio-economic, and medical risk factors play an important role in the infection of the population with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) and in the development of tuberculosis disease [2; 3]. Students of higher educational institutions constitute a high-risk group for tuberculosis due to exposure to a combination of adverse factors: changes in the educational and social environment, substantial psycho-emotional stress, inadequate nutrition, and insufficient attention to their health [1]. It has been shown that the incidence of tuberculosis among students from various universities is 1.6 times higher than among their non-student peers [1]. Medical university students, during their studies and clinical practice in institutions of various profiles, inevitably encounter patients with tuberculosis of various localizations, creating conditions conducive to their potential infection and disease [10; 11]. Furthermore, in recent years, many senior students have combined

university studies with employment in healthcare facilities attended by patients with tuberculosis, thereby permitting their classification as healthcare workers. Medical professionals, in the course of their professional activities, as a result of contact with patients with tuberculosis, face an increased risk of both latent tuberculosis infection [9; 13] and developing active tuberculosis disease [14]. However, in tuberculosis disease among medical students, in addition to contact with tuberculosis patients, socio-economic and medical risk factors play a significant role – living conditions, financial status, comorbidities and other medical conditions [7; 17], malnutrition, regularity of meals, sufficient protein and micronutrients in the diet, optimal duration of sleep and rest [6], immunodeficiency, diabetes mellitus, malignant neoplasms, pregnancy, smoking and alcohol consumption [15; 8], inadequate organization of educational outreach, and non-compliance with infection control measures when working with patients suspected of tuberculosis or tuberculosis patients in clinical settings [5]. It is known that stress, poor sleep, and depression among university students significantly impair the body's immune function [12], which may lead to developing tuberculosis. Activities conducted in educational institutions promoting a healthy lifestyle and enhancing students' physical activity represent an effective measure for preventing tuberculosis among this population [16].

The objective of this study is to examine the presence and prevalence of risk factors for tuberculosis among senior students of a medical university in order to determine strategies for implementing preventive interventions.

Materials and Methods

Study design: sociological; **method:** analytical. An analysis of the presence of tuberculosis risk factors was performed among 477 Russian students in the 5th and 6th years of the therapeutic, pediatric, and medical-preventive faculties at Voronezh State Medical University named after N. N. Burdenko, based on a survey conducted with the students' voluntary written consent during 2022–2026. Among them were 109 (22.85%) male students and 368 (77.15%) female students. All risk factors were analyzed according to the generally accepted categories: epidemiological, socio-economic, and medical-biological factors. Students who came from other countries to study were not included in the research.

Statistical analysis of the results was conducted using Microsoft Excel and Statistica 10 software. A 95% confidence interval (CI) was determined.

Results

Analysis of statistical data from the Voronezh Regional Tuberculosis Dispensary demonstrated that in recent years the number of Russian students diagnosed with tuberculosis across all higher education institutions in the city of Voronezh has significantly declined. Thus, while during the period 2012–2015 there were annually between 6 and 13 cases, in the period 2022–2025 the number of affected students ranged from 1 to 4.

In the course of this study, known epidemiological risk factors for tuberculosis among medical university students included contact with tuberculosis patients during clinical examinations in the inpatient department of the tuberculosis dispensary as part of their training at the phthysiology department. Furthermore, it was established that 100 (20.96%; 95% CI 17.31–24.69); students had confirmed short-term contact with tuberculosis patients during their professional duties as mid-level medical personnel in other healthcare institutions in the city, and 20 (4.19%; 95% CI 2.39–5.99) students had household tuberculosis contact.

Among the socio-economic factors, it should be noted that 28 (5.87%; 95% CI 3.76–7.98) students resided in environmentally disadvantaged regions prior to university enrollment, which generally exerts a negative effect on the overall reactivity of the organism and the functioning of certain organs and systems.

One hundred and one (101; 21.17%; 95% CI 17.50–24.84) students resided outside their parents' family, either in a dormitory or in a rented apartment. This generally increases the number of interpersonal contacts and fails to provide a comfortable living environment, precludes adequate rest, and the high cost of rent diminishes the student's material standard of living. An assessment of the socio-economic well-being of students revealed that 68 (14.26%; 95% CI 11.12–17.40) students came from families with many children, and 18 (3.77%; 95% CI 2.06–5.48) considered their parents' financial situation to be not entirely satisfactory, which limited their expectations for significant financial support. A total of 198 students (41.51%; 95% CI 37.09–45.93) did not receive scholarships, and 10 students (2.10%; 95% CI 0.81–3.39) had dependent children. Consequently, 44 students (9.22%; 95% CI 6.62–11.82) were compelled to obtain bank loans and other financial credits.

The analysis revealed that a considerable proportion of students (330 individuals, 69.18%; 95% CI 65.04–73.32) combined their studies with employment in city medical institutions as mid-level medical staff, which typically results in disruption of the optimal balance between cognitive work and rest, reduces time allocated to physical education and sports, causes increased fatigue and nervousness, and subsequently lowers the body's resistance to infectious diseases, including tuberculosis. It was established that 116 students (24.32%; 95% CI 20.47–28.17) combined studying with work during daytime hours, 75 (15.72%; 95% CI 12.45–18.99) worked exclusively night shifts, and 139 (29.14%; 95% CI 25.06–33.22) had alternating day-and-night shift schedules. A total of 177 students (37.11%; 95% CI 32.77–41.45) worked 1–2 times per week, while 153 (32.08%; 95% CI 27.89–36.27) worked three or more times per week.

Non-compliance with the proper balance of work and rest regimes, coupled with insufficient financial support, contributed to inadequate nutrition among students, which, as is well known, increases the body's susceptibility to infectious diseases. Thus, 242 (50.73%; 95% CI 46.24–55.22) students evaluated their diet

as nutritionally adequate but irregular, while 85 (17.82%; 95% CI 14.39–21.25) reported an irregular diet lacking sufficient protein, vitamins, and micronutrients. A total of 260 (54.51%; 95% CI 50.04–58.98) students consumed dry snacks instead of a full lunch. Fifty (10.48%; 95% CI 7.73–13.23) students were underweight. Did not participate in physical activity: 135 (28.35%; 95% CI 24.31–32.39), did not participate in sports or sports events – 189 (39.62%; 95% CI 35.23–44.01) university students. Did not go on wellness trips during holidays (holiday homes, tourist bases, sanatoriums): 273 (57.23%; 95% CI 52.79–61.67) students.

Harmful habits reduce resistance to infections. The analysis revealed that 273 (57.23%; 95% CI 52.79–61.67) students smoked tobacco products, 38 (7.97%; 95% CI 5.54–10.40) consumed alcoholic beverages once per week, and 11 (2.31%; 95% CI 0.96–3.66) more than once per week.

The presence of medical risk factors for tuberculosis was identified in a number of students. Specifically, 17 (3.56%; 95% CI 1.90–5.22) students were presumed to have a genetic predisposition to tuberculosis (with affected blood relatives), and 65 (13.63%; 95% CI 10.55–16.71) students had been registered in childhood at a tuberculosis dispensary due to altered tuberculin sensitivity in the Mantoux test with 2 TU PPD-L. Our research using the skin test with recombinant tuberculosis allergen (ATR test) demonstrated that 3.6% of 5th- and 6th-year students had latent tuberculosis infection [4], which may progress to active tuberculosis in the presence of risk factors.

Medical risk factors for tuberculosis include various chronic somatic diseases and conditions that impair immunity and increase susceptibility to tuberculosis, as well as treatment regimens involving drugs with immunosuppressive properties. It was found that 23 (4.82%; 95% CI 2.90–6.74) students had chronic nonspecific respiratory diseases, 13 (2.73%; 95% CI 1.27–4.19) had peptic ulcer disease of the stomach or duodenum, 29 (6.08%; 95% CI 3.94–8.22) had chronic genitourinary diseases, 3 (0.63%; 95% CI –0.08–1.34) had oncological pathology at various sites, 62 (13.00%; 95% CI 9.98–16.02) suffered trauma or underwent surgery within the past year, and 163 (34.17%; 95% CI 29.91–38.43) students frequently (more than twice a year) suffered from acute respiratory viral infections. Eleven (2.46%; 95% CI 1.07–3.85) students underwent long-term courses of treatment with glucocorticosteroids and immunosuppressants in recent years. Nine (1.89%; 95% CI 0.67–3.11) students had pregnancies and childbirths, and eight (1.68%; 95% CI 0.53–2.83) students had pregnancies followed by termination (abortion/miscarriage).

The analysis of the psychoemotional status of students identified constant psychoemotional tension in 183 (38.36%; 95% CI 34.00–42.72) students, attributed to disruptions in work and rest schedules during periods of significant mental workload. A predisposition to stress reactions was reported by 272 students (57.02%; 95% CI 52.58–61.46), while 24 students (5.03%; 95% CI 3.07–6.99) consulted a psychotherapist or psychiatrist.

The survey data revealed a negligent attitude of students towards their own health. Upon the appearance of symptoms of any illnesses, 110 students (23.06%; 95% CI 19.28–26.84) frequently did not seek medical attention and engaged in self-medication without physician's prescription. Irregular fluorographic screening was performed in 22 (4.61%; 95% CI 2.73–6.49) students. Therefore, it is advisable to organize annual screening of students using the tuberculin skin test with recombinant tuberculosis allergen for early detection of latent tuberculosis infection, with the aim of conducting additional diagnostic evaluation and preventive therapy.

Conclusions

1. Medical university students, upon beginning clinical studies and contact with tuberculosis patients, are at risk of infection with the tuberculosis pathogen; the presence of social and medical risk factors may provoke disease development both through exogenous infection by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and through endogenous reactivation of healed primary tuberculosis lesions due to immunosuppression.

2. Among medical students, a significant proportion were found to experience psycho-emotional overstrain (38.4%) and a predisposition to stress reactions (57.0%), necessitating attention from the university's psychological service towards student health and the organization of anti-stress measures.

3. Analysis of survey data from medical students revealed the need for regular and effective university efforts to promote a healthy lifestyle, organize healthy nutrition and leisure activities, conduct and actively involve students in annual medical examinations, increase physical activity through participation in sports events, and enhance students' awareness of tuberculosis prevention methods via continuous educational outreach.

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早产儿围产期中枢神经系统损伤的发病机制和临床表现特征
**FEATURES OF THE PATHOGENESIS AND CLINICAL
MANIFESTATIONS OF PERINATAL DAMAGE TO THE CENTRAL
NERVOUS SYSTEM IN PREMATURE NEWBORNS**

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摘要：由于脑形态功能不成熟、脑血管自动调节功能受损、抗氧化系统活性降低、代谢过程异常、能量不足以及可塑性低下，胎龄不足的儿童最易受到慢性宫内缺氧和急性出生时窒息的损害。本研究旨在分析新生儿期神经系统疾病的发病机制，并揭示不同胎龄早产儿的神经系统特征。方法：对75例不同胎龄早产儿的神经系统状况进行比较评估。采用动态方法进行神经系统评估，并使用通用电气Voluson 730型超声诊断仪和频率为3.5-5.5 MHz的传感器进行神经超声检查。结果：研究发现，胎龄小于31周的早产儿，其中枢神经系统（CNS）最严重的损伤（包括III度脑缺血、II度和III度脑室内出血以及脑室周围白质软化）的发生率显著高于胎龄大于28周的足月儿（ $p < 0.05$ ）。结论：早产儿最易发生围产期中枢神经系统损伤，且其体重增加与胎龄缩短有关。

关键词：脑缺血，脑室内出血，脑室周围白质软化，早产。

Summary. *Gestationally immature children are most prone to the damaging effect of chronic intrauterine hypoxia and acute intranatal asphyxia due to morpho-functional immaturity of the brain, impaired cerebrovascular autoregulation, decreased activity of antioxidant systems, features of metabolic processes, energy deficit and low level of plastic processes. The purpose of the study: to*

analyse pathogenetic mechanisms of development of neurologic pathology of the neonatal period and to reveal features of the neurologic status at prematurely born children of various gestational age. Methods. the comparative assessment of the neurologic status at 75 prematurely born children of various gestational age is carried out. In dynamics the assessment of the neurologic status was carried out, neyrosonografichesky research with use of the device Voluson 730 General Electric and sensors with a frequency of 3,5–5,5 MHz was conducted. Results: it is revealed that children with gestational age have less than 31 weeks, the most severe defeats of central nervous system (CNS) presented by cerebral ischemia of the III degree, intra ventricular hemorrhages (IVG) II and the III degrees, periventricular leukomalacia (PVL) meet authentically ($p < 0,05$) more often in comparison with the children born in gestation term more than 28 weeks. Conclusion: prematurely born children are most subject to perinatal defeats of CNS, weight which accrues in process of decrease in gestational age.

Keywords: cerebral ischemia, intra ventricular hemorrhage, periventricular leukomalacia, prematurity.

An important medical and social problem is the increase in morbidity and disability of children associated with perinatal lesions of the central nervous system of hypoxic, hemorrhagic, metabolic and infectious origin. Gestationally immature children are most prone to the damaging effect of chronic intrauterine hypoxia and acute intranatal asphyxia due to morpho-functional immaturity of the brain, impaired cerebrovascular autoregulation, decreased activity of antioxidant systems, features of metabolic processes, energy deficit and low level of plastic processes. So, if the frequency of perinatal lesions of the central nervous system, depending on the nature of the course of the ante- and intranatal periods, in full-term babies ranges from 15% to 60%, then in premature babies this indicator increases to 65%-85%. Damage to the central nervous system of various origins in premature babies, due to predisposing circumstances, can lead to the formation of persistent neurological disorders with subsequent chronization of the process, disability, social maladjustment and a decrease in the quality of life in general. In the structure of childhood disability, 70%-80% of neurological pathology has perinatal genesis [4, 6].

The pathogenetic aspects of the formation of perinatal hypoxic damage to the central nervous system primarily include cerebral hypoperfusion, which develops due to an increase in hypoxia and hypercapnia against the background of a general redistribution of blood flow in conditions of fetoplacental insufficiency. These metabolic changes lead to a pronounced vasoconstrictor effect in the cerebral vascular bed and further impaired autoregulation of cerebral blood flow (initially defective in a premature baby). Hypoxic damage to the vascular endothelium with the development of edema-destructive processes in it with a decrease in the capillary bed lumen also contributes to an increase

in resistance to cerebral blood flow. The cerebral vasoconstrictor effect is facilitated by electrolyte changes against the background of hypoxia in the form of a decrease in extracellular calcium, accompanied by an increase in vascular tone [2].

An important role of the rheological properties of blood in the development of cerebral hypoxia and hemorrhagic brain damage has been established. An infectious process, chronic somatic pathology in the mother, acute intranatal asphyxia can lead to a hypercoagulable orientation of the hemostasis system with the development of thrombosis in the microvasculature, leading to the formation of foci of ischemia with subsequent necrotization of brain tissue and the development of pseudocysts at the necrosis site with replacement by connective tissue in the future [4, 13]. However, in premature infants suffering from chronic intrauterine hypoxia, hypocoagulation is more common with a predisposition to the development of hemorrhagic lesions of the central nervous system, represented more often by subependymal and intraventricular hemorrhages (IVH), the source of which is the hermenative matrix of the lateral ventricles. Intraventricular hemorrhages based on hypoxia are one of the main causes of death and account for about 70% in premature babies. The development of IVH is associated with metabolic changes in the form of activation of lipid peroxidation against the background of a decrease in antioxidant activity, activation of anaerobic glycolysis with lactic acidosis, an increased content of malondialdehyde, and hyperglycemia [7, 8, 11]. But, in premature babies, hyperglycemia is more often replaced by hypoglycemia due to depletion of liver glycogen due to prolonged antenatal and acute intranatal hypoxia, as well as due to the development of adrenal insufficiency and a decrease in the stimulating effect of glucocorticoids on gluconeogenesis due to a decrease in their formation. Consequently, the energy supply of cerebral reparative and neurophysiological processes is sharply reduced due to a decrease in the level of the main energy substrate of the nervous system – glucose. The imbalance in the processes of lipid peroxidation and antioxidant activity also affects the level of the erythrocyte membrane, reducing the content of reduced glutathione and thereby leading to a decrease in elasticity and an increase in rigidity of erythrocyte membranes, which reduces the deformability of red blood cells, increases their aggregation ability and leads to the development of thrombosis not only in the central nervous system, but also in the vascular bed of other organ systems, predisposing, against the background of general hypocoagulation, to the development of disseminated intravascular coagulation syndrome [11, 13, 14].

The predominance of the anaerobic pathway of glucose metabolism in hypoxic conditions leads to the depletion of neuronal energy reserves due to a decrease in the formation of adenosine triphosphate, the accumulation of free radicals, disruption of ion channels and depolarization of presynaptic neurons, leading to the release of aspartate and glutamate, excitatory amino acids that activate the receptors of the postsynaptic neuron. Activation of these receptors is accompanied by the opening

of ion channels for K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , the flow of these electrolytes, and with them water, into the neuron, the development of intracellular cytotoxic edema and the death of the neuron. This process is cascading and can spread to areas of the brain tissue that were not susceptible to hypoxia, thereby significantly expanding the focus of the lesion. Intracellular edema with the subsequent death of the neuron can also cause an imbalance in the production of antidiuretic hormone both in the form of hyperproduction and with a decrease in its formation. In addition, hypoxia is initially accompanied by suppression of capillary formation even in the antenatal period, which reduces the intensity of cerebral perfusion, and also damages the endothelium of already formed vessels, leading to thrombosis and vasoconstriction. Against this background, cerebral ischemia increases the intensity of the process of apoptosis of neurons and neuroglia, the severity of which depends on the severity of cerebral ischemia and the duration of exposure to the hypoxic factor [9, 10, 13].

The topic of hypoxic damage to the brain tissue depends on the architectonics of the vascular bed. So in premature babies, the most vulnerable area with the least number of capillaries and anastomoses is the periventricular areas, severe hypoxic damage to which is accompanied by destruction of the periventricular nervous tissue – periventricular leukomalacia (PVL). Basal ganglia and thalamus are also affected. The location and type of brain tissue damage also depends on the duration of hypoxia. Thus, acute asphyxia leads mainly to focal lesions in the form of thrombosis, leading to the development of regional necrosis, while chronic oxygen starvation of the nervous tissue is accompanied by diffuse changes in the form of cytotoxic edema, which is more typical for premature babies [12, 16].

Thus, hypoxic brain damage is pathogenetically a complex, multicomponent process involving cerebral hypoperfusion with the development of circulatory and hemic hypoxia against the background of metabolic, neuroregulatory, rheological disorders and combined somatic pathology [17]. Despite the prerequisites in the architectonics of the cerebral capillary bed of premature babies for pronounced compensatory capabilities due to abundant capillary branching and a developed network of anastomoses, antenatal pathology leading to the birth of a gestationally immature child increases the sensitivity of brain tissue to the action of damaging factors, reducing the effectiveness of compensatory-adaptive mechanisms [1, 3, 11].

The purpose of the study is to analyze the pathogenetic mechanisms of the development of neurological pathology of the neonatal period and to identify the features of the neurological status in premature babies of various gestational ages.

Materials and methods.

A randomized prospective study of 75 premature infants with gestational age from 26 to 36 weeks, body weight from 700 gr. to 2990 gr. during the first three months of life. Children were divided into 4 groups according to gestational age: 1 group – 14 children with gestational age less than 28 weeks, 2 group – 18 children

with gestational age 28–31 weeks, 3 group – 22 children with gestational age 32–34 weeks, 4 group – 21 children with gestational age 35–37 weeks. In dynamics, the neurological status was assessed, a neurosonographic study was carried out using the Voluson 730 General Electric apparatus and sensors with a frequency of 3.5–5.5 MHz. Transphenolic sectoral neurosonography was performed on the fifth day of life, at the end of 1, 2 and 3 months of life (every 10–14 days – according to indications, in the presence of occlusion of the cerebrospinal tract, ventriculitis) according to a generally accepted method in the anterior coronary section, middle coronary section, posterior coronary section through the cerebellum and through the plexus, medial sagittal section, paramedial sagittal section. During neurosonography, subependymal hemorrhages (SEH), IVH with a breakthrough into the ventricular cavity without its expansion and with expansion, IVH with a breakthrough into the periventricular parenchyma were visualized. Levene M. J., Crespighny L. C.H., modification of K. V. Vatolin were used to determine the degree of HBC [5, 8, 15].

The criteria for diagnoses of perinatal lesions of the central nervous system in the neonatal period corresponded to the classification approved by the Russian Association of Perinatal Medicine Specialists [6]. Statistical data processing was carried out using the Statistica 15 program.

Results and its discussion.

A direct correlation between the gestational age and the severity of cerebral ischemia (CI), the degree of IVH, the incidence of PVL was revealed ($r = 0.64$, $r = 0.56$, $r = 0.71$, respectively, $p < 0.05$). Children with gestational age less than 28 weeks (group 1) were characterized by a significant ($p < 0.05$) predominance of grade III CI – 64.3%, in 85.7% of cases combined with IVH: grade I IVH (21.4%), grade II (50%), grade III (14.3%). PVL occurred in 21.4% of children. Children with a gestational age of 28–31 weeks (group 2) had a higher incidence of grade II CI (88.9%) with a predominance of grade II IVH (44.4%) ($p < 0.05$). The incidence of PVL in this group was 16.6%. Both groups were characterized by the predominance of diffuse changes on the neurosonogram with pronounced signs of immaturity and smoothing of the pattern of brain furrows. Patients in groups 3 and 4 were characterized by the lowest frequency of PVL, as well as similar distribution of the frequency of CI and IVH. Thus, in group 3, there was a decrease in the total number of cases of IVH with a predominance of grade I IVH – 31.8%, grade II IVH occurred in 13.6% of cases, grade III IVH – in 4.5% of cases, in group 4 the number of children with grade I and II IVH was 23.8%, 4.8%, respectively, against the background of a significantly ($p < 0.005$) predominant in both groups Grade II CI.

According to the results of dynamic observation, 96% of all examined children developed ventriculomegaly at the end of the first month of life, the severity of which depended mainly on gestational age, the degree of IVH, as well as the presence of concomitant CNS infection, represented by ventriculitis, complicated in

some cases by obstruction at the level of Mozhandi and Lyushko holes. By the end of the third month of life, 48.6% of children with ventriculomegaly had regression of the ventricular system dilation. In the case of PVL, by the second month of life, cystic transformation of the affected areas of the brain tissue took place.

Clinically, according to the results of assessing the neurological status, CNS depression syndrome prevailed, including a decrease in neuro-reflex activity, muscle hypotension, and a decrease in spontaneous motor activity. In 23 (30.7%) patients included in the study (9 patients from 3 groups and 14 patients from 4 groups), by the end of the early neonatal period, depression syndrome was replaced by hyperexcitability syndrome, represented by increased motor activity, tremor of the limbs and chin, increased oral and spinal unconditional automatisms, emotional anxiety. Children with gestational age less than 35 weeks were characterized by the persistence of CNS depression syndrome throughout the neonatal period. Convulsive syndrome occurred in all study groups with a statistically significant predominance in children in groups 1 and 2. Thus, episodes of tonic and clonic-tonic convulsions, accompanied by vegetative-visceral disorders, impaired breathing rhythm up to apnea, decreased muscle tone and neuro-reflex activity in groups 1, 2, 3 and 4 of the study were noted in 42.9%, 38.9%, 27.3%, 14.3%, respectively.

Conclusion. Thus, the maximum degree of damage to the central nervous system is characteristic of children with a gestational age of less than 31 weeks with a predominance of diffuse changes in the brain tissue and the development of further pronounced ventriculomegaly with cystic transformation of necrosis areas in the case of PVL.

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抗氧化剂治疗急性化脓性多鼻窦炎-上颌筛窦炎患者的临床疗效
**CLINICAL EFFICACY OF ANTIOXIDANT THERAPY IN PATIENTS
WITH ACUTE PURULENT POLYSINUSITIS – MAXILLARY
ETHMOIDITIS**

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注释。本研究旨在通过抗氧化剂、益生菌和益生元联合治疗，提高慢性化脓性筛窦炎患者的临床疗效。95名年龄在32至39岁之间、诊断为J01.8“急性化脓性筛窦炎”的患者参与了本研究，研究内容包括免疫状态以及血清过氧化过程。所有患者被分为3组：第1组（30例）为对照组（健康供体），第2组（28例）为接受传统治疗的急性鼻窦炎患者，第3组（37例）为接受抗氧化剂治疗的患者。研究期间，观察到使用抗氧化剂治疗后，脂质过氧化活性和蛋白质氧化修饰均呈现较为稳定的积极降低趋势；治疗后，慢性鼻窦炎患者血液中非酶促抗氧化系统相关参数——还原型谷胱甘肽（GSH）和蛋白质硫醇化合物（SH⁻）的含量水平升高，表明治疗有效。采用抗氧化剂的治疗方案能够稳定并恢复慢性（化脓性）鼻窦炎患者的主要生化和免疫指标，实现长期缓解且无疾病进展。长期无复发表明，对慢性（化脓性）鼻窦炎患者体内环境进行综合药物治疗，是预防内脏器官和系统并发症发生的因素之一。

关键词：急性化脓性多发性鼻窦炎，鼻窦炎，抗氧化疗法，免疫状态。

Annotation. *The aim of the study was to improve the clinical efficacy of combination treatment for patients with chronic purulent ethmoiditis using antioxidant, probiotic, and prebiotic agents. Ninety-five patients aged 32–39 years with*

a diagnosis of J01.8 “Acute purulent ethmoiditis” participated in the study, which conducted a study of the state of the immune status, as well as peroxidation processes in the blood serum. All patients were divided into 3 groups: Group 1 (30 patients) – control (donors, healthy), Group 2 (28 patients) – patients with acute sinusitis who received traditional treatment, Group 3 (37 patients) – patients who additionally received antioxidant therapy. During the study, with the use of antioxidant therapy, a fairly stable positive trend in the reduction of lipid peroxidation activity and oxidative modification of proteins was observed; the level of content of parameters of the non-enzymatic link of the antioxidant system – reduced glutathione (GSH) and protein thiol compounds (SH-) in the blood of patients with chronic sinusitis after treatment increased, which also indicated the effectiveness of the treatment. The use of a treatment regimen using antioxidant therapy allowed for the stabilization and normalization of the main indicators of the biochemical and immunological status in patients with chronic (purulent) rhinosinusitis, long-term remission and the absence of disease progression. The long-term absence of relapses of the disease allows us to consider complex pharmacological correction of the internal environment of the body in patients with chronic (purulent) rhinosinusitis as a factor preventing the development of complications in the internal organs and systems of the body.

Key words: *acute purulent polysinusitis, sinusitis, antioxidant therapy, immune status.*

Introduction. Chronic purulent polysinusitis, like acute forms, occupies a leading place in the structure of otolaryngological diseases [8]. Recent epidemiological studies indicate that these are the most common respiratory diseases in modern society. Chronic polysinusitis, especially with frequent exacerbations, is characterized by decreased reactivity of local and systemic factors of the immune system, reducing patients’ productivity and quality of life [5,9].

The ineffectiveness of traditional treatment for various forms of purulent rhinosinusitis, despite the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, is most often associated with the development of antibiotic resistance in pathogenic microflora, as well as the immunosuppressive effect of antibiotics, and, as a result, severe dysbiosis [1,4]. Insufficient knowledge of the mechanisms of inflammatory reactions in chronic rhinosinusitis at the molecular and cellular level also indicates the ineffectiveness of traditional treatment for this pathology. As is known, with inflammation of the nasal mucosa and paranasal sinuses, mucus production by goblet cells and glands of the submucosal layer increases [10,11]. The biological rationale for this reaction lies in increasing the thickness of the protective layer of epithelial cells. As a result of phagocyte activation, xanthine oxidase reactions (oxidation of hypoxanthine, xanthine) and the conversion of nitric oxide to nitrosoic cation significantly increase

prooxidant production [2,6]. A local shift in the redox potential toward oxidative values promotes goblet cell hyperplasia and, consequently, mucus hyperproduction. It is known that mucus hyperfunction is initially a protective reaction, but under certain conditions it can turn into a pathogenic factor [3,7,12]. All this leads to stasis and creates favorable conditions for microbial colonization of the mucous membrane, their proliferation, and deeper penetration into the tissue, leading to further chronic inflammation. Thus, stasis of viscous mucus on the surface of the epithelial lining of the nose and paranasal sinuses is a direct consequence of oxidative stress.

The aim of the study is to increase the clinical effectiveness of complex treatment of patients with chronic purulent sinusitis with drugs of antioxidant, pro- and prebiotic action.

Methodology. The study involved 95 individuals aged 32–39 years with a diagnosis of J01.8 “Acute purulent maxillary ethmoiditis,” whose immune status and serum peroxidation processes were examined, and 30 healthy individuals. All patients were divided into 3 groups. Group 1 (30 patients) was a control group (donors), Group 2 (28 patients) included patients with acute maxillary ethmoiditis who underwent conventional treatment, and Group 3 (37 patients) included patients who additionally received antioxidant therapy.

Patients in group 2 received traditional treatment: broad-spectrum antibiotics (cefixime, ceftriaxone and others, taking into account sensitivity to microflora), decongestants (xylometazoline, phenylephrine) and local nasal antibacterial sprays (framycetin, neomycin, polymyxin B).

Patients in Group 3 received antioxidant therapy in addition to conventional therapy (TT). The nasal cavity and paranasal sinuses (PNS) were irrigated with a 0.01% hydrogen peroxide solution once daily for 2–3 weeks, followed by a repeat irrigant wash 15 minutes later with a 1.67% emoxypine succinate solution (Mexidol) in 0.33% novocaine (Patent No. 2394567). To restore intestinal eubiosis, Linex Forte, a drug with pre- and probiotic activity, was prescribed per os (1 capsule twice daily).

Results and discussion. Along with traditional clinical and laboratory tests, the levels of immunoglobulins of the main classes (IgA, IgM, and IgG) were determined in the peripheral blood. The intensity of free radical oxidation was assessed by determining the level of malondialdehyde (MDA), oxidative modifications of protein (OMP), and the activity of superoxide dismutase (SOD), glutathione peroxidase (GP), and thiol protein compounds (SH-). Lipid and protein peroxidation is known to be a critical regulator of cell membrane function and an indicator of stability. Determining lipid peroxidation status is necessary to assess the activation of peroxidation processes observed during the development of inflammation, particularly in polysinusitis (sinusitis sinusoiditis), in order to promptly and adequately address the issue. The results of the immunological and biochemical study of patients with acute purulent sinusitis showed that almost all the studied parameters of the

immunological and biochemical status were quite variable. Statistical analysis of the mean values of Groups 2 and 3 and comparison with similar values for individuals in the control group (Group 1) revealed statistically significant differences in the parameters studied during the acute inflammatory stage. This is particularly true for hypergammaglobulinemia of IgM proteins, elevated circulating immune complexes (CICs)—markers of autoaggressive processes in patients – as well as the intensity of free radical oxidation and metabolic disturbances in the antioxidant defenses of both enzymatic and non-enzymatic components.

When studying the immunoglobulins of the main classes (IgA; IgM; IgG) in patients with polysinusitis after traditional treatment (group 2), it was found that the average IgA levels (g/l) slightly decreased and amounted to 3.2 ± 0.02 g/l versus 3.9 ± 0.03 g/l before treatment. Whereas the level in individuals in the control group 1 was 1.2 ± 0.04 g/l. Differences between groups were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). When studying serum IgM levels in patients with acute purulent ethmoiditis after treatment, only a downward trend was noted. Average IgG levels remained high compared to donors (15.0 ± 0.04 g/L and 9.7 ± 0.88 g/L, respectively, $P < 0.05$).

Conventional therapy for patients with acute purulent maxillary ethmoiditis also failed to improve the oxidative stress profile detected in these patients upon admission. After conventional treatment, the prooxidant-oxidant imbalance persisted. Meanwhile, in Group 3, antioxidant therapy demonstrated a fairly stable positive trend in reducing lipid peroxidation and protein oxidative modification. The results of comparison of the levels of the studied parameters MDA and OMB in group 3 patients with maxillary ethmoiditis before and after treatment decreased by 2.0 and 2.5 times, respectively. Analysis of the activity of the enzymatic link of the antioxidant system (SOD and GP) in the blood serum of patients of group 3 after treatment indicated a decrease in these parameters: superoxide dismutase – by 1.5 times, and glutathione peroxidase – from 1.42 ± 0.61 U/ml against 0.50 ± 0.03 U/ml before treatment. The level of content of parameters of the non-enzymatic link of the antioxidant system – reduced glutathione (GSH) and protein thiol compounds (SH-) in the blood of patients with acute sinusitis of group 3 after the treatment increased, which also indicates the effectiveness of the treatment.

The imbalance in the prooxidant and oxidant systems (i.e., activation of free radical oxidation of lipids and proteins and suppression of antioxidant defense (enzymatic and non-enzymatic components) in patients with acute rhinosinusitis largely returned to normal after a course of treatment with the proposed method. Peroxidation products (MDA, OMB) statistically significantly decreased, enzyme activity (SOD, GP, GR) increased, and the content of reduced glutathione and protein thiol compounds (SH-groups) increased. That is, oxidative stress “decreased” due to increased antioxidant defense (enzymatic and non-enzymatic components).

Conclusion. The data obtained from this study suggest that stabilization and normalization of key biochemical and immunological parameters in patients with chronic (purulent) rhinosinusitis, long-term remission and absence of disease progression, and the absence of relapses suggest that comprehensive pharmacological correction of the internal environment in patients with chronic (purulent) rhinosinusitis can prevent the development of complications affecting internal organs and body systems.

The recommended method of treating patients with chronic purulent sinusitis by pharmacological correction of oxidative stress is quite effective, easy to implement, well tolerated by patients, does not cause any side effects, requires the use of available domestic drugs, and can be used in both inpatient and outpatient settings.

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新生儿先天性肺发育不全伴双侧气胸：一例致命病例的临床观察
**CONGENITAL PULMONARY HYPOPLASIA WITH BILATERAL
PNEUMOTHORAX IN A NEWBORN: A CLINICAL OBSERVATION
WITH A FATAL OUTCOME**

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摘要：本文报道了一例罕见的先天性呼吸系统疾病——足月新生儿（妊娠41周）肺发育不良和肺发育不全的临床观察。该病例的特殊之处在于，婴儿出生时状况良好，但随后迅速进展为严重的呼吸衰竭、难治性低氧血症和双侧张力性气胸。尽管采取了包括高频通气和胸腔引流在内的一系列综合复苏措施，但患儿仍于出生后第一天死亡（存活时间12.5小时）。尸检结果显示，肺组织发育停滞于晚期小管期（宫内妊娠23-26周），回顾性分析发现，这与母亲在妊娠17-18周时感染的严重冠状病毒（COVID-19）感染相关。这一观察结果凸显了产前诊断的重要性，并探讨了宫内感染在先天性肺发育不良发病机制中的潜在作用。

关键词：新生儿，先天性肺发育不良和肺发育不全，气胸，妊娠期新冠肺炎，新生儿死亡率。

Abstract. *This article presents a clinical observation of a rare congenital pathology of the respiratory system – pulmonary dysplasia and hypoplasia in a full-term newborn (41 weeks of gestation). A distinctive aspect of the case is the birth of the infant in a satisfactory condition, followed by a rapid progression to severe respiratory failure, refractory hypoxemia, and bilateral tension pneumothorax. Despite the application of a comprehensive set of resuscitation procedures, including high-frequency ventilation and pleural drainage, a fatal outcome was confirmed on the first day of life (survival time 12.5 hours). Autopsy findings demonstrated arrest of pulmonary tissue development at the late canalicular stage (23–26 weeks of intrauterine life), which retrospectively correlates with the maternal severe coronavirus infection (COVID-19) contracted at 17–18 weeks of gestation. This observation highlights the importance of prenatal diagnosis and discusses the potential role of intrauterine infection in the pathogenesis of the defect.*

Keywords: *newborn, congenital dysplasia and pulmonary hypoplasia, pneumothorax, COVID-19 during pregnancy, neonatal mortality.*

Significance

Congenital pulmonary hypoplasia and dysplasia represent severe and life-threatening malformations of the respiratory system. This pathology is characterized by underdevelopment of lung tissue, reduction in lung mass and volume, as well as disruption of structural and functional differentiation of the respiratory tract [1, 2].

Primary (idiopathic) pulmonary hypoplasia, occurring in isolation and not associated with secondary factors (such as congenital diaphragmatic hernia, marked oligohydramnios, or skeletal dysplasias), is an extremely rare condition characterized by a high neonatal mortality rate [3, 4]. Epidemiological data indicate that the frequency of primary pulmonary hypoplasia detection ranges from 1 to 4 cases per 10,000 live births. According to autopsy results, this pathology accounts for up to 10–15% of neonatal mortality causes [5, 6].

The etiopathogenesis of primary hypoplasia remains incompletely understood; however, the role of teratogenic influences, including severe viral infections contracted by the mother during critical periods of embryonic and fetal development, has been established [7, 8]. Diagnostic assessment of this defect is associated with considerable objective challenges. Prenatal screening relies on expert ultrasonographic evaluation (assessment of the fetal thoracic circumference and calculation of the lung-to-head ratio – LHR) as well as fetal magnetic resonance imaging [9, 10, 11]. In the postnatal period, the differential diagnosis between primary hypoplasia and severe infectious lesions (notably congenital pneumonia) in urgent neonatology poses a challenging clinical problem [12, 13].

Disease manifestation typically occurs in the early neonatal period (within the first hours or days of life) and is characterized by the development of refractory

progressive respiratory failure. The addition of complications such as air leak syndromes (spontaneous pneumothorax) fatally worsens the prognosis and necessitates urgent surgical intervention [14, 15].

Final verification of the diagnosis in most cases is only possible based on autopsy findings with morphometric evaluation of lung tissue (including the radial alveolar count and the ratio of lung mass to body mass) [8, 11].

To date, data accumulated during the pandemic in the international literature indicate an association between maternal COVID-19 infection and adverse perinatal outcomes, including preterm birth, fetal growth restriction, and placental abnormalities [16, 17, 18, 19]. At the same time, information on the specific influence of COVID-19 on the organogenesis and morphogenesis of the fetal respiratory system remains limited, and the pathogenetic mechanisms of potential effects remain under discussion. Some studies suggest that the SARS-CoV-2-associated inflammatory response and placental dysfunction may affect intrauterine fetal development, including the morphogenesis of the respiratory system [20, 21]. This highlights the need for further investigation into the impact of intrauterine infections on embryogenesis and postnatal outcomes. The presented clinical case report is relevant in the context of studying the long-term consequences of coronavirus infection during pregnancy and expanding the understanding of the role of SARS-CoV-2 as a potential risk factor for the development of dysplastic lesions in the fetal respiratory system.

Objective of the study: To demonstrate a rare clinical case of congenital dysplasia and pulmonary hypoplasia in a full-term newborn, which led to the development of bilateral tension pneumothorax and a fatal outcome, as well as to analyze the possible association of the malformation with maternal SARS-CoV-2 infection.

Patients and Methods: We present a clinical observation with a fatal outcome of a full-term female newborn, born on 25.02.2024 at the Perinatal Center of the State Budgetary Healthcare Institution Burdenko Neurosurgery Clinical Hospital.

A retrospective analysis of medical records was conducted, including the newborn's developmental history, intensive care unit charts, results of laboratory tests (respiratory insufficiency blood gases, biochemistry, hemostasiogram), and instrumental investigations (radiography, ultrasound, echocardiography), as well as the forensic (pathological-anatomical) autopsy report. All therapeutic and diagnostic procedures performed in the inpatient setting were conducted with the voluntary informed consent of the patient's parents.

Results

The medical history revealed that the child was born from a second pregnancy, during which the mother had a laboratory-confirmed COVID-19 infection at 17–18 weeks of gestation accompanied by a fever reaching 39 °C. At 29–30 weeks of gestation, ultrasound examination diagnosed fetal growth restriction relative to gestational age. The female newborn was delivered at 41 weeks gestation from

a second spontaneous delivery, weighing 3010 g and measuring 47 cm in length. The Apgar score was 8 at both 1 and 5 minutes. The condition at birth was considered satisfactory, with neonatal breathing pattern (respiratory rate 44/min) and stable hemodynamics.

Fifteen minutes after birth, a rapid deterioration occurred: worsening respiratory distress, onset of acrocyanosis, decreased oxygen saturation (SpO₂ 83%), and diminished breath sounds accompanied by crepitant rales. Assessment according to the Downes score was 3 points. The infant was switched to CPAP (PEEP 6 cm H₂O, FiO₂ 40%), but the condition continued to progressively worsen (SpO₂ fell to 68%, Downes score – 6 points). Endotracheal intubation was performed, and mechanical ventilation was initiated in HFO mode (high-frequency oscillatory ventilation).

Chest X-ray demonstrated signs of bilateral tension pneumothorax. An emergency thoracocentesis and drainage of both pleural cavities with active suction were performed by a pediatric surgeon at 2 hours of life.

At admission, laboratory blood gas analysis revealed severe decompensated mixed acidosis (pH 6.748; pCO₂ 111 mmHg; pO₂ 9.7 mmHg; base excess –18.8 mmol/L). During the clinical course, marked hyperglycemia (up to 22 mmol/L) and lactic acidosis (15 mmol/L) were observed. According to NSG data – edema of the brain parenchyma.

Intensive care: rigid HFO ventilation was performed (FiO₂ 100%), high-dose inotropic support with maximal doses of three agents (dopamine 15 µg/kg/min, adrenaline 4 µg/kg/min, dobutamine 10 µg/kg/min), antibacterial therapy (amibactam + amikacin), analgesosedation (fentanyl), anticonvulsant therapy, correction of acidosis with sodium bicarbonate, and insulin therapy.

Despite ongoing therapy and adequate pleural cavity drainage, hypoxemia remained refractory (SpO₂ did not exceed 62–70%). At 12 hours and 30 minutes of age, cardiac arrest occurred in the context of progressive multiple organ failure. Resuscitation efforts were unsuccessful. Biological death was confirmed.

The clinical diagnosis included unspecified congenital pneumonia, spontaneous bilateral tension pneumothorax, infectious-toxic shock (ITS), and stage III respiratory failure. However, the pathomorphological examination revealed a significant discrepancy between the clinical evaluation and the morphological findings.

Based on the medicolegal autopsy results: Primary pathological diagnosis – dysplastic architecture of the pulmonary tissue characterized by developmental arrest at the late canalicular stage (23–26 weeks of intrauterine life). The radial alveolar count (RAC) was 3, reflecting marked pulmonary tissue immaturity. Decreased lung volume was noted, along with a reduced lung-to-body mass ratio (less than 0.012): right lung – 20 g, left lung – 13.7 g with a body weight of 3220 g. Bullous transformation of the pulmonary tissue was observed, predisposing to spontaneous rupture.

Complications included bilateral pneumothorax accompanied by multiorgan failure (edema of the brain and spinal cord, hydroperitoneum, and protein dystrophy in the liver).

Discussion

In the presented case, the clinical picture during the first minutes of life (Apgar score 8/8) was misleading, as the initial respiratory efforts compensated for the infant's condition. However, dysplasia of the lung tissue (presence of bullae, stromal immaturity) and severe pulmonary hypoplasia failed to ensure adequate gas exchange, resulting in spontaneous rupture of bullae and the development of fatal bilateral tension pneumothorax.

The etiology of the defect merits special attention. The cessation of lung development occurred at the canalicular stage (the phase of bronchiole and primary capillary network formation), which normally spans from the 16th to the 26th week of gestation. It was precisely during this period (17–18 weeks) that the mother experienced a severe course of coronavirus infection (COVID-19) characterized by marked hyperthermia. Maternal viral injury and systemic inflammatory response may have acted as a trigger for disrupted embryogenesis of the fetal pulmonary tissue.

Conclusions:

1. Congenital pulmonary hypoplasia and pulmonary dysplasia in full-term newborns may manifest immediately after birth as rapidly progressive respiratory failure and spontaneous pneumothoraces that are resistant to the most advanced respiratory support methods, including high-frequency oscillatory ventilation (HFO).

2. Maternal coronavirus infection (SARS-CoV-2) during the second trimester of pregnancy, coinciding with the canalicular phase of fetal lung organogenesis, constitutes a potential risk factor for the development of severe forms of congenital pulmonary dysplasia. It is probable that viral exposure and the associated maternal systemic inflammatory response acted as triggers for disruptions in embryonic pulmonary tissue development.

3. This clinical case illustrates significant challenges in the prenatal differential diagnosis of congenital pulmonary malformations and neonatal pneumonias in an emergency clinical context.

4. The findings underscore the necessity for meticulous monitoring of fetal intrauterine development during viral infections in pregnant women accompanied by pronounced systemic inflammatory responses.

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高水平手球运动员心动周期的相位结构及其在竞技期体能训练负荷优化中的作用

THE PHASE STRUCTURE OF THE CARDIAC CYCLE IN HIGHLY QUALIFIED HANDBALL PLAYERS AS A BASIS FOR OPTIMIZING PHYSICAL TRAINING LOADS DURING THE COMPETITIVE PERIOD

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摘要：本文探讨了高水平手球运动员心动周期生理的理论和实践方面。这类运动员的心动周期相位结构具有特定的时序特征。本研究考察了参加俄罗斯手球锦标赛超级联赛和顶级联赛的高水平运动员在比赛期间的心脏形态学和血流动力学参数，以及这些参数与心动周期各相位时序指标的相关性。

关键词：适应；心肌；心动周期相位；二尖瓣血流；形态学参数；运动负荷；高水平运动员；不同类型的运动负荷。

Abstract: *The article considers the theoretical and practical aspects of cardiac cycle physiology in highly qualified athletes representing handball as a team sport. The phase structure of the cardiac cycle in this category of athletes has specific timing features. The study examines morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the heart and their correlations with timing indices of cardiac cycle*

phases during the competitive period in highly qualified athletes competing in the Premier League and Super League of the Russian Handball Championship.

Keywords: *adaptation; myocardium; cardiac cycle phases; transmitral blood flow; morphometric parameters; physical load; highly qualified athletes; different types of physical loads.*

Introduction

Long-term endurance training leads to autonomic remodeling of cardiac rhythm with increased cardioprotective activity of the vagus nerve [19]. From the perspective of autonomic rhythm regulation, trained individuals usually demonstrate a negative correlation between heart rate and heart rate variability [19]. According to L. A. Bockeria (2009), to improve the accuracy of heart rate variability assessment, this method should be combined with additional diagnostic methods such as echocardiography (EchoCG), including the assessment of stroke volume and ejection fraction [2].

Since heart rate (HR) and heart rate variability are negatively correlated, analysis of cardiac cycle phases in relation to the morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of the left ventricle is relevant in athletes exposed to different types of physical load. This relevance is supported by correlations between isovolumic relaxation time (IVRT) and pedagogical test results found in our previous studies of qualified handball players [17, 18].

Ventricular systole begins with an electromechanical latency period during which excitation spreads through the myocardium without mechanical contraction; its duration is approximately 20 ms. This is followed by asynchronous contraction lasting about 34 ms. At the end of this phase, the atrioventricular valves close [8, 14]. The next phase is isovolumic contraction time (IVCT), a hemodynamic parameter that can be measured during EchoCG [12].

The ejection period is assessed by pulsed-wave Doppler imaging as ejection time (ET) from the left ventricular outflow tract through the aortic valve into the aorta [12]. The systolic phase is followed by diastole [8].

The diastolic phase is the part of the cardiac cycle during which myocardial relaxation and ventricular filling occur. The initial phase of relaxation is the protodiastolic interval. It is followed by isovolumic relaxation time (IVRT, ms), characterized by a rapid decrease in intraventricular pressure. This parameter is measured by continuous-wave or pulsed-wave Doppler and normally lasts 70–100 ms [12, 15].

The aim of this study was to obtain new data on the adaptive capabilities of a physiologically normal heart in highly qualified handball players exposed to different types of physical load during the competitive period. The simultaneous assessment of physiologically normal morphometric cardiac parameters and timing parameters of systolic and diastolic components of the cardiac cycle may

help to clarify adaptation mechanisms and optimize training loads during the competitive period.

Mathematical Statistics Methods

Statistical processing was performed using STATISTICA 8.0. The significance of differences was assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis ANOVA test. Data are presented as Mean \pm SE. Correlation analysis was used to identify relationships between the studied parameters. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Research Methodology and Organization

The study involved 19 highly qualified athletes from the main roster of a team regularly competing in the Super League of the Russian Handball Championship. Three members of this team participated in an international friendly tournament in Ganzhou, China, on May 12–16, 2026, where the Russian national team took first place. The study was conducted during the competitive period of the 2024–2025 season. The athletes were 18–32 years old; the mean age was 24.7 ± 5.6 years, and sports experience ranged from 10 to 20 years. All athletes had medical clearance for professional sport in accordance with the legislation of the Russian Federation.

Individual physical development parameters were assessed, including body mass index (BMI, kg/m^2) and body surface area (BSA, m^2) [7]. Morphometric and hemodynamic cardiac parameters were assessed using Echo-Doppler cardiography as part of medical support and continuous functional monitoring of a Super League team. A Mindray Z60 diagnostic ultrasound system was used.

The measured left ventricular (LV) remodeling parameters included left ventricular myocardial mass (LVMM, g), left ventricular myocardial mass index (LVMI, g/m^2), ejection fraction (EF, %), stroke volume (SV, ml), and relative wall thickness (RWT). Normal LV geometry was defined as $\text{RWT} < 0.42$ with normal LVMI values below $115 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ for men and below $95 \text{ g}/\text{m}^2$ for women [7, 12, 20].

Hemodynamic parameters of diastolic and systolic function included peak early diastolic filling velocity (Peak E), peak atrial systolic filling velocity (Peak A), E/A ratio, IVRT, IVCT, deceleration time of early diastolic filling (DT), mitral ET, aortic ET, and diastasis time. These indicators correspond to the systolic, early diastolic, and late diastolic phases of the cardiac cycle [12, 15].

Discussion

The results of the assessment of individual anthropometric data and morphometric myocardial parameters in athletes during the autumn and spring phases of the competitive period are presented in Table 1. No statistically significant differences were found between the stages of the competitive period ($p > 0.05$). The myocardial parameters of the tested highly qualified athletes corresponded to normal LV geometry.

Table 1 shows that LVMI and RWT remained within the parameters of normal LV geometry. A slight increase in LVMM and LVMI during the annual competitive period may indicate adaptive myocardial changes caused by different types of

physical load. However, these parameters remained within the range of normal LV geometry according to current recommendations [20].

Table 1. Indices of physical development and morphometric parameters of the myocardium in highly qualified handball players during the competitive period, n=19 (Mean \pm SE), p<0.05

No.	Parameter	Autumn 2024	Spring 2025
1	BMI	25.4 \pm 2.6	25.6 \pm 2.4
2	Body surface area, m ²	2.27 \pm 0.18	2.27 \pm 0.17
3	LVMM, g	202.97 \pm 41.72	210.3 \pm 34.96
4	LVMI, g/m ²	89.75 \pm 15.77	92.42 \pm 12.17
5	LV RWT	0.35 \pm 0.03	0.35 \pm 0.03
6	SI	0.65 \pm 0.07	0.65 \pm 0.07

Table 2. Hemodynamic parameters of the heart in highly qualified handball players during the competitive period, n=19 (Mean \pm SE), p<0.05

No.	Parameter	Autumn 2024	Spring 2025
1	Resting HR, bpm	57.9 \pm 3.6	56.6 \pm 3.7
2	E/A, a. u.	2.43 \pm 0.51	2.32 \pm 0.30
3	IVRT, ms	88.4 \pm 11.3	91.5 \pm 9.6
4	Mitral ET, ms	766.4 \pm 149.7	789.3 \pm 138.6
5	Aortic ET, ms	300.1 \pm 36.6	308.6 \pm 41.1
6	IVCT, ms	80.9 \pm 12.2	82.1 \pm 10.1
7	DT, ms	147.2 \pm 12.1	142.0 \pm 11.7
8	Diastasis, ms	373.8 \pm 140.1	422.7 \pm 158.2

Table 2 indicates that a resting HR below 60 bpm (bradycardia), or a tendency toward bradycardia, may be considered a hemodynamic marker of an athletic heart with a supernormal transmitral blood flow pattern (E/A ratio > 2.0 a.u.) while normal LV geometry is preserved [13, 16, 19].

Figure 1. Parameters of transmitral diastolic blood flow showing supernormal remodeling.

The systolic part of the cardiac cycle presented in Table 2 reflects the time spent ejecting blood from the LV outflow tract through the aortic valve into the aorta. No significant correlations were found between systolic timing parameters and HR values. This may be explained by the predominant influence of sympathetic nerves on LV myocardial innervation, in contrast to the left atrium, where autonomic innervation includes both parasympathetic and sympathetic influences [10].

The correlations between individual morphometric and hemodynamic parameters of cardiac function are of particular interest. Stroke volume (SV) was positively correlated with LVMM ($r=0.72$) and LVMI ($r=0.67$), while a negative correlation was found with LV RWT ($r=-0.70$). Among hemodynamic parameters of the diastolic phase, mitral ET showed a strong negative correlation with resting HR. Diastasis time showed a strong positive correlation with mitral ET ($r=0.91$), which was associated with a decrease in resting HR.

Our findings in qualified handball players competing in the Premier League and Super League of the Russian Championship are consistent with previous studies [8]. From a sports practice perspective, both IVRT and its correlations with indicators of physical fitness may have practical application (Figure 2).

A high correlation was found between IVRT and step frequency during aerobic running load at HR 150–156 bpm ($r=0.82$), as well as with the Cooper test distance ($r=0.82$). A negative correlation was also observed between IVRT and the 300 m running test time ($r=-0.62$). Blood lactate concentration at the 3rd minute of recovery after the 300 m run was correlated with IVRT ($r=0.63$). Athletes with longer IVRT may have greater recovery capacity after glycolytic loads. IVRT was also negatively correlated with systolic blood pressure before the Cooper test ($r=-0.69$).

Figure 2. Correlations of IVRT with indicators of physical performance, metabolism, and systemic circulation

Figure 2. Correlations of IVRT with indicators of physical performance, metabolism, and systemic circulation.

Conclusions

1. Studying cardiac cycle phases in professional athletes is essential for evaluating and analyzing the distribution of timing parameters between systolic and diastolic components.

2. Differentiation of systolic and diastolic components of the cardiac cycle makes it possible to study correlations between hemodynamic and morphometric parameters of the athlete's heart more precisely during the competitive period.

3. The diastolic component of the cardiac cycle is correlated with HR and contributes to a decrease in resting HR.

4. Analysis of timing parameters of cardiac cycle components makes it possible to assess at which HR values the most effective cardiac cycle parameters are observed during different physical loads.

5. Phase indicators of the cardiac cycle may have practical application for distributing different physical loads in the training process of highly qualified handball players during the competitive period.

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肥胖患者体液调节循环系统机制的特征

**FEATURES OF HUMORAL MECHANISMS OF REGULATION OF
THE CIRCULATORY SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH OBESITY**

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摘要：全球肥胖症患病率的上升伴随着心血管疾病死亡率增加。其发展的关键机制是慢性低度炎症和氧化应激引起的内皮功能障碍。在肥胖症中，肥大的脂肪组织（尤其是内脏脂肪）成为活跃的内分泌器官，分泌肾素-血管紧张素-醛固酮系统（RAAS）的多种成分，包括血管紧张素原；促炎细胞因子（肿瘤坏死因子- α 、白细胞介素-6）；脂肪因子（瘦素、抵抗素、脂联素减少）；以及游离脂肪酸。

过量的瘦素会减少一氧化氮（NO，一种重要的血管舒张剂）的生成，而RAAS的激活会增加血管紧张素II（一种强效血管收缩剂）的水平。这会破坏血管舒张，加剧炎症，并引发动脉粥样硬化。脂肪因子失衡和氧化应激会加剧胰岛素抵抗、高血压和血脂异常。这会形成恶性循环：肥胖会损伤内皮，而内皮功能障碍又会加速肥胖和血管疾病的进展。长期来看，这会增加冠心病、中风和慢性心力衰竭的风险，因此需要采取综合方法来纠正肥胖和内皮功能障碍。

关键词：内皮功能障碍，醛固酮，胰岛素抵抗，肥胖，冠心病，中风。

Abstract.. *The rising prevalence of obesity worldwide is accompanied by an increase in mortality from cardiovascular diseases. The key mechanism for their development is endothelial dysfunction caused by chronic low-grade inflammation and oxidative stress. In obesity, hypertrophied adipose tissue (especially*

visceral) becomes an active endocrine organ, secreting components of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), including angiotensinogen; pro-inflammatory cytokines (tumor necrosis factor- α , interleukin 6); adipokines (leptin, resistin, decreased adiponectin); and free fatty acids.

Excess leptin reduces the production of nitric oxide (NO), a key vasodilator, and activation of the RAAS increases levels of angiotensin II, a potent vasoconstrictor. This disrupts vascular relaxation, increases inflammation, and triggers atherosclerosis. Adipokine imbalance and oxidative stress exacerbate insulin resistance, hypertension, and dyslipidemia. This creates a vicious cycle: obesity damages the endothelium, and endothelial dysfunction accelerates the progression of obesity and vascular disease. Over the long term, this increases the risk of coronary heart disease, stroke, and chronic heart failure, requiring a comprehensive approach to correcting obesity and endothelial dysfunction.

Keywords: *endothelial dysfunction, aldosterone, insulin resistance, obesity, coronary heart disease, stroke.*

Introduction.

Along with the rising prevalence of obesity worldwide, mortality from cardiovascular disease is also increasing. Chronic low-grade inflammation associated with obesity disrupts vascular homeostasis and contributes to the development of endothelial dysfunction. Endothelial dysfunction, a disorder of the regulatory function of the vascular endothelium, is closely linked to obesity [1]. Adipose tissue is currently considered an active endocrine organ, producing numerous biologically active substances that exert systemic effects on the vascular wall. Hypertrophy and hyperplasia of adipose tissue in obesity lead to the active secretion of proinflammatory cytokines (tumor necrosis factor- α , interleukin-6), adipokines (leptin, resistin), and free fatty acids, which, when released into the systemic circulation, initiate chronic low-grade inflammation and oxidative stress—key mechanisms of endothelial cell damage.

Excess leptin in obesity contributes to the development of insulin resistance and directly inhibits the production of nitric oxide (NO), a key vasodilator synthesized by the endothelium, leading to impaired endothelium-dependent vasodilation [2].

The renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) is intricately intertwined with adipose tissue, which is capable of synthesizing RAAS components and modulating its activity.

Adipose tissue, particularly visceral adipose tissue, actively participates in RAAS activation. It expresses genes encoding all the major RAAS components, including angiotensinogen, angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE), angiotensin II receptors (AT1 and AT2), and renin. In obesity, hypertrophied adipocytes begin to secrete angiotensinogen, a precursor of angiotensin I, which, under

the influence of ACE, is converted to angiotensin II (AT II), a potent vasoconstrictor and proinflammatory mediator. This leads to an increase in its local concentration in adipose tissue and contributes to the development of chronic low-grade inflammation [3].

This also triggers a cascade of intracellular signaling pathways that increase the production of proinflammatory cytokines and suppress the synthesis of adiponectin, an adipokine with anti-inflammatory and insulin-sensitizing properties. Simultaneously, activation of the RAAS in adipose tissue stimulates the proliferation of preadipocytes and inhibits their differentiation, which disrupts normal adipose tissue metabolism and promotes the accumulation of ectopic fat in organs and muscles, exacerbating insulin resistance.

Furthermore, the adipokine imbalance (increased leptin and decreased adiponectin) triggers pathological reactions: signaling pathways are activated that increase the production of reactive oxygen species, which, when combined with NO, form a compound that damages the proteins and lipids of cell membranes. As a result, the bioavailability of NO decreases, the relaxation of vascular smooth muscle cells is impaired, vascular resistance increases, and the processes of leukocyte adhesion to the endothelium and their migration into the subendothelial space are activated, which is the initial stage of atherogenesis.

Comorbid conditions including obesity, hypertension, dyslipidemia, and hyperglycemia exacerbate endothelial dysfunction.

Thus, obesity creates a vicious cycle: excess body weight triggers chronic inflammation and metabolic disorders that damage the endothelium. Conversely, endothelial dysfunction exacerbates insulin resistance, hypertension, and atherogenesis, contributing to the further progression of obesity and associated vascular diseases. Over the long term, this increases the risk of coronary heart disease, stroke, chronic heart failure, and other complications, highlighting the need for a comprehensive approach to correcting obesity and associated endothelial dysfunction.

Materials and Methods.

The study was conducted as part of research project No. FGMF-2025–0003. The study protocol was approved by the Local Ethics Committee of Federal state budgetary scientific institution Federal research centre of nutrition, biotechnology and food safety (Protocol No 1. Dated 23.01.26). All participants were informed about the objectives and methodology of the study and signed voluntary informed consent for participation and publication of the obtained data. The study, conducted at the Clinic, included 80 patients divided into two groups. Group 1 included patients with class I–II obesity (BMI less than 40 kg/m²), and Group 2 included patients with class III obesity (BMI greater than 40 kg/m²).

Inclusion criteria: BMI greater than 30 kg/m², no history of vascular events.

Exclusion criteria: diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease of any origin.

Results

The collection of anamnesis, complaints, and examination of patients were carried out according to standard methods. Arterial hypertension of grades 1–3 was detected in 84% of patients in group 1 and 87% of patients in group 2 with satisfactory drug correction. A study of RAAS components was conducted: plasma renin concentration, plasma angiotensin II concentration, plasma aldosterone concentration. The obtained data were processed using methods of systemic statistical analysis.

Determination of the concentration of aldosterone in the blood plasma of patients revealed hyperaldosteronism in the majority of them. A direct relationship was noted between the concentration of aldosterone in the blood plasma and the degree of obesity. Moreover, the aldosterone level in group 2 exceeded the similar indicator in group 1 by more than 20% and by 25% of the norm (at $p < 0.05$): group 1–58.9 [54.9; 73.8] pg/ml, group 2–79.5 [64.5; 90.1] pg/ml.

The concentration of renin in the blood plasma in both groups was within the normal range: in group 1–23.2 [10.9; 51.8] pg/ml, in group 2–22.4 [11.2; 39.8] pg/ml. There were no statistically significant differences between the groups ($p > 0.05$). The concentration of angiotensin II in group 1 was 17.95 [1.58; 18.53] pg/ml, in group 2–18.54 [18.25; 18.83] pg/ml. There were also no statistically significant differences between the groups ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusions

The data obtained as a result of the work show a “dose-dependent” relationship between the concentration of aldosterone in the blood plasma and obesity – the concentration of aldosterone increases with increasing degree of obesity. Excessive aldosterone activity leads to peripheral edema and stagnation in the pulmonary circulation.

High ratios of aldosterone to renin and aldosterone to angiotensin-II make it highly likely that angiotensin-independent pathways of activation of aldosterone synthesis by the adrenal glands are important. Stimulators of aldosterone synthesis can be norepinephrine, cortisol, ACTH, vasopressin, histamine, serotonin, dopamine, prostaglandins, endothelin, hyperkalemia and other factors.

In obese patients, many of the listed factors increase exponentially, which indicates the need for additional research in the field of neurohormonal interactions and the cause-and-effect mechanisms of the development of secondary hyperaldosteronemia in obese patients.

Thus, the data obtained from the study become especially relevant in connection with the so-called “new biology” of aldosterone. According to it, aldosterone is given great importance as a factor in the development of pathological conditions and effects: an increased risk of diabetes mellitus and a significant increase in the risk of stroke (risk ratio 2.58) [4]; endothelial dysfunction; pathological fibrosis leading to myocardial remodeling; disturbance of carbohydrate and lipid metabolism; inflammation and tissue damage; hypercoagulability; proarrhythmogenic effect.

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寻求体外受精服务的患者的医疗和社会特征
**MEDICAL AND SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WHO
SEEK IN VITRO FERTILIZATION SERVICES**

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摘要：数据显示，体外受精（IVF）治疗结果受多种因素共同影响。30岁以下女性的妊娠率最高；40岁以后，治疗效果下降，并发症发生率增加。

不孕症的病因也会影响预后。输卵管-腹膜因素导致的不孕症成功率较高，而子宫内膜异位症和子宫腺肌症导致的不孕症则妊娠率较低。合并症，如子宫肌瘤、子宫瘢痕、肥胖和卵巢储备功能下降，进一步限制了治疗效果。

关键词：体外受精，不孕症，体外受精预后因素

Abstract. *The data show that IVF program outcomes are influenced by multiple factors simultaneously. The highest pregnancy rates have been observed in women younger than 30 years; After the age of 40, effectiveness declined, while the frequency of complicated outcomes increased.*

The causes of infertility also influenced the prognosis. In cases of the tubal-peritoneal factor, chances of success were higher, whereas with endometriosis and adenomyosis, pregnancy was rare. Comorbid conditions – myoma, uterine scar, obesity, and decreased ovarian reserve – further limited treatment effectiveness.

Keywords: *IVF, infertility, prognostic factors of IVF outcome*

Relevance

According to the 2023 WHO report, approximately 17.5% of the global adult population suffers from infertility, effectively every sixth individual. Infertility statistics in the Russian Federation are similarly discouraging. Data from the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation indicate that the prevalence of female infertility increased by one third over the ten-year period from 2011 to 2021, while

male infertility nearly doubled. In 2023, the number of women affected by infertility in Russia reached 254,800. people, among whom 8 thousand were newly diagnosed [1–3]. At the same time, infertility statistics vary significantly across various regions of the country.

The aim of the study was to examine the medical and social characteristics of female patients seeking IVF services in the Chechen Republic of Russia.

Materials and Methods

The study included female patients treated at the assisted reproductive technologies clinic ‘Generation NEXT’ in the city of In Grozny, over the course of three years of the center’s operation. During the specified period, 623 cycles of extracorporeal fertilization, 374 frozen embryo transfers, and 138 fresh embryo transfers were carried out. Additionally, 5 cycles were conducted as part of the delayed maternity program. Therefore, the total number of treatment cycles exceeded 1100, enabling an objective evaluation of both the structure of the protocols used and their effectiveness.

Despite the substantial volume of treatment cycles performed over three years, a separate cohort was selected for detailed analysis of the patients’ social and clinical characteristics. This methodology allowed focusing not on the statistics of all procedures, but on the characteristics of individual women who underwent treatment at the clinic. Subsequent analysis will be based on data from 101 patients, providing an opportunity to examine the age structure, reproductive history, and clinical factors influencing the effectiveness of ART.

The collected data were processed using classical methods of variational statistics.

Results. Age is one of the key factors determining the effectiveness of assisted reproductive technology programs. The average age of female patients in the studied sample was 34.3 ± 5.8 years (range 21 to 47 years), with a median age of 35 years.

The majority of women fell within the 30–39 year age group ($n=55$; 54.5%), which corresponds to the most reproductively significant period. There were 22 patients under 30 years of age (21.8%) and 24 women over 40 years old (23.7%). The sample was biased toward the average reproductive age, which is consistent with the general age distribution of patients seeking ART services.

The analysis of treatment outcomes confirmed the significance of age as a prognostic factor. In the subgroup under 30 years of age, clinical pregnancy was achieved in 7 out of 22 women (31.8%), representing the highest rate across all age groups. Negative outcomes accounted for 45.5%, while treatment in some patients was limited to preparation for the cryopreservation protocol.

In the 30–39 years cohort, a positive outcome was achieved in 13 out of 55 patients (23.6%). Although the success rate was lower than in the younger group, this age category demonstrated the highest absolute number of clinical pregnancies. Complicated outcomes were documented – one ectopic pregnancy and one missed abortion.

In the group aged 40 years and older, clinical pregnancy was achieved in 6 out of 24 women (25%). Although this indicator is formally similar to that in the 30–39 year age group, the proportion of complicated and negative outcomes was highest here: biochemical pregnancies and a high failure rate (62.5%) were recorded.

In summary, the highest chances of pregnancy were observed in women under 30 years of age, moderate chances in those aged 30–39, whereas in patients over 40 years, the effectiveness of ART programs declined and was accompanied by an increase in complicated outcomes.

Table 3.2 presents detailed outcomes by age categories.

Table 3.2 – Outcomes by age categories

Age group	Total patients	Pregnancy	No pregnancy	Bio-chemical	Specific outcomes	Preparation for cryo-preservation	No data
<30 years	22	7 (31.8%)	10 (45.5%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (18.2%)	1 (4.5%)
30–39 years	55	13 (23.6%)	34 (61.8%)	2 (3.6%)	1 (1.8%)	2 (3.6%)	3 (5.5%)
40+ years	24	6 (25.0%)	15 (62.5%)	2 (8.3%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (4.2%)
Total	101	26 (25.7%)	59 (58.4%)	4 (4.0%)	1 (1.0%)	6 (5.9%)	5 (5.0%)

As shown in Table 3.2, the data demonstrate the key role of age as a prognostic factor for IVF outcomes. The highest chances of success are recorded in women under 30 years of age, moderate rates in the 30–39 age group, whereas after 40 years, the probability of conception and favorable pregnancy progression significantly decreases, which should be taken into account when planning treatment strategies.

Analysis of residence distribution revealed that the majority of patients were residents of the city of Grozny (approximately 27 cases).

Analysis of marital status data indicated that most women were married. Eighty-four patients reported a history of marital relationships, with only 8 patients in unregistered marriages.

Regarding the presence of children in medical history, 23 women had given birth or had at least one child, allowing them to be classified as having secondary infertility. Among the remaining 78 patients, no previous pregnancies or births were reported, corresponding to primary infertility.

Thus, in the studied sample, women with primary infertility predominated, while secondary infertility was observed in approximately one in every four patients.

Assessment of the number of in vitro fertilization attempts revealed a mean of 2.2 ± 2.6 , with a median of 1 attempt (interquartile range: 1–2). Patients most frequently underwent one (34 cases) or two (17 cases) IVF attempts. More than three attempts were less common, with the highest recorded number reaching 19.

Figure 3.1 shows the distribution of patients according to the number of IVF attempts performed.

Figure 3.1 – Number of IVF attempts in medical history

The chart clearly shows that the majority of patients underwent a limited number of treatment cycles, while multiple IVF attempts were rare and distinctly stood out from the overall distribution.

Analysis of patients' complaints showed that the predominant symptom was the absence of pregnancy over varying periods, reported by more than one-third of the women. In certain cases, patients indicated a duration of infertility ranging from 2 to 8 years or more within their complaints. A portion of women presented specifically for frozen embryo transfer or cryopreservation protocol procedures, reflecting the staged approach to treatment.

Reviewing medical histories revealed that among specific gynecological conditions, endometriosis was the most frequent (12 cases), followed by uterine scarring (7 cases), uterine myoma (5 cases), and less commonly adenomyosis (3 cases), ovarian cysts (2 cases), and adhesions (2 cases). These conditions can exert a significant influence on reproductive function and infertility treatment outcomes.

Information on previous somatic diseases included viral hepatitis (4 cases), as well as infectious diseases contracted during childhood (chickenpox, rubella,

mumps). Isolated cases of autoimmune, endocrine, and neurological diseases, as well as congenital developmental anomalies, were reported.

Figure 3.2 shows the distribution of patients according to past and concurrent diseases. The data reflect the most frequently occurring nosologies in the studied sample.

Figure 3.2 – Associated diseases

The most common conditions among patients were infectious diseases contracted in childhood, as well as viral hepatitis. Chronic inflammatory processes and endocrine pathologies were noted less frequently. Overall, concomitant somatic diseases had a limited distribution and were not pronounced.

Previous surgical interventions also varied. Some women had a history of hysteroscopies and polypectomies, while others underwent laparoscopies for endometriosis, ovarian cysts, or adhesions. Cases of cesarean sections were documented, along with isolated reports of interventions involving the heart, blood vessels, and ocular organs. This underscores the diversity of surgical histories that may affect reproductive health.

Figure 3.3 presents surgical interventions in the medical histories of the women.

Surgical interventions history

Figure 3.3 – Past surgical interventions

Analysis of allergy history showed that it was unremarkable in most women (42 cases). Drug allergies were rare and occurred mainly to antibiotics (penicillin, ceftriaxone).

Heredity was also unremarkable in most cases. A portion of patients had cardiovascular diseases and diabetes mellitus among their relatives, with oncological pathology observed less frequently.

Particular attention was paid to the presence of harmful habits. The vast majority of women reported no smoking or alcohol use. Smoking was recorded in only a single case, allowing this factor to be considered negligible for the studied sample.

Conclusions. The results indicate that the outcomes of IVF programs are influenced simultaneously by multiple factors. The highest pregnancy rates have been observed in women younger than 30 years; After the age of 40, effectiveness declined, while the frequency of complicated outcomes increased.

The causes of infertility also influenced the prognosis. In cases of the tubal-peritoneal factor, chances of success were higher, whereas with endometriosis and adenomyosis, pregnancy was rare. Comorbid conditions – myoma, uterine scar, obesity, and decreased ovarian reserve – further limited treatment effectiveness.

Overall, the clinical pregnancy rate in the studied sample was approximately one quarter of cases, which is comparable to data from leading centers. The most favorable outcomes were observed in women of younger age groups in the absence of severe gynecological pathology.

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腰骶椎疾病的医学和社会意义
**MEDICAL AND SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF DISEASES OF THE
LUMBOSACRAL SPINE**

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摘要：本文对大量文献资料进行了书目语义分析，作者得出结论：腰骶椎疾病的医学和社会意义在于其高发病率、高复发率、暂时性和永久性残疾、生活质量下降、治疗费用高昂以及需要结构化的康复路径等因素的综合作用。

关键词：腰骶椎疾病，医学和社会意义，神经根病

Abstract. *A bibliosemantic analysis of extensive literary sources was conducted, through which the authors conclude that the medical and social significance of this group of diseases is related to a combination of high prevalence, recurrence, temporary and permanent disability, reduced quality of life, treatment costs, and the necessity for structured rehabilitation pathways.*

Keywords: *lumbosacral spine region diseases, medical and social significance, radiculopathies*

Relevance

Global estimates of the burden of disease demonstrate that low back pain is not only a frequent symptom but also one of the leading causes of health loss associated with activity limitation. In the Global Burden of Disease 2010 study, it ranked first among 291 conditions in terms of years lived with disability and sixth in total burden as measured by DALYs [1]. Later GBD 2017 evaluations revealed that the absolute number of individuals experiencing low back pain rose from 377.5 million in 1990 to 577.0 million in 2017, despite a moderate decrease in age-standardized rates [2]. According to GBD 2021 data, in 2020, low back pain was observed in 619 million people, with the number of such patients projected to increase to 843 million by 2050 [3]. The increase in the absolute number of patients is associated not only with medical factors but also with demographic changes, population aging, and a growth in the number of individuals living with chronic functional limitations.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the medical and social significance of diseases of the lumbosacral spine region.

Materials and methods

A bibliosemantic analysis of literary sources was conducted using the databases Scopus, Web of Science, MedLine, The Cochrane Library, EMBASE, Global Health, CyberLeninka, RSCI, and eLibrary.ru. Based on the keywords lumbosacral spine region diseases, radiculopathy, and the medical and social burden of lumbosacral spine region diseases, 255 publications were selected, comprising 200 international and 55 Russian sources. This paper presents a detailed analysis of 17 of them.

Results

Diseases of the lumbosacral spine region rank among the most common causes of pain, limitations in daily activity, and medical consultations. Pain in the lower back plays a central role in the structure of this pathology. Its prevalence is difficult to assess with a single indicator, as the results depend on the definition of pain, the observation period, the age of examined individuals, and the method of data collection. In a systematic review of population-based studies from different regions worldwide, the average point prevalence estimate of low back pain was 11.9%. The prevalence of low back pain over the course of one month was 23.2%, indicating that nearly one in four adults reported experiencing such pain during the previous four weeks [4]. Higher prevalence rates were noted among women and persons of middle and older age.

The magnitude of the problem is also confirmed by national data. In a nationwide epidemiological study of chronic pain in adults, chronic pain lasting more than three months was reported by 43% of respondents, with low back pain identified as the most frequent site of chronic pain. It was reported by 37% of respondents. In the context of chronic pain, 45% of respondents reported being unable to perform certain physical activities, and 38% reported reduced work capacity [5].

Official medical statistics reflect not the true prevalence of pain but the recorded incidence, that is, cases captured within the healthcare system. According to statistical data from the Central Research Institute of Organization and Informatization of Healthcare under the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, in 2023, 4,561,625 cases of diseases of the musculoskeletal system and connective tissue with a diagnosis made for the first time in life were registered, corresponding to 3,114.9 cases per 100,000 population. In the group of deforming dorsopathies, 1,156,965 cases were recorded, corresponding to 790.0 per 100,000 population [6]. The national context is appropriately examined through the combination of two data sources: population-based studies of chronic pain and official registries of musculoskeletal diseases. The demand on specialized rehabilitation services is influenced not only by the number of patient visits but also by the high prevalence of pain, recurrent episodes, limitations in physical activity, and decreased work capacity.

The prevalence of pain in the lumbosacral region should be considered separately from the rate of medical consultation, as these indicators reflect different aspects of the problem. According to population data, a significant proportion of adults experience lower back pain over a relatively short observation period; however, not all patients seek medical care [7]. For this reason, referrals to specialized centers are influenced not only by the overall disease frequency but also by pain severity, symptom duration, recurrence of episodes, activity limitations, and dissatisfaction with previous treatment outcomes.

The recurrent nature of pain holds substantial medical and social significance. A prospective follow-up of patients in general medical practice demonstrated that discontinuation of consultations does not always indicate complete recovery – some patients cease seeking medical advice yet continue to experience pain and associated functional limitations throughout the subsequent year [8]. Long-term follow-up within the North Carolina Back Pain Project further confirmed that following an acute episode, pain may recur and again prompt patients to seek medical care [9]. When assessing the prevalence of diseases of the lumbosacral spine region, it is important to take into account not only primary consultations but also recurrent episodes, which increase the burden on outpatient care and rehabilitation services.

The importance of this group of pathologies is determined not only by the frequency of pain but also by its impact on the patient's functional independence. Even in the absence of severe structural spinal damage, pain syndrome can limit walking, bending, lifting weights, prolonged sitting, sleep, work activity, and participation in family life. Therefore, evaluation based solely on morphological changes identified through radiological diagnostics does not accurately reflect the actual severity of the condition. Contemporary understanding of low back pain entails consideration of anatomical, functional, psychological, and social factors [10].

Diseases of the lumbosacral spine region impose a sustained burden on the healthcare system due to recurrent medical consultations, episodes of temporary disability, prolonged medication use, radiological examinations, referrals to multiple specialists, and the demand for rehabilitation services. At the same time, high costs of care do not always result in better functional outcomes. It is emphasized that the overuse of low-evidence methods, unjustified imaging, and passive treatment modalities can increase patient dependence on the healthcare system and fail to reduce the risk of pain chronification [11].

The economic consequences of diseases of the lumbosacral spine region are associated not only with direct medical costs but also with work disability. In the study by W. F. Stewart et al. Back pain was one of the common causes of working time loss among employed adults, with a significant portion of these losses attributable not to absence from the workplace, but to reduced labor productivity while formally present at work [12]. This circumstance indicates that improvement in the patient's condition should be evaluated not only by pain reduction but also by the restoration of the capacity to perform professional and everyday tasks.

Rising expenditures on care for patients with back and neck pain are not always accompanied by a commensurate improvement in health outcomes. An analysis of US national data from 1997 to 2005 demonstrated an increase in medical care costs associated with spinal diseases, underscoring the need for more rational organization and management of such patients [13]. Significant factors for chronic pain include initial pain intensity, severity of disability, prior episodes of work disability, and expectation of a poor prognosis, as these factors are linked to slower recovery [14].

A distinctive feature of diseases in the lumbosacral spine region is that the clinical course often does not correspond to the severity of degenerative changes. Protrusions, intervertebral disc degeneration, spondyloarthritis, and other findings may be observed in individuals without pain. Therefore, simple correlation of complaints with magnetic resonance imaging data does not always allow for identification of the symptom source and selection of a rational rehabilitation strategy [10].

Rehabilitation for diseases of the lumbosacral spine region should focus not only on pain reduction. Its objectives are restoring movement, enhancing tolerance to everyday and professional activities, correcting motor control, reducing kinesiophobia, educating the patient on safe physical activity, and preventing recurrent episodes [15].

The medical and social significance of diseases of the lumbosacral spine region is determined not only by the frequency of pain but also by its prolonged effects on daily functioning, work capacity, and the increased need for repeated medical interventions. In the literature, back pain is regarded as one of the frequent causes for medical consultation and temporary disability, and in chronic cases, it is often accompanied by a decrease in quality of life, limitations in motor activity, anxiety responses, and persistent erroneous patient beliefs about the disease [16]. Therefore,

the severity of the problem cannot be evaluated solely on the basis of radiological diagnostic data or the mere presence of an established diagnosis. For the medical rehabilitation system, greater importance is placed on the intensity of pain, the degree of functional limitations, frequency of episode recurrence, duration of disability, and the patient's willingness to restore activity.

Of practical significance is the fact that patients with dorsopathies often receive fragmented treatment: repeated courses of pharmacotherapy, physiotherapeutic procedures, massage, or other passive methods without adequate patient education, kinesiotherapy, and monitoring of functional outcomes. Such a management approach may provide temporary pain relief but does not always restore motor function and does not reduce the risk of recurrent consultations [16]. Consequently, diseases of the lumbosacral spine region should be addressed not only as a clinical problem but also as an organizational issue. Early assessment of functional limitations, identification of factors leading to chronification, determination of indications for rehabilitation, selection of an active program, and monitoring of outcomes related to pain, movement, work activity, and quality of life are essential [17].

Conclusions

Thus, the medical and social significance of this group of diseases is linked to a combination of high prevalence, relapsing course, temporary and persistent disability, decreased quality of life, treatment costs, and the need for organized rehabilitation pathways.

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SMART研讨会作为一种现代教育技术，可用于改善银屑病急性发作的预防和远程患者管理。

SMART SEMINAR AS A MODERN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY FOR IMPROVING THE PREVENTION OF PSORIASIS EXACERBATIONS AND REMOTE PATIENT MANAGEMENT

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摘要。引言。银屑病是一种慢性免疫介导的炎症性皮肤病，其特征是反复发作、生活质量下降以及需要长期随访。现代皮肤病学越来越多地将人工智能（AI）、远程皮肤病学和数字化监测技术应用于临床，旨在改善疾病控制、提高治疗依从性并提升专科护理的可及性。同时，有效实施数字化技术需要提升医疗专业人员的数字化能力并引入现代化的教育方法。

材料与方法。SMART研讨会的概念是基于对2020年至2025年间PubMed、Web of Science、Scopus和IEEE Xplore收录的国际文献的分析性回顾而提出的。分析重点关注基于人工智能的图像评估、数字化PASI评估、远程皮肤病学、远程患者监测、治疗反应预测以及银屑病发作的预防。研究采用了内容分析、比较分析、组织建模和结构设计等方法。

结果。我们开发了一种名为“银屑病患者数字化监测与风险导向管理智能研讨会”的实践导向型教育模式。该模式整合了远程皮肤病学、人工

智能辅助图像分析、远程照片监测、数字化PASI评估、跨学科互动和案例式学习。研讨会结构包含多个模块，分别侧重于病情加重预防、数字化监测、人工智能分析、远程患者管理、PASI评估和远程医疗转诊。该模式旨在提升医疗专业人员的数字化能力，并增强其在实际医疗中应用数字化皮肤病学技术的准备。参与患者管理的医护人员，包括皮肤科医生、基层医疗专家、全科医生、护士、住院医师等，均可参与该教育模式。

结论：智能研讨会是一种极具前景的组织和教育技术，有助于推动持续性数字化医学教育的发展，提升医疗队伍的准备水平，加强远程银屑病管理，并促进远程皮肤病学技术在医疗系统中的更广泛应用。

关键词：银屑病、SMART研讨会、人工智能、远程皮肤病学、数字皮肤病学、远程监测、PASI、医学教育、数字能力。

Abstract. *Introduction.* Psoriasis is a chronic immune-mediated inflammatory skin disease characterized by recurrent exacerbations, decreased quality of life, and the need for long-term follow-up. Modern dermatology increasingly incorporates artificial intelligence (AI), tele dermatology, and digital monitoring technologies aimed at improving disease control, treatment adherence, and accessibility of specialized care. At the same time, effective implementation of digital technologies requires the development of healthcare professionals' digital competencies and the introduction of contemporary educational approaches.

Materials and Methods. *The SMART seminar concept was developed based on an analytical review of international publications indexed in PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and IEEE Xplore between 2020 and 2025. The analysis focused on AI-based image assessment, digital PASI evaluation, tele dermatology, remote patient monitoring, prediction of treatment response, and prevention of psoriasis exacerbations. Content analysis, comparative analysis, organizational modeling, and structural design methods were applied.*

Results. *A practice-oriented educational model entitled "SMART Seminar on Digital Monitoring and Risk-Oriented Management of Patients with Psoriasis" was developed. The proposed format integrates tele dermatology, AI-supported image analysis, remote photo monitoring, digital PASI assessment, interdisciplinary interaction, and case-based learning. The seminar structure includes modules devoted to exacerbation prevention, digital monitoring, AI analysis, remote patient management, PASI assessment, and telemedicine routing. The proposed model is aimed at improving digital competencies of healthcare professionals and enhancing readiness for the implementation of digital dermatology technologies in practical healthcare. The educational format may also involve dermatologists, primary healthcare specialists, general practitioners, nurses, residents, and other healthcare professionals participating in patient management.*

Conclusion. *SMART seminars may be considered a promising organizational and educational technology contributing to the development of continuous digital*

medical education, improvement of healthcare workforce readiness, enhancement of remote psoriasis management, and wider implementation of teledermatology technologies in healthcare systems.

Keywords: *psoriasis, SMART seminar, artificial intelligence, teledermatology, digital dermatology, remote monitoring, PASI, medical education, digital competencies.*

Introduction. Psoriasis is a chronic immune-mediated inflammatory skin disease characterized by recurrent exacerbations, a prolonged clinical course, impaired quality of life, and the need for continuous long-term follow-up. The multifactorial nature of psoriasis, variability in clinical manifestations, and the necessity for individualized therapeutic approaches determine the growing importance of modern technologies aimed at optimizing patient management and preventing disease progression.

In recent years, significant attention has been devoted to the implementation of digital technologies in dermatological practice, including artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), telemedicine, and remote patient monitoring systems. These technologies are increasingly considered promising tools for improving diagnostic accuracy, optimizing clinical decision-making, enhancing treatment adherence, and ensuring continuity of care for patients with chronic dermatoses.

Modern studies demonstrate that AI-based systems are capable of performing automated image analysis, assessing the severity and extent of psoriatic lesions, calculating PASI scores, and supporting clinical interpretation during remote consultations. Digital dermatology technologies additionally contribute to the standardization of visual assessment, reduction of subjective interpretation, and improvement of reproducibility in clinical evaluation.

The rapid development of teledermatology has substantially expanded opportunities for remote patient management, particularly in regions with limited access to dermatologists and specialized medical services. The use of digital communication platforms, photo monitoring technologies, and telemedicine consultations enables dynamic follow-up of patients, early identification of signs of disease progression, and timely correction of therapy.

At the same time, international experience indicates that the successful implementation of digital technologies in healthcare requires adequate training of healthcare professionals, development of digital competencies, and adaptation of educational models to contemporary clinical practice. The integration of AI-based technologies, telemedicine, and digital monitoring into educational programs may therefore be considered an important direction for improving continuous professional education in dermatology.

In this context, the development of practice-oriented educational technologies focused on digital dermatology and remote patient support appears highly relevant.

Objective. To scientifically substantiate and develop the concept of a SMART seminar aimed at improving the prevention of psoriasis exacerbations, developing digital competencies among healthcare professionals, and implementing technologies for remote patient management using AI-based image analysis and teledermatology.

Materials and Methods. The development of the SMART seminar concept was based on an analytical review of contemporary international scientific publications devoted to the use of artificial intelligence, machine learning, digital dermatology, and telemedicine technologies in the management of patients with psoriasis.

An analytical review of publications indexed in PubMed, Web of Science, Scopus, and IEEE Xplore between 2020 and 2025 was conducted. The analysis focused on the following areas:

- AI-based image analysis;
- digital PASI assessment;
- teledermatology;
- remote patient monitoring;
- prediction of therapeutic response;
- prevention of psoriasis exacerbations;
- clinical decision support systems.

The following methodological approaches were applied:

- content analysis;
- comparative analysis;
- systematization of scientific evidence;
- organizational modeling;
- structural design of educational technologies.

Additionally, contemporary concepts of patient-centered care, risk-oriented monitoring, and digital dermatology were analyzed.

Results and Discussion

Based on the conducted analysis, a modern educational model entitled “SMART Seminar on Digital Monitoring and Risk-Oriented Management of Patients with Psoriasis” was developed.

The proposed educational format is intended as a practice-oriented organizational and educational technology integrating:

- teledermatology;
- AI-based image analysis;
- remote photo monitoring;
- digital PASI assessment;

- interdisciplinary collaboration;
- case-based clinical learning;
- elements of personalized medicine.

The SMART seminar structure includes the following modules:

- psoriasis exacerbation prevention module;
- digital patient monitoring module;
- AI-based image analysis module;
- remote patient management module;
- PASI assessment module;
- interdisciplinary support module;
- telemedicine routing module.

According to contemporary international studies, the implementation of AI-based image analysis technologies in dermatological practice contributes to several important directions for improving psoriasis patient management.

First, automated analysis of skin lesions increases the objectivity of visual assessment, standardizes image interpretation, and improves reproducibility of diagnostic evaluation. Second, digital PASI assessment reduces subjectivity in determining disease severity and promotes greater consistency between specialists. Third, remote digital monitoring technologies facilitate continuous follow-up of patients, timely identification of clinical deterioration, and dynamic assessment of therapeutic effectiveness.

Moreover, AI-based systems contribute to more accurate assessment of lesion extent and inflammatory activity during tele dermatology consultations. Such technologies additionally support personalized approaches to therapy, improve prediction of treatment response, and optimize patient routing within healthcare systems.

Contemporary evidence also demonstrates that AI systems may achieve levels of diagnostic accuracy comparable to expert clinical assessment performed by dermatologists. In this regard, artificial intelligence is increasingly considered a promising tool for personalized medicine and risk-oriented monitoring of chronic inflammatory skin diseases.

The proposed SMART seminar model is focused on the development of practical competencies in digital dermatology, prevention of psoriasis exacerbations, and remote patient support. The educational format includes:

- interactive practice-oriented learning;
- analysis of clinical images and digital assessment of skin manifestations;
- training in remote consultation technologies;
- development of digital and telemedicine competencies;
- training in remote patient monitoring algorithms;
- implementation of risk-oriented approaches to exacerbation prevention.

An important feature of the proposed SMART seminar is the possibility of expanding the target audience beyond dermatologists alone. The educational format may additionally involve primary healthcare specialists, general practitioners, advanced practice nurses, residents, master's students, and other healthcare professionals participating in patient routing and long-term follow-up.

The relevance of this interdisciplinary approach is associated with the persistent shortage of dermatologists, unequal territorial accessibility of specialized care, and increasing demand for remote consultation technologies in the management of chronic skin diseases.

Under these conditions, SMART seminars may be considered an effective tool for improving healthcare workforce readiness for the implementation of teledermatology technologies, early identification of disease progression, and enhancement of continuity of medical care.

The proposed educational model additionally contributes to increasing healthcare professionals' awareness regarding risk factors for psoriasis exacerbations, strengthening interdisciplinary interaction, and expanding the use of remote monitoring technologies in routine clinical practice.

The organizational novelty of the proposed approach lies in the integration of educational technologies, digital dermatology, telemedicine, and AI support into a unified format of continuous professional education.

From a scientific and organizational perspective, the SMART seminar may be considered a modern educational platform integrating clinical training, digital competencies, AI-based support systems, and telemedicine technologies into a single educational environment.

It is expected that implementation of SMART seminars will improve the effectiveness of remote patient management, facilitate earlier identification of disease deterioration, enhance treatment adherence, and improve the timeliness of therapeutic correction.

Furthermore, implementation of digital educational technologies may contribute to reducing the risk of severe exacerbations, optimizing dynamic patient follow-up, and improving access to specialized dermatological care, particularly in settings characterized by workforce shortages and limited accessibility of dermatologists.

An additional advantage of SMART seminars is the possibility of establishing an interdisciplinary educational model involving dermatologists, primary healthcare specialists, general practitioners, nurses, residents, and other participants in patient management systems.

Overall, the proposed approach creates prerequisites for strengthening continuity between different levels of healthcare, improving healthcare professionals' awareness of exacerbation risk factors, and promoting wider implementation of teledermatology technologies in practical healthcare.

Thus, SMART seminars may be regarded as a promising organizational and educational technology aimed at developing continuous digital medical education, improving healthcare workforce capacity, and supporting the transition toward patient-centered models of remote management for patients with psoriasis.

Conclusions

Contemporary scientific evidence indicates that artificial intelligence technologies, digital monitoring, and tele dermatology represent important directions for improving psoriasis patient management by enhancing objectivity of disease severity assessment, supporting personalized therapeutic approaches, and expanding remote patient support technologies.

The developed SMART seminar model represents a modern practice-oriented format of continuous professional education integrating clinical training, AI-based image analysis, telemedicine technologies, and risk-oriented approaches to prevention of psoriasis exacerbations.

The proposed educational format is aimed at improving healthcare professionals' digital competencies, enhancing remote monitoring skills, and increasing readiness for implementation of digital dermatology technologies in practical healthcare.

An important advantage of the SMART seminar is the possibility of involving primary healthcare specialists, general practitioners, nurses, residents, and other healthcare professionals participating in patient routing and follow-up, which is particularly relevant under conditions of dermatologist workforce shortages.

The implementation of SMART seminars may be considered a promising direction for the development of continuous medical education, improvement of access to specialized care, strengthening of interdisciplinary continuity, and optimization of psoriasis exacerbation prevention strategies within the context of healthcare digitalization.

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不同国籍个体下颌磨牙特征的牙形学研究及其在预防牙科学中应用前景
**ODONTOGLYPHIC STUDIES OF THE CHARACTERISTICS
OF MANDIBULAR MOLARS IN INDIVIDUALS OF DIFFERENT
NATIONALITIES AND PROSPECTS FOR USING THE OBTAINED
DATA IN PREVENTIVE DENTISTRY**

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摘要：本文介绍了阿尔泰国立医科大学（AGMU）俄罗斯族和阿拉伯族学生下颌第一和第二恒磨牙咬合结构特征的牙形学研究结果。

通过临床检查和口内摄影，对颌面凹陷数量、沟槽模式（Y、+、X）和复杂形态进行了比较分析。研究发现，不同族裔之间存在显著差异：俄罗斯族学生第一恒磨牙以X型沟槽为主（50%），第二恒磨牙以+型沟槽为主（75%）；阿拉伯族学生第二恒磨牙更易出现X4、Y4等复杂类型（53%，而俄罗斯族学生为25%）。阿拉伯族学生第二恒磨牙全部为四齿状，且X型沟槽出现频率较高（33%），表明其颌面形态更为复杂，龋齿风险也更高。

在制定牙科疾病预防措施时，采用以民族为导向的方法十分必要。

结论认为，在多国联合牙科检查中引入牙纹筛查，并利用所得数据为咬合面龋齿的个性化预防提供依据，是可取的。

关键词：牙纹，下颌磨牙，凸起数量，种族差异，面部龋齿，预防牙科，以民族为导向的方法，口内摄影

Abstract. *The article presents the results of an odontoglyphic study of the features of the occlusion structure of the first and second permanent moles of the lower jaw in students of the Altai State Medical University (AGMU) of Russian and Arab nationalities.*

Comparative analysis of the number of bumps, pattern of grooves (Y, +, X) and complex morphology of the jawlike surface was carried out using clinical examination

and intra-oral photography. Statistically significant ethnic differences have been identified: Russians are dominated by X-patterns on the first plots (50%) and plus-patterns on the second (75%); Arabs are more likely to encounter complex types X4, Y4 on the second plots (53% vs. 25% for Russians). The Arab group is found to be characterized by 100% of four-buggy second moles and a high frequency of X patterns (33%), indicating a more complex relief and an increased cariesogenic risk.

The need for an ethnically oriented approach in planning preventive measures of dental diseases is justified.

It was concluded that it would be advisable to introduce odontoglyphic screening in the practice of dental examinations with a multinational contingent and use the data obtained for personalized prevention of cavities on occlusive surfaces.

Keywords: *odontoglyphics, lower jaw molars, number of bumps, ethnic differences, facial caries, preventive dentistry, ethno-oriented approach, intra-oral photography*

Introduction. The clinical aspect of evolutionary retraction features of dental structure has not long been a priority in dental studies, which focus on tooth decay and parodontal disease. However, the broadening of scientific horizons, the progress of science and the uniqueness of the oral environment as a functional system require a broader approach.

Prevention is key to maintaining dental health [1]. The study of occlusal surface anatomy is essential for developing methods to prevent and treat fisura [2]. The effectiveness of programs depends on taking into account regional and climate-geographical factors, as well as reductional changes in the maxillofacial system related to brain evolution, social conditions, and diet [3].

Statistically significant difference in occlusive surface relief of caries and incipient teeth has been established, so a detailed study of the morphology of jaw surfaces is important not only to combat tooth decay but also for correction of occlusive disorders and orthopedic treatment [4]. The susceptibility of fisurs to tooth decay is correlated with their odontoglyphic characteristics [5]. Precise repair of the bumps and their squabs is essential for functional rehabilitation of the maxillary system and proper distribution of chewing load [6].

Knowledge of individual and populational features of the dentition allows for early prevention and a personalized approach to treatment, as well as being relevant to anthropology and forensic medicine.

Thus, the study of reductionary changes in the maxillary system among representatives of different ethnic groups and climatic zones represents an urgent scientific and practical task for modern dentistry.

The aim of the study is to identify and analyze the odontoglyphic features of lower jaw molars in people of different nationalities to identify potential links

between these features and the risk of developing dental diseases, with a view to developing scientifically justified preventive measures.

The object of research are students of the Altai State Medical University, 18–25 years old Russian and Arab nationalities with intricate lower figures. Studied the first and second molars (teeth 3.6, 4.6, 3.7, 4.7 according to FDI); the third molars are excluded due to reductive volatility. Distribution by self-identification: Russians – 44% (Europeans, natives of the Altai Territory), Arabs – 56% (from the Levant and North Africa).

Data collection methods:

1. Clinical examination – dental sounder and intraoral mirror, air desiccation to confirm the dentition 3.6, 4.6, 3.7, 4.7.

2. Photography – a smartphone camera with the macro through an intra-ocular mirror mounted perpendicularly to the chewing surface. For each tooth – at least 3 images for the subsequent most informative choice.

3. Morphometry and processing – analysis of images in Adobe Photoshop (estimation of number of bumps, pattern of grooves, complex morphology).

Conclusion. Based on the conducted clinical study, statistically significant differences of odontoglyphic traits in Russian and Arab students of AGMU were revealed. In the group of Russian students, we found X-patterns in 50% of the first molars, +-patterns – 38%, and Y-patterns only in 12%. In the group of students of Arab nationality, the distribution of patterns is more even: X-pattern occurs in 33%, +-pattern – 42% and Y-pattern in 25% of the first molars. Ethno-specific features have been identified: in Russians, the six-point form of the first molars is present – 12% and there is no four-point form; in Arabs, on the contrary, there is a four-point form in 17% of the first molars and there is no six-point form. The classical five-bugorkan form is most common among all nationalities: 88% of the first Russians and 83% of the Arabs. The second molars in 100% of Arab cases are four bugoroves, and in 91% of Russian cases are second moles. The latter also had 9% of second moles with five buggers.

It has been established that the most common complex relief in Russians is the morphoviruses +5, X5 (five-point molars with a pattern plus “+” and x “X”) on the first molars (74% of all cases); among Arabs – X5, Y5, +5 (patterns x “X”, x-point “Y” and + “+”, totaling 83% of the first five-point molars), and X4, Y4 (The X “X” pattern and the Y “Greek” on the second four-point mound at 53%), at that time the Russians had 25%. The predominant morphology among Russian students (67% of second-rate moths) is +4 (pattern plus “+”, 4 buggy), as well as among foreigners (47% of second moths). The obtained data support the need for a differentiated approach to assess the risk of caries and to insulate the fisur according to the patient’s ethnicity. Therefore, it is important to introduce odontoglyphic screening into the practice of external examinations in universities with a multinational contingent and

in dental clinics for early identification of risk groups; It is necessary to use the data obtained in the educational process at the departments of pediatric dentistry and therapeutic dentistry to prepare students to work with patients from different ethnic groups.

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阻塞性睡眠呼吸暂停综合征作为心肌梗死和动脉高血压的危险因素：病例报告

**OBSTRUCTIVE SLEEP APNEA SYNDROME AS A RISK
FACTOR FOR MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AND ARTERIAL
HYPERTENSION: A CASE REPORT**

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摘要：阻塞性睡眠呼吸暂停综合征（OSAS）是一种常见但诊断不足的疾病，与心血管疾病发病率和死亡率的增加相关。我们报告了一例61岁女性患者，她患有III级肥胖，因非ST段抬高型心肌梗死（NSTEMI）和心力衰竭入院。冠状动脉造影显示严重的多支冠状动脉病变，需要进行经皮冠状动脉介入治疗（PCI）并取得成功。该患者有打鼾、白天嗜睡和目击呼吸暂停发作史，多导睡眠图证实其患有重度OSAS，呼吸暂停低通气指数（AHI）为54.8次/小时，并伴有严重的夜间低氧血症（最低SpO₂为57%）。其他检查显示血脂异常、糖代谢异常和左心室收缩功能障碍。治疗方案包括指南指导的药物治疗、冠状动脉血运重建和持续气道正压通气（CPAP）治疗，最终患者临床症状改善，心血管症状减轻。本病例凸显了阻塞性睡眠呼吸暂停综合征（OSAS）作为急性冠状动脉事件的独立且潜在可控危险因素的重要性，并强调了早期诊断和治疗的重要性。

关键词：阻塞性睡眠呼吸暂停综合征，心肌梗死，心血管疾病，肥胖，CPAP治疗，多导睡眠图。

Abstract. Obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome (OSAS) is a common and underdiagnosed disorder associated with increased cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. We present the case of a 61-year-old woman with grade III obesity admitted with non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) and heart failure. Coronary angiography revealed severe multivessel coronary artery disease

requiring successful percutaneous coronary intervention. The patient had a history of snoring, excessive daytime sleepiness, and witnessed apnoeic episodes, while polysomnography confirmed severe OSAS with an apnea-hypopnea index of 54.8 events/hour and profound nocturnal hypoxaemia (minimum SpO₂ 57%). Additional investigations showed dyslipidaemia, impaired glucose metabolism, and left ventricular systolic dysfunction. Treatment included guideline-directed medical therapy, coronary revascularization, and continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) therapy, resulting in clinical improvement and reduced cardiovascular symptoms. This case highlights OSAS as an independent and potentially modifiable risk factor for acute coronary events and emphasizes the importance of its early diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: *obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome, myocardial infarction, cardiovascular disease, obesity, CPAP therapy, polysomnography.*

Introduction

Obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome (OSAS) represents an increasingly prevalent global health problem, affecting approximately one billion individuals. It is recognized as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease and is associated with the development of obesity, hypertension, cardiac arrhythmias, coronary artery disease, and heart failure. The recurrent episodes of intermittent hypoxia observed in obstructive sleep apnoea play a pivotal role in the development of its cardiovascular diseases. An obstructive respiratory event index of ≥ 15 events per hour is considered sufficient for diagnosis, even in individuals who do not exhibit related symptoms or comorbidities. Studies have demonstrated a linear association between the apnoea-hypopnoea index (AHI) and increases in blood pressure, independent of potential confounding factors. Beyond vascular remodeling, **obstructive sleep apnea** (OSA) is associated with the early onset of atherosclerotic changes in the arterial wall. Despite successful reperfusion after acute myocardial infarction, patients with OSA exhibit more severe coronary artery disease, prolonged myocardial ischaemia, and greater ventricular dysfunction than those without OSA [1]. Adequate CPAP therapy remains the gold-standard treatment for OSA and is associated with lower cardiovascular morbidity. The condition is defined by episodic narrowing or collapse of the upper respiratory tract during sleep, causing reduced ventilation or repeated apnoeic events. Recurrent apnoea and hypopnoea in OSA lead to intermittent hypoxia and systemic dysfunction, increasing the risk of cardiovascular diseases [2]. The sleep-wake cycle regulates cardiovascular function, but sleep apnoea disrupts this interaction, and OSA and central sleep apnea differ in their underlying mechanisms. Sleep duration is associated with a U-shaped change in heart rate, with lower values in short sleep and higher values in extended sleep. Myocardial infarction shows a morning peak,

with a threefold increased risk in the first hours after awakening and maximum incidence around 9 a.m.[3]. Vagal activation during apnoea and hypoxia in OSA leads to bradyarrhythmias, including sinus bradycardia, sinus arrest, and AV block. OSA prevalence is likely increasing due in part to rising obesity rates [4]. OSA involves episodic upper OSA is associated with concentric cardiac hypertrophy, with an odds ratio of 1.62 for left ventricular hypertrophy, and worsening oxygen desaturation correlates with increased ventricular remodeling.airway collapse during sleep, leading to transient decreases in intrathoracic airflow [5].

Objective: To present a clinical case of a patient with obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome and obesity as significant risk factors for myocardial infarction.

Case Report

A 61-year-old female was admitted to the LLP “Hadisha” Medical Center on 17 the January in 2026, with a diagnosis of Non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) of the lateral wall of the left ventricle. Acute stage. Complication: Killip class III heart failure. Ischaemic cardiomyopathy. Heart failure with improved ejection fraction (LVEF 45%). Grade III arterial hypertension, very high risk. Prediabetes. Chronic autoimmune thyroiditis. Moderate hypothyroidism. The patient complained of burning retrosternal chest pain at rest lasting up to 30 minutes, accompanied by shortness of breath and general weakness. The condition worsened over the course of one week. An echocardiography was performed, which showed an ejection fraction of 45%; however, no cardiology consultation was sought. Episodes of angina were self-managed with valerian. Coronary angiography (CAG) was recommended. In the medical history prior to myocardial infarction, the patient reported headaches, a sensation of shortness of breath, daytime sleepiness, and nocturnal apnoea and snoring. The patient had grade III obesity, with a body mass index (BMI) of 38 kg/m².

CAG findings:

- Left coronary artery:
- Left main stem: no significant lesions.
- LAD: bifurcation stenosis in the mid segment up to 90%, TIMI III flow.
- Diagonal branch 2: proximal stenosis up to 40%, TIMI III flow.
- LCx: distal segment stenosis of 60%, TIMI III flow.
- Obtuse marginal branch: ostial stenosis of 80%, TIMI III flow.
- Second obtuse marginal branch: proximal segment stenosis of 30%, TIMI III flow.

Right coronary artery: no significant stenoses, TIMI III flow. Posterior descending and posterolateral branches: no significant lesions.

Intervention:

It was decided to perform percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) of the LAD. A coronary guidewire (Asahi Sion Blue) was advanced into the distal LAD.

Balloon angioplasty was performed at the site of stenosis using a 2.0 × 15 mm Powerline balloon catheter at 10 atm. A BioMatrix Alpha 3.5 × 24 mm stent was then implanted in the mid LAD at 12 atm. Post-dilatation was performed using a 3.5 × 8 mm NC balloon at 20 atm. Final angiography showed TIMI III flow in the LAD. No complications were observed.

Outcome:

During follow-up, the patient's condition improved. No recurrent anginal pain or arrhythmias were noted, and there was no dyspnoea at rest. The patient tolerated physical rehabilitation well and was discharged in improved condition.

Table 1. Blood test results.

Date of completion	Test	Result	Unit
21.01.2026 08:13	NT-proBNP (N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide) in serum	1091.57	pg/mL
17.01.2026 23:11	Troponin I in serum	0.073	ng/mL
17.01.2026 17:33	Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c)	6.44	%
17.01.2026 13:41	D-dimer (quantitative, plasma)	0.32	µg/mL
17.01.2026 13:44	Troponin I in serum	0.091	ng/mL
17.01.2026 13:45	NT-proBNP (serum)	3818.24	pg/mL
17.01.2026 17:15	PT (prothrombin time)	11.15	sec
17.01.2026 17:24	Total cholesterol	7.87	mmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	LDL cholesterol	5.87	mmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	HDL cholesterol	1.34	mmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	Triglycerides	2.89	mmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	ALT	18.44	U/L
17.01.2026 17:24	AST	14.33	U/L
17.01.2026 17:24	Total protein	69	g/L
17.01.2026 17:24	Total bilirubin	9.7	µmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	Direct bilirubin	3.2	µmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	Urea	8	mmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	Creatinine	77.83	µmol/L
17.01.2026 17:24	CRP (C-reactive protein)	3.8	mg/L
17.01.2026 17:24	HbA1c	6.44	%
17.01.2026 19:35	Urinalysis (protein)	0.264	g/L

Brief interpretation of blood test abnormalities

• **Cardiac biomarkers:** Markedly elevated NT-proBNP (up to 3818 pg/mL) and mildly elevated troponin I (0.073–0.091 ng/mL), suggesting significant myocardial strain and possible myocardial injury.

• **Lipid profile:** Severe dyslipidemia with high total cholesterol (7.87 mmol/L), elevated LDL (5.87 mmol/L), and increased triglycerides (2.89 mmol/L), indicating high atherosclerotic cardiovascular risk.

• **Glucose metabolism:** HbA1c 6.44%, consistent with prediabetes or early type 2 diabetes.

• **Inflammation/coagulation:** Mildly elevated CRP (3.8 mg/L); D-dimer and PT within normal limits.

• **Renal involvement:** Normal creatinine with mild proteinuria (0.264 g/L), suggesting early renal involvement.

• **Liver function:** ALT, AST, and bilirubin within normal ranges.

Overall: Findings are consistent with significant cardiovascular strain with possible heart failure, high atherosclerotic risk, and early metabolic and renal involvement (Table 1).

Table 2. Echocardiography results:

Examination	Findings
Echocardiography	Dilatation of the left heart chambers
Mitral valve	Moderate mitral regurgitation (MR grade 2)
Tricuspid valve	Tricuspid regurgitation (TR grade 1+)
Left ventricular systolic function	Moderately reduced (LVEF by Simpson: 45%)
Regional wall motion	No hypo- or akinesia detected
Diastolic function	LV diastolic dysfunction type I
Right ventricle	No systolic dysfunction detected
Pericardium	No pathological changes

Echocardiography shows left heart chamber dilation with moderately reduced left ventricular systolic function (LVEF 45%), moderate mitral regurgitation and mild tricuspid regurgitation, along with grade I diastolic dysfunction, while right ventricular function and the pericardium are normal and no regional wall motion abnormalities are present (Table 2).

Medication therapy recommendations at hospital:

- Nitroglycerin spray (Isoket, Nitromint) as needed for chest pain
- Ticagrelor 90 mg: 1 tablet twice daily (08:00, 20:00) until 19.01.2027
- Acetylsalicylic acid 100 mg: 1 tablet once daily (19:00), long-term
- Pantoprazole 40 mg: 1 tablet once daily (07:30), 30 minutes before meals
- Perindopril/amlodipine/indapamide (Triplixam 10/2.5/10 mg): 1 tablet once daily (08:00), long-term
- Bisoprolol 5 mg: 1 tablet once daily (08:30), continuous use
- Rosuvastatin/Ezetimibe (Rozulip Plus 20/10 mg): 1 tablet once daily (20:00), long-term

- Dapagliflozin (Forxiga) 10 mg: 1 tablet once daily (10:00), continuous use
- Metformin (Glucophage) 850 mg: 1 tablet once daily (20:00), long-term

Picture 1. Polysomnography: Maximum oxygen saturation and apnea index.

Picture 2. Polysomnography: Minimum oxygen saturation and apnea index.

Polysomnography interpretation:

The patient was discharged from the hospital on 21.01.2026 in improved condition. On 15.02.2026, a sleep study was performed. **Results:** Severe obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome was diagnosed. The cardiac risk index (CRI) was 1.0 (high risk). Severe sleep-disordered breathing was identified with an apnea-hypopnea index (AHI) of 54.8 events/hour (normal <5/hour). The longest respiratory pause was 46 seconds. Minimum oxygen saturation was 57%, and average nocturnal

saturation was 92%. Automatic analysis revealed Cheyne-Stokes respiration patterns. High risk of cardiovascular events (Picture 1, 2).

Recommendations: CPAP therapy. Otolaryngology consultation to exclude an anatomical cause of sleep apnoea.

The patient underwent several courses of CPAP therapy, which led to a reduction in recurrent myocardial infarction episodes. In addition, weight reduction measures were implemented, including transition to a balanced diet and increased physical activity of 75–150 minutes per week. On examination by an otolaryngologist, macroglossia was identified, and the use of oral sleep appliances (mandibular advancement devices) was recommended.

Discussion. Thus, this clinical case of myocardial infarction in a patient with grade III obesity demonstrates the presence of obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome prior to the development of cardiovascular complications. The results of the sleep study confirm a high risk of myocardial infarction, stroke, and other adverse cardiovascular events in the context of severe hypoxia. The patient had previously ignored symptoms such as snoring, brief nocturnal breathing pauses, daytime sleepiness and headaches. Earlier sleep evaluation might have potentially prevented the development of arterial hypertension and myocardial infarction. This case highlights the key role of obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome (OSAS) in the development of arterial hypertension and cardiovascular events. CPAP therapy combined with the use of oral appliances helped reduce the frequency of apnoeic episodes and hypoxic events, thereby lowering the risk of repeat myocardial infarction and stroke and improving the patient's overall prognosis.

Obstructive sleep apnea is a disorder marked by repeated partial or complete collapse of the upper airway during sleep, resulting in sleep disruption and/or intermittent drops in blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂) [6]. These events usually last 10–30 seconds (up to several minutes in severe cases) and cause intermittent hypoxia, sleep fragmentation, hypercapnia, and intrathoracic pressure fluctuations. OSA is consistently recognized as an independent risk factor for cardiovascular disease, including coronary artery disease, stroke, myocardial infarction, heart failure, and arrhythmias such as atrial fibrillation [7]. Due to the repeated episodes of intermittent hypoxia, hypercapnia, and heightened sympathetic nervous system activity seen in obstructive sleep apnea (OSA), it has been suggested that OSA may influence a wide range of neural, metabolic, thrombotic, and inflammatory pathways involved in the development of cardiovascular disease (CVD) [8]. Obstructive sleep apnea is a severe and potentially fatal disorder. The National Commission on Sleep Disorders Research estimated that it may contribute to approximately 38,000 cardiovascular deaths each year, along with about 42 million dollars in healthcare costs related to hospital admissions [9]. Negative intrathoracic pressure increases left ventricular afterload and impairs its relaxation. It also

reduces cardiac contractility, leading to higher left ventricular volumes in both systole and diastole. In addition, hypoxia can directly disrupt energy-dependent myocardial contraction and relaxation processes [10].

Conclusion. This clinical case highlights obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome as an important, often underdiagnosed and modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular disease. In this patient, severe OSAS coexisted with obesity, metabolic disorders and advanced coronary artery disease, resulting in acute myocardial infarction and heart failure. Polysomnography confirmed severe sleep-disordered breathing with marked nocturnal hypoxaemia, underscoring the link between intermittent hypoxia and cardiovascular injury. Early diagnosis and treatment of OSAS, particularly CPAP therapy and lifestyle modification, may improve cardiovascular outcomes and reduce recurrent ischemic events. This case supports routine screening for sleep-disordered breathing in high-risk cardiovascular patients.

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Informed consent: *Written informed consent was obtained from the patients for publication of this case report.*

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向日葵杂交种根际纤维素分解细菌数量的动态变化取决于农业技术要素
**THE DYNAMICS OF THE NUMBER OF CELLULOLYTIC
BACTERIA IN THE RHIZOSPHERE OF SUNFLOWER HYBRIDS
DEPENDING ON THE ELEMENTS OF AGRICULTURAL
TECHNOLOGY**

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摘要：土壤中纤维素分解细菌的高丰度是一个积极的特征，因为已知这类微生物在自然界的碳循环中发挥着重要作用。本研究在西高加索地区淋溶黑钙土上，对向日葵生长季期间根际纤维素分解细菌种群的季节动态进行了研究。在整个向日葵生长季中，这类微生物的数量没有出现显著波动；它们的丰度与播种前非根际土壤中的水平相当，或高出1-2个数量级。土壤中这些细菌的高含量表明农业生产实践具有科学依据。

关键词：向日葵，根际，细菌，纤维素分解细菌，播种日期，播种量标准。

Abstract. *A high abundance of cellulolytic bacteria in the soil is a positive characteristic, as representatives of this group of microorganisms are known to play a principal role in the carbon cycle in nature. The seasonal dynamics of the population of cellulolytic bacteria in the sunflower agroecosystem were studied during the growing season of the crop on leached chernozem of the Western Pre-Caucasus. Throughout the entire growing season of sunflower, no significant fluctuations were observed in the number of this trophic group of microorganisms; their abundance corresponded to the levels found in non-rhizosphere soil before sowing or exceeded them by 1–2 orders of magnitude. A high content of these bacteria in the soil indicates scientifically justified agricultural practices in farming.*

Keywords: *sunflower, rhizosphere, bacteria, cellulolytic bacteria, sowing date, seeding rate norm.*

The rhizosphere is the zone of most intense microorganism development, acting as a biological buffer that regulates the interactions between higher plants and the soil and its resident microorganisms; the assemblage of microorganisms inhabiting the rhizosphere is referred to as the rhizosphere microflora [1; 2; 3]. Microbial biodiversity is important for enhancing plant resistance to abiotic environmental factors and pathogenic microorganisms [4; 5]. The assemblage of microorganisms performing the same function in the soil substance transformation chain is called physiological groups [6]. Among the most prominent physiological groups in microbiological research are cellulolytic bacteria, which participate in carbon cycling processes, since up to 70% of the carbon entering the soil with plant residues consists of cellulose and hemicellulose [7]. The greatest influence on the abundance of microorganisms in the rhizosphere of field crops among the complex of agricultural practices is exerted by: soil type, composition of applied agrochemicals, soil cultivation technology, and the intensity of the agricultural technologies applied [8; 9; 10; 11; 12].

The aim of our research was to study the dynamics of the population of cellulolytic bacteria in the rhizosphere of sunflower depending on various agronomic practices: sowing time and seeding rate norm of different sunflower hybrids.

The studies were conducted in 2024–2025. on leached chernozem soil of the Western Fore-Caucasus at the agrotechnological department of FSBSI FNC VNIIMK (Krasnodar) within a three-factor field experiment, where: factor A – sunflower hybrid: the mid-season Surus and mid-early Lavrus; factor B – sowing date: a total of four dates – the first at the attainment of the optimal soil temperature (10–12 °C) at the depth of seed placement, and subsequently at intervals of 14–17 days; C – seeding rate norm: recommended – 60 thousand pcs/ha (control) and increased – 80 thousand pcs/ha. The field experiment was conducted in three replicates, plot arrangement – systematic, experimental plot area 56 m². Soil

samples from the sunflower rhizosphere were collected in accordance with GOST 17.4.3.01–83 and soil microbiology methods. Microorganisms were quantified by the titration method. The result was expressed as the number of colony-forming units per gram of dry soil (CFU/g).

The population size of cellulolytic bacteria in soil samples taken before the sunflower sowing in 2024 was 3.8×10^5 CFU/g, and in 2025– 2.0×10^6 CFU/g. The cluster of cellulolytic bacteria was identified, and the isolates were assigned to the genera *Bacillus* Cohn, *Pseudomonas* Migula, and *Cellulomonas* Bergey et al.

The dynamics of the quantitative ratio of cellulolytic bacteria during the vegetation period in the rhizosphere of sunflower hybrids at the first sowing date were atypical for this trophic group. Thus, in the 4–6 true leaf phase, a high bacterial count was observed – $0.8–9.7 \times 10^7$ CFU/g in 2024, and $3.3–7.3 \times 10^8$ CFU/g in 2025. In 2024, at the beginning of the budding phase, their number decreased to $0.6–2.6 \times 10^6$, and in the flowering phase increased to $2.0–6.7 \times 10^7$ CFU/g, followed by a decrease in the ripening phase to $1.3 \times 10^6–1.2 \times 10^7$ CFU/g. In 2025, A decrease in the number of cellulolytic bacteria was also observed by the beginning of the sunflower budding phase, followed by stabilization at a level of $0.1–6.2 \times 10^7$ CFU/g up to maturation (table).

Table – Number of cellulolytic bacteria in the rhizosphere of sunflower hybrids by vegetation phases depending on sowing dates and seed rates, CFU/g CEB FSBSI FNTS VNIIMK, 2024–2025.

Variant			Growth phase							
sowing date	hybrid	seeding rate norm, thousand pes/ha	4–6 true leaves		beginning budding		flowering		ripening	
			before sowing: 2024– 3.8×10^5 ; 2025– 2.0×10^6							
			2024	2025	2024	2025	2024	2025	2024	2025
First	Surus	60	1.2×10^7	3.3×10^8	1.4×10^6	2.4×10^6	6.7×10^7	6.0×10^6	1.2×10^7	2.7×10^6
		80	8.3×10^6	7.3×10^8	2.6×10^6	5.1×10^7	2.0×10^7	1.7×10^7	1.3×10^6	1.1×10^6
	Lavrus	60	4.0×10^7	6.0×10^8	2.0×10^6	8.0×10^5	2.1×10^7	3.9×10^6	6.7×10^6	3.6×10^6
		80	9.4×10^7	7.2×10^8	5.6×10^5	6.2×10^7	3.8×10^7	1.9×10^6	1.2×10^7	2.3×10^7
Second	Surus	60	4.4×10^6	3.1×10^6	5.1×10^6	2.1×10^5	2.0×10^7	1.6×10^7	8.0×10^6	1.0×10^7
		80	5.0×10^6	2.5×10^6	5.3×10^6	2.1×10^7	2.6×10^7	7.6×10^6	1.3×10^7	5.1×10^6
	Lavrus	60	3.5×10^6	2.5×10^6	3.8×10^6	1.3×10^7	1.3×10^7	7.5×10^6	6.7×10^6	4.8×10^6
		80	4.9×10^6	2.1×10^6	7.0×10^6	8.3×10^6	2.7×10^7	9.1×10^6	5.3×10^6	2.8×10^6

Third	Surus	60	2.7×10^6	2.5×10^7	8.2×10^6	1.7×10^6	2.1×10^7	2.3×10^6	5.3×10^6	3.5×10^6
		80	1.6×10^6	1.2×10^6	6.1×10^6	3.5×10^6	1.5×10^7	3.3×10^6	5.3×10^6	1.8×10^7
	Lavrus	60	3.0×10^6	2.3×10^6	6.0×10^6	3.2×10^6	8.8×10^7	2.0×10^6	2.9×10^6	5.4×10^6
		80	4.3×10^6	1.1×10^6	6.3×10^6	8.3×10^5	7.9×10^7	1.7×10^6	4.7×10^6	2.3×10^7
Fourth	Surus	60	6.1×10^5	1.9×10^7	1.9×10^7	4.0×10^6	2.7×10^6	4.0×10^5	1.6×10^7	1.5×10^6
		80	8.3×10^5	9.3×10^6	4.7×10^7	3.2×10^6	2.8×10^6	4.0×10^5	9.3×10^6	3.7×10^6
	Lavrus	60	4.9×10^5	1.0×10^6	1.6×10^7	3.2×10^6	1.5×10^6	4.0×10^5	1.3×10^7	5.9×10^6
		80	4.9×10^6	9.7×10^6	1.9×10^7	6.5×10^6	4.0×10^6	1.2×10^6	1.4×10^7	2.0×10^7

The minimum concentration of cellulolytic bacteria in the rhizosphere of sunflower hybrids during the experiment was recorded in 2024. at the fourth sowing date in the phase of 4–6 true leaves (4.9 – 8.3×10^5 CFU/g). At the same time, the period of peak development for these bacteria occurred at the beginning of sunflower budding (1.6 – 4.9×10^7 CFU/g). Subsequently, during the flowering phase, a decrease in their abundance was observed to 2.8 – 4.5×10^6 CFU/g, and during the ripening phase, an increase to 0.9 – 1.6×10^7 CFU/g. At the second and third sowing dates in 2024. The dynamics of cellulolytic bacteria abundance in the sunflower rhizosphere were identical. Thus, at the stages of 4–6 true leaves and the onset of sunflower budding, their abundance remained consistent at 1.6 – 7.0×10^6 CFU/g, whereas during flowering a more active proliferation was observed (1.3 – 8.8×10^7 CFU/g), exhibiting cultivar-specific variation: the Lavrus hybrid demonstrated the highest bacterial cell concentration in the study (7.9 – 8.8×10^7 CFU/g). At the maturation phase, a decrease in the number of bacteria of the studied group was noted, reaching 2.9 – 1.3×10^6 CFU/g. In 2025, a similar dynamic in the abundance of bacteria within this trophic group was observed for the second sowing time, whereas for the third and fourth sowing times, the number of cellulolytic bacteria remained stable throughout the entire growing season (0.1 – 2.3×10^7 CFU/g). An exception was observed during sampling in the flowering phase of sunflower, where bacterial titers decreased by one order of magnitude (4.0 – 10.0×10^5 CFU/g).

In the course of analyzing the microbial community of cellulolytic bacteria in the rhizosphere of two sunflower hybrids during the 2024–2025 growing seasons, under various sowing dates and seeding rates, it was established that the bacterial populations in the rhizosphere exhibit abundance comparable to the baseline levels of non-rhizosphere soil prior to sowing or exceed these by 1–2 orders of magnitude. The obtained results align with those of other researchers who observe the dynamics of the rhizosphere microbial community depending on the stage of plant development.

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斑点乳蓟多倍体品系的形态特征
**MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF POLYPLOID LINES
OF SPOTTED MILK THISTLE**

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摘要。本研究于2023年和2025年对斑点水飞蓟的多倍体品系进行了全面的形态性状评估。结果表明，与原始二倍体相比，多倍体品系植株更高，增幅为7%至120%。多倍体品系每株植物的主茎和花序数量随年份变化，与对照组相比未观察到明显的数量规律。多倍体品系的花头直径与对照组相当或更大。多倍体品系的叶片厚度是二倍体的1.3至2.5倍。多倍体品系每个显微视野中的气孔数量约为二倍体的一半；气孔大小增大10%至20%；气孔保卫细胞中的叶绿体数量比原始二倍体高37%至142%。

关键词。斑点水飞蓟、多倍体、形态特征、株高、主茎数、花序数、花序直径、气孔、叶绿体。

Abstract. *Polyploid lines of spotted milk thistle were evaluated for a comprehensive set of morphological traits in 2023 and 2025. It was established that polyploid lines were taller compared to the original diploid form, with increases ranging from 7 to 120%. The number of primary shoots and inflorescences per plant in polyploid forms varied by year, and no clear numerical pattern was observed relative to the control. The diameter of the flower heads in polyploid lines was at the control level or greater. Leaf thickness in polyploids was 1.3 to 2.5 times greater than in diploids. The number of stomata per microscopic field of view in polyploids was approximately two times lower; stomata size was 10–20% larger; the number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of stomata was 37–142% higher compared to the original diploid form.*

Keywords: *Spotted milk thistle, polyploids, morphological traits, plant height, number of primary shoots, number of inflorescences, inflorescence diameter, stomata, chloroplasts.*

Spotted milk thistle *Silybum marianum* (L.) Gaertn. – a medicinal plant of the Asteraceae family. Its seeds are of particular medicinal importance, containing approximately 200 biochemical components, including flavonoids such as silymarin, silybin, and others. It is widely used for the treatment and prevention of liver diseases (Aprosina, 1981; Podymova, 1998). However, in recent years, spotted milk thistle has been increasingly applied in the food industry owing to the presence in its seeds of valuable biochemical substances: up to 32 % fatty oil, 27 % protein comprising 18 amino acids, up to 26 % fiber, as well as microelements and vitamins; In cosmetology, owing to the regenerative properties of the raw material (Pospelov S. V., Samorodov V. N., Kislichenko V. S., Ostapchuk A. A., 2008).

Given the high mortality rate from liver diseases in Transnistria, the inclusion of spotted milk thistle in the Registry of plants authorized for use in the republic is pertinent (Andrus S. N., Volkova J. I., 2001; Volkova L. V., Dolgov Yu. A., Andrus S. P., Andrus L. N., 2002; Andrus, Gaidey, 2005).

Consequently, there is a need to develop a cultivar of spotted milk thistle suitable for cultivation under the environmental conditions of Transnistria.

Polyploidy is one of the methods, alongside selection and hybridization, for creating new cultivars of various agricultural crops.

In 2015, polyploid lines of spotted milk thistle were developed.

The aim of this study is to evaluate polyploid lines of spotted milk thistle, obtained using an aqueous colchicine solution, based on morphological characteristics.

The objectives of the research included:

1. Characterize the polyploid lines according to the traits of bush architecture:
 - plant height, cm;
 - number of primary shoots, pcs. per plant;
 - number of inflorescences per plant, pcs. per plant.
2. Account for:
 - leaf thickness, mm;
 - number of stomata within the microscope field of view, pcs;
 - stomatal size, mm;
 - number of chloroplasts in stomatal guard cells, pcs.

Materials and methods

Tetraploid lines of spotted milk thistle were used for the study, obtained in 2015, and compared with the original diploid form.

Tetraploid lines were sown in three replicates compared to the control. Sowing date: March 21, 2023. and March 24, 2025; sowing scheme: (90 x 20) cm. The plot area was 1.8 m².

Leaf thickness was measured using an electronic caliper. A biological microscope was used to count the number of stomata, their size, and the number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of stomata.

Mathematical data processing was performed using analysis of variance (Dospikhov, 1985).

Research Results

The morphological traits examined in the spotted milk thistle lines include architectural characteristics of the shrub: plant height, the number of first-order shoots and inflorescences, as well as the number of stomata within the microscope field of view, their size, and the number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of the stomata.

Analysis of the trait ‘plant height’ indicated that in 2023, this parameter in the polyploid lines ranged from 45.7±4.9 cm in Line 5/15 to 95.6±7.6 cm in Line 10/15, compared to 42.7±5.9 cm in the control. The increase relative to the control ranged from 7.0% to 123.9%. In 2025, the trend remained consistent – the trait values were higher, ranging from 51.0±8.1 cm to 106.2±6.0 cm in polyploid lines, compared to the control value of 48.0±3.1 cm, representing an increase of 6.3–121.3% (Table 1).

Table 1. Plant height of spotted milk thistle, ATP experimental field

No.	Sample designation	Plant height (cm)	
		2023	2025
1	Control – diploid	42.7±5.9	48.0±3.1
2	Line 5/15	45.7±4.9	65.0±2.1
3	Line 6/15	47.8±4.8	51.6±4.1
4	Line 7/15	94.0±7.2	106.2±6.0
5	Line 12/15	47.2±9.1	51.0±8.1
6	Line 13/15	59.1±4.4	59.0±2.4
7	Line 15/15	79.0±5.5	87.6±4.8
8	Line 23/15	54.4±4.8	54.8±3.9
9	Line 24/15	60.4±4.1	61.2±3.3
10	Line 29/15	86.0±5.9	92.2±6.9
11	Line 30/15	86.7±4.3	95.6±5.3
12	Line 35/15	81.7±4.3	83.6±6.1
13	Line 35–1/15	64.3±8.4	66.2±6.3
14	Line 7–1/15	82.6±6.7	88.8±6.2
15	Line 10/15	95.6±7.6	99.2±6.1
16	Line 13–1/15	52.4±8.6	67.6±3.2

The number of primary shoots in all polyploid lines in 2023 exceeded that of the diploid form. The trait variation ranged from 2.0 ± 0.4 shoots in Line 13–1/15 to 4.7 ± 0.8 shoots in Line 10/15, compared to 1.8 ± 0.6 shoots in the control; the trait exceeded the control by 11.1–161.1%. In 2025, the trait exceeded that of the control only in five polyploid lines out of the 15 studied, representing 33.3%. The trait varied from 2.8 ± 0.2 to 4.4 ± 1.0 shoots per plant (Table 2).

Table 2. Number of first-order shoots in polyploid lines of spotted milk thistle

No.	Sample designation	Average number of first-order shoots per plant (pcs./plant)	
		2023	2025
1	Control – diploid	1.8 ± 0.6	3.2 ± 0.2
2	Line 5/15	3.7 ± 1.3	3.0 ± 0.3
3	Line 6/15	2.4 ± 0.5	2.8 ± 0.2
4	Line 7/15	3.9 ± 0.7	4.2 ± 0.8
5	Line 12/15	2.8 ± 1.0	3.2 ± 0.7
6	Line 13/15	2.3 ± 0.3	3.0 ± 0.3
7	Line 15/15	3.3 ± 0.8	3.8 ± 0.8
8	Line 23/15	3.4 ± 1.0	3.0 ± 0.3
9	Line 24/15	2.8 ± 0.4	2.6 ± 0.4
10	Line 29/15	3.4 ± 0.4	3.6 ± 0.4
11	Line 30/15	2.9 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.2
12	Line 35/15	2.6 ± 0.3	2.8 ± 0.2
13	Line 35–1/15	3.0 ± 0.7	3.0 ± 0.3
14	Line 7–1/15	2.3 ± 0.4	2.8 ± 0.4
15	Line 10/15	4.7 ± 0.8	4.4 ± 1.0
16	Line 13–1/15	2.0 ± 0.4	2.2 ± 0.2

Table 3. Number of inflorescences in polyploid lines of spotted milk thistle

No.	Sample designation	Average number of inflorescences per plant (pcs./plant)	
		2023	2025
1	Control – diploid	2.8 ± 0.6	5.2 ± 0.4
2	Line 5/15	4.7 ± 1.3	4.8 ± 0.4
3	Line 6/15	3.4 ± 0.5	4.2 ± 0.5
4	Line 7/15	5.3 ± 0.8	6.4 ± 1.0
5	Line 12/15	4.4 ± 1.6	5.0 ± 1.3
6	Line 13/15	3.4 ± 0.3	4.0 ± 0.3
7	Line 15/15	4.7 ± 1.2	5.6 ± 1.1

No.	Sample designation	Average number of inflorescences per plant (pcs./plant)	
		2023	2025
8	Line 23/15	4.6±1.2	4.4±0.5
9	Line 24/15	3.8±0.4	4.0±0.3
10	Line 29/15	4.5±0.5	5.2±0.5
11	Line 30/15	4.1±0.4	4.8±0.4
12	Line 35/15	3.6±0.3	4.2±0.4
13	Line 35–1/15	5.3±1.9	4.6±0.7
14	Line 7–1/15	3.4±0.5	4.0±0.5
15	Line 10/15	6.3±1.1	6.2±1.1
16	Line 13–1/15	3.0±0.4	3.0±0.0

In 2023, the number of inflorescences per plant was higher in all studied polyploid lines compared to the control. The number of inflorescences per plant in polyploid lines varied from 3.0±0.4 in Line 13–1/15 to 6.3±1.1 in Line 10/15, while the control showed a value of 2.8±0.6, representing an increase ranging from 7.1 to 125%. In 2025, only three polyploid lines showed an increase in the average number of inflorescences per plant (Table 3).

The diameter of the inflorescences (capitula) on spotted milk thistle plants in polyploid lines ranged from 4.1±0.3 cm in Line 5/15 to 5.4±0.3 cm in Line 35–1/15, compared to 4.0±0.3 cm in the control, representing an increase of 2.5–35%. In 2025, the diameter of the capitula in polyploid lines was at or above the control level, except for the measurement observed in Line 13/15. Trait variation ranged from 3.9±0.2 cm to 5.1±0.2 cm (Table 4).

Table 4. Inflorescence diameter of polyploid lines of spotted milk thistle

No.	Sample designation	Inflorescence diameter, cm	
		2023	2025
1	Control – diploid	4.0±0.3	4.2±0.2
2	Line 5/15	4.1±0.3	4.2±0.3
3	Line 6/15	5.1±0.3	4.5±0.3
4	Line 7/15	4.9±0.2	4.8±0.2
5	Line 12/15	4.3±0.2	4.2±0.2
6	Line 13/15	4.2±0.2	3.9±0.2
7	Line 15/15	4.4±0.2	4.3±0.2
8	Line 23/15	4.3±0.2	4.2±0.2
9	Line 24/15	4.2±0.2	4.4±0.3
10	Line 29/15	4.9±0.2	4.9±0.2
11	Line 30/15	4.7±0.1	4.6±0.3

No.	Sample designation	Inflorescence diameter, cm	
		2023	2025
12	Line 35/15	4.5±0.2	4.3±0.2
13	Line 35–1/15	5.4±0.3	5.1±0.2
14	Line 7–1/15	5.0±0.2	4.6±0.3
15	Line 10/15	5.0±0.2	4.4±0.1
16	Line 13–1/15	4.4±0.3	4.5±0.3

Leaf thickness in polyploids, measured with an electronic caliper, exceeds that of diploids by a factor of 1.3 to 2.5 (Table 5).

Table 5. Leaf thickness in spotted milk thistle plants

Genotype	Leaf thickness, mm	Range (leaf thickness), mm
Control, ‘Pervenets of Transnistria’ cultivar (diploid)	0.39	0.32–0.46
Milk thistle without spots (diploid)	0.21	0.16–0.28
Polyploid (tetraploid)	0.52	0.43–0.57

The number of stomata in the microscope field of view in polyploids is approximately half that of the diploid form, ranging from 5.0±0.3 to 9.6±0.5 per field, compared to 10.4±0.3 in the control; stomata size is 10–20% larger, varying from 0.027±0.0009 mm to 0.039±0.001 mm, whereas in the control it is 0.032±0.0002 mm; the number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of stomata is 37–142% greater, ranging from 13.5±0.7 upwards, up to 25.5±0.6–25.5±1.0 units with a control value of 10.5±0.3 units (Table 6; Figs. 1, 2).

Table 6. Characteristics of stomata in spotted milk thistle

Plot number	Sample designation	Number of stomata per microscope field of view	Stomata size, mm	Number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of stomata
1	Control – diploid	10.4±0.3	0.032±0.0002	10.5±0.3
2	Line 5/15	5.0±0.3	0.039±0.001	18.8±1.6
3	Line 6/15	7.6±0.3	0.036±0.0004	25.5±0.6
4	Line 7/15	5.7±0.3	0.034±0.001	19.9±1.0
5	Line 12/15	8.1±0.3	0.037±0.001	18.1±0.8
6	Line 13/15	8.4±0.3	0.031±0.0009	14.4±0.7
7	Line 15/15	6.1±0.4	0.035±0.0004	21.1±0.7
8	Line 23/15	7.2±0.3	0.032±0.001	16.9±0.6

Plot number	Sample designation	Number of stomata per microscope field of view	Stomata size, mm	Number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of stomata
9	Line 24/15	6.4±0.4	0.033±0.001	18.7±0.6
10	Line 29/15	7.6±0.4	0.033±0.001	13.6±0.3
11	Line 30/15	9.6±0.5	0.027±0.0009	13.5±0.7
12	Line 35/15	6.6±0.3	0.035±0.001	25.5±1.0
13	Line 35-1/15	6.6±0.3	0.035±0.001	25.5±1.0
15	Line 7-1/15	5.7±0.3	0.034±0.001	19.9±1.0
16	Line 10/15	7.7±0.4	0.031±0.0003	16.2±0.8
18	Line 13-1/15	6.0±0.4	0.036±0.0004	15.7±0.4

Fig. 1. Stomata on leaves of spotted milk thistle in the diploid form – control, 800-fold magnification

Fig. 2. Stomata on leaves of spotted milk thistle in the tetraploid form, 800-fold magnification

Conclusions

1. Polyploid lines are taller compared to the baseline diploid form, with increases ranging from 7 to 120%.
2. The number of primary shoots and inflorescences per plant in polyploid forms varied from year to year, and there is no clear trend in the numerical expression of these traits compared to the control.
3. The diameter of the capitula in the polyploid lines was equal to or greater than that of the control.

4. Leaves of polyploids are thicker than those of diploids by a factor of 1.3 to 2.5.

5. The number of stomata per microscopic field of view in polyploids was approximately two times lower; stomata size was 10–20% larger; The number of chloroplasts in the guard cells of stomata is 37–142% greater compared to the baseline diploid form.

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